

Digital
Facilitator
Trainer Role

THE DIGITAL FACILITATOR TRAINER ROLE

**HARNESSING AI, GAMIFICATION AND
DATA ANALYSIS IN VET DIGITAL
FACILITATION**

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Cooperation for innovation and exchange of good practices

VET – Vocational Education and Training

DIGITAL FACILITATOR TRAINER ROLE

DigiFact

Harnessing AI, Gamification and Data Analysis in

VET Digital Facilitation

Information

Project number	2020-1-TR01-KA226-VET-097638
Project coordinator	Osmaniye İl Milli Eğitim Müdürlüğü, Turkey
Partners	Femxa Formación S.L.U., Spain TEAM Excellence, Romania
Intellectual output	IO2: Open Digital Community
Activity	Create educational materials to support VET Digital Facilitators
Derivable authors	Osmaniye İl Milli Eğitim Müdürlüğü, Turkey Femxa Formación S.L.U., Spain TEAM4Excellence, Romania

Acknowledgement

This paper has received funding from the European Commission under the Grant Agreement number 2020-1-TR01-KA226-VET-097638, ERASMUS+ Strategic Partnership project “Digital Facilitator Trainer Role”.

Disclaimer

The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the content which reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Copyright notice

© 2021 - 2023 DigiFact Consortium

The licence **Attribution CC BY** lets others distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licences offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.

Contents

DigiFacT Model Course.....	4
Introduction.....	4
VET Digital facilitator competence map.....	4
Gamification, Data analysis and Artificial Intelligence tools	5
VET Digital facilitation into practice: The 5E Model.....	5
Course aim and objectives	5
Entry standards (prerequisites).....	5
Staff requirements	6
Teaching facilities and aids.....	6
Course outline	6
Teaching syllabus (and training outcomes).....	7
Evaluation method and recognition system	8
VET digital facilitator competence map	9
Area of competence 1: Professional Engagement	10
Area of competence 2: Digital Resources	16
Area of competence 3: Teaching and Learning.....	21
Area of competence 4: Assessment	28
Area of competence 5: Empowering Learners.....	32
Area of competence 6: Facilitating Learners’ Digital Competence.....	38
Gamification	46
What is gamification.....	46
Gamification tools	48
Kahoot	48
BookWidgets	49
PlayBrighter	51
Kialo Edu.....	52
Quizlet	53
Skills and competences for using gamification tools	54
Artificial intelligence.....	57
What is artificial intelligence	57
Artificial intelligence tools.....	58
Alexa Skill Blueprints	58

IBM SkillsBuild	60
Chatfuel	61
Gradescope.....	62
Linguaskill	63
Skills and competences for using artificial intelligence tools.....	65
Data analysis.....	67
What is data analysis.....	67
Data Analysis tools	68
Easyclass	68
Plickers.....	70
Lessons Plan - Symbaloo.....	71
Socrative	72
Eduflow – Peer Review	74
Skills and competences for using data analysis tools.....	75
VET digital facilitation into practice. The 5E Model	78
1. Engage	80
2. Explore.....	85
3. Explain	91
4. Elaborate	99
5. Evaluate	106
Recommendations for instructional designers and facilitators	112
Course evaluation quiz	113
Use cases for digital facilitation in VET.....	114
Gamification use case.....	114
Artificial intelligence use case	115
Data analysis use case	115
Conclusions.....	116
About the partner organisations.....	117
Bibliography.....	118
Appendix 1 Evaluation quiz check sheet	121

DigiFacT Model Course

Introduction

The use of digital content in education worldwide was relatively uncommon before the COVID-19 crisis started. Only 20% of countries had digital learning resources in teaching, and a mere 10 percent of countries had more robust digital learning capabilities offering some of the educational materials available outside of the classroom.

According to the World Bank, no country has a universal digital curriculum for teaching and learning. These numbers paint a picture of the efforts that governments and schools had to take to rapidly move to distance learning to ensure continuity of learning. The other part of the equation is how educational institutions are equipped for online learning, and how well teachers are prepared for and engaged in online teaching. Teachers need to quickly adjust their teaching methods and learning expectations. Is in this context that the figure of the digital facilitator trainer (DFT) became necessary.

We detected that in some countries the educational entities took charge of the demand for training by implementing virtual classrooms and telematic media, and the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), gamification, and data analysis for the improvement of educational services. During the Pandemic, AI became an instrument of measurement parameters that we didn't pay attention to before, for instance, a good example in Spain was the inclusion of new AI tools into final university examinations to avoid cheating.

Gamification (GA) is another innovative methodology that is making its way into the VET community, as an efficient tool to engage and motivate learners during online training. The quality of gamification techniques and digital tools is improving year by year, making it essential to include gamification in the Digital Facilitator Trainer model.

Finally, we included Data analysis (DA), since we also detected a pre-existing gap in the use of data to improve the learning models. Data analysis presents an especially effective solution to improve, monitor, and assess teaching in online settings.

Additionally, the consortium detected in a previous analysis the lack of high-quality digital content to improve the digital skills of educators that are available both in English and in the partners' languages (Spanish, Turkish, Romanian).

In this context, the DigiFacT project has the following objectives:

- Developing a new methodology that answers the needs of vocational and education trainers in the countries part of the DigiFacT consortium (Turkey, Romania, and Spain) and in the EU.
- Creating an innovative new figure, a Digital Facilitator Trainer (DFT), with digital pedagogical skills and knowledge enough to “train the trainers”, especially in the areas of AI, gamification and Data analysis.
- Fostering innovative learning opportunities and providing learning materials for professional development for VET teachers and trainers interested in improving their digital skills. The DFT course comprises a toolbox of non-formal education methods using digital resources and tools, available in EN and own languages (TR, RO, ES).

Following these objectives, the Digital Facilitator Trainer course is made up of these key components:

VET Digital facilitator competence map

The competence map shows the digital skills required in any educator to become a digital facilitator and introduce digital skills in their teaching to enhance the learning experience of their students. It is

aimed to help educators understand and assess the digital skills they require, identify their needs and gaps, and work towards improving their competencies.

The DigiFacT Competence Map uses the European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu) as their reference document. The DigCompEdu Framework is a scientifically sound framework describing what it means for educators to be digitally competent. It provides a general reference frame to support the development of educator-specific digital competences in Europe.

Gamification, Data analysis and Artificial Intelligence tools

The DigiFacT course is composed of three modules designed to improve teachers' knowledge in the use of tools that incorporate gamification, data analysis and artificial intelligence methodologies, the identified key areas to train a digital facilitator. These modules are made up of practical guidelines to a wide range of tools, free and accessible, that teachers can easily introduce into their educational practice.

VET Digital facilitation into practice: The 5E Model

The last component of the DFT course is a comprehensive approach to digital facilitation implementing the 5E model of instructional design. The 5E Model has been used to help frame the sequence and organisation of programs, units, and lessons and consists of the following phases: engagement, exploration, explanation, elaboration, and evaluation. Each phase has a specific function and contributes to the trainer's coherent instruction and the students' getting better understanding of scientific and technological knowledge, attitudes, and skills. The DFT course guides educators on how to incorporate the 5E Model into their teaching and use digital tools as a support to facilitate teaching&learning at every stage of instruction.

Course aim and objectives

This course aims to improve the knowledge and skills of VET educators to become digital facilitators. The main objectives are strongly related to the course components:

- Comprehend the competences -values, knowledge, and skills- required in VET educators today to become digital ones.
- Get to know the common challenges, gaps and needs faced by educators at the European level when approaching digital training.
- Improve their knowledge and understanding of gamification, data analysis and Artificial Intelligence.
- Gain practical knowledge on specific digital tools for GA, AI, and DA and how to incorporate them into their classrooms.
- Learn the principles of instruction and how to implement the 5E Model to create a unique learning experience for students.
- Learn how to incorporate digital tools in the instruction process.

Entry standards (prerequisites)

The most important prerequisite to join this attend this course and join is the desire to acquire knowledge, skills and attitudes related to what involves creating and facilitating vocational education and training in the digital environment.

This course is specially created for VET digital facilitators and trainers who contribute directly to educational activities and want to use digital technology in their teaching and training. Although it is not a prerequisite, it would be helpful for course attendants to have previous knowledge or practice with digital tools. Likewise, prior competences in Gamification, Data Analysis and Artificial Intelligence are not required but may prove useful.

Staff requirements

This course is available online free of charge in MOOC format but may also be delivered or facilitated. The course facilitators are VET teachers, trainers and facilitators who have pedagogical competences as well as knowledge, experience and skills in the area of digital education, including in the field of Gamification, Data Analysis and Artificial Intelligence.

As the modules of the online course can also be taught during a presential course, the staff requirements for the trainers leading this course are the following:

- Previous experience in vocational education and training
- Ability to transfer knowledge, and skills and encourage positive attitudes
- Ability to create engaging methods to deliver the theoretical content of the modules

Teaching facilities and aids

To implement the course face-to-face, we recommend the following teaching facilities and aids:

- Non-electronic – Chalkboards/ flip board, flipcharts, chalk/markers, course handouts, copies of the evaluation sheets
- Electronic/digital – Computer, video projector, clicker devices, speakers; internet, course materials in electronic form and the relevant software (e.g. MS Office, PDF reader, video/audio player)

Course outline

Knowledge

Trainees should acquire knowledge of:

- Requirements for educators reflected on the DigCompEdu Framework of the EU
- Professional Engagement for VET educators
- Digital Resources
- Teaching and learning process.
- Understanding of student assessment
- Gamification tools and methodologies
- Data analysis tools and methodologies
- Artificial Intelligence tools
- Instructional design
- The 5E model of instruction

Skills

Trainees should be competent in:

- Empowering learners through digital means
- Facilitating learners' digital competences
- Search and select the digital tools that are best suited to their needs.
- Incorporating digital tools into their teaching practices

- Gamify their learning resources to motivate and engage students.
- Incorporate data analysis techniques to monitor and assist students.
- Using AI to improve and facilitate teaching&learning
- Improve their instructional design abilities.

Attitudes

Trainees should:

- Understand the change of paradigm in education worldwide and the necessity for all educators to become digital facilitators.
- Be aware of the DigCompEdu Framework of the EU, its aims, goals and the competencies it addresses.
- Recognize the gaps and needs found in vocational education and training regarding opportunities to improve the digital skills of educators.
- Be open and willing to improve and adapt their teaching techniques in order to address the needs of students regarding digitalization.
- Be aware of the vast amounts of digital tools available online for free and the importance of exploring and choosing carefully
- Understand how the usage of digital tools can be harmful or detrimental and the importance of considering students' needs and level of digital knowledge when incorporating them into their courses.
- Recognize the benefits of gamification, data analysis and artificial intelligence tools and processes in education.

Teaching syllabus (and training outcomes)

The teaching syllabus was created based on Bloom's Taxonomy, ensuring gradual learning from theory to practice.

Bloom's Taxonomy comprises three learning domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor, and assigns to each of these domains a hierarchy that corresponds to different levels of learning. There are six levels of cognitive learning according to the revised version of Bloom's Taxonomy. Each level is conceptually different. The six levels are remembering, understanding, applying, analysing, evaluating, and creating.

The five modules were created on these six levels of gradually learning from theory to practice:

VET digital facilitator competence map: six competence areas (professional engagement, digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment, empowering learners and facilitating learners' digital competence). Each area is further refined in 3 dimensions: what is and why is important, the needs of VET educators and specific competences.

Gamification: what is gamification; tools for digital gamification (Kahoot, BookWidgets, PlayBrighter, Kailo Edu and Quizlet) and the skills and competences needed for using those tools.

Artificial Intelligence: what is artificial intelligence; tools using artificial intelligence (Alexa Skill Blueprints, IBM SkillsBuild, Chatfuel, Gradescope and Linguaskills) and the skills and competences needed for using those tools.

Data Analysis: what is data analysis; tools for data analysis (Easyclass, Plickers, Lessons Plan - Symbaloo, Socrative and Edulflow) and the skills and competences needed for using data analysis tools.

Each of the specific chapters (Gamification, Artificial Intelligence and Data Analysis) includes resources and further reading, references to video materials and self-reflection questions.

In its online version, the course also includes slide presentations, course materials with text and images, and video summaries (with audio).

Evaluation method and recognition system

At the end of the course, there are **10 multiple-choice questions**. These questions are meant to **evaluate the acquired knowledge and skills** at the end of the course. However, in terms of **evaluating attitudes**, we **encourage self-reflection** during, but especially after the completion of the course in situations related to using gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis.

The recommended time of evaluation for each module is **10 minutes**. (1 min per MCQ).

Participants receive badges at the end of the gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis.

VET digital facilitator competence map

DigiFacT addresses a huge gap in the VET community in Europe, the lack of digital learning resources in teaching, essential to help educators to develop their own digital skills, with the ultimate purpose of engaging their students and providing them with the key knowledge and skills in the digital era.

The goal of this report is to offer a map of digital competences required in VET educators today, following the state-of-the-art of digital education, the recommendations of the DigCompEdu Framework by the European Commission, and the prior findings of the research developed as part of the project.

Competency mapping is the process of identifying the specific skills, knowledge, abilities, and behaviours required to operate effectively in a specific trade, profession, or job position. Competency maps are often referred to as competency profiles or skills profiles.

Specifically, in the field of education, maps are how skills and competencies, or competency definitions can be aggregated to form more comprehensive skills and competencies or decomposed into component skills or competencies. Taxonomies are simple maps in the form of trees, according to the IMS Reusable Definition of Competency or Educational Objective - Best Practice and Implementation Guide¹

Competence maps allow for defining curriculum content in terms of interrelated competencies rather than in terms of fragmented or disassociated knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

The following publication constitutes a map of competencies required in any educator to become a digital facilitator and introduce digital skills, platforms, processes, and tools in their teaching to enhance the learning experience of students. It is aimed to help educators understand and assess the digital skills they required, identify their needs and gaps, and work towards improving their competencies.

The DigiFacT consortium has chosen to use the DigCompEdu Framework as their reference document. The **European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu)** is a scientifically sound framework describing what it means for educators to be digitally competent. It provides a general reference frame to support the development of educator-specific digital competences in Europe. DigCompEdu is directed towards educators at all levels of education, from early childhood to higher and adult education, including general and vocational education and training, special needs education, and non-formal learning contexts.² In the fields of education and training and employment, there was a need to have a common reference framework of what it means to be digitally savvy in an increasingly globalised and digital world.

The Digital Facilitator Trainer Role competence map is divided into 6 areas of competence, following the DigCompEdu structure:

1. Professional Engagement
2. Digital Resources
3. Teaching and Learning

¹ IMS, IMS Reusable Definition of Competency or Educational Objective - Best Practice and Implementation Guide, Version 1.0 Final Specification, May 2016

² Redecker, C. European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators: DigCompEdu. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2017, ISBN 978-92-79-73494-6, doi:10.2760/159770, JRC107466

4. Assessment
5. Empowering Learners
6. Facilitating Learners Digital Competence

Each has been broken down into 3 dimensions:

1. Explanation of the area of competence
2. The needs assess in the VET community of Spain, Romania, and Turkey in the specific area
3. The specific competences of educators in each area of competence

The competence map also provides specific skills identify during the research developed on the project in each of the fields of focus: Gamification, AI, and data analysis, apply to education and training.

Area of competence 1: Professional Engagement

Dimension 1: What is and why is important to foster Professional Engagement in educators?

The importance of considering the area of competence referred to as Professional Engagement when examining the digital competences of educators lies in the fact that the simple use of digital skills for the learning and teaching process would not cover all the aspects of an educator's work, as we cannot ignore the rest of the professional and educational relationships that unfold. Educators have to maintain good communication with their students, families, the school and third parties involved at all times; they need to communicate and collaborate with other educators to continue to develop professionally but also to provide a better educational experience for their students; and they must use technologies to organise themselves, improve their pedagogical skills, learn new skills and adapt to changes in the educational world and the world of work.

The domain of professional engagement refers to two important areas, the engagement of the teachers with their professional development as ongoing learners. And their engagement with all parties of the teaching and learning process, meaning colleagues, their teaching institutions, students, and families. Therefore, the maintenance of participation and collaboration with all actors

of the teaching community that they are a part of, with the goal of fostering students' well-being and intellectual and personal development.

Source: Edmentum blog

Summing up, the application of digital competences to the sphere of professional engagement implies the proper use of digital tools and processes for all tasks related to the professional practice of educators.

According to the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017, we can find four main professional engagement competencies, that are required in educators to have an adequate level of digital competence, these are the following:

Organisational communication	To use digital resources to improve communication with learners, teaching institutions, and third parties involved in the educational and labour world. Meaning to providing better and more efficient communication, as well as to contribute with and share organizational strategies for communication.
Professional collaboration	To use ICTs to collaborate with other educators, to improve the exchanges of knowledge and experiences, and to work collaboratively in the improvement of teaching techniques and pedagogical approaches.
Reflective practice	To reflect, assess, develop, and improve your own digital pedagogical practices for your individual professional development, but also in the aspects that involve learners and the educational community.
Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD)	To use digital resources for your continuous professional development as an educator.

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

The research carried out in the DigiFacT project showed that the needs of educators for professional engagement include:

- Tools that allow direct and fluid communication.
- Tools that prioritize the effectiveness of time and costs.
- A user-friendly tool adapted to the level of the target group of students that, if possible, is already familiar to the learners.
- A balance between richness of functionalities and effectiveness (the simpler the platform, the less time is wasted in setting up the communication channel and more in the actual exchange between users).

Moreover, it is not possible to pick a single digital tool that will be the best option for communication and collaboration with all parties of the VET community, rather, it is a question of knowing what to

take into account when choosing these digital tools, i.e. knowing the characteristics of who you want to communicate with, what their level of digitisation is and what project or specific function you need this communication channel for. On the other hand, it is important to consider that it is necessary to constantly learn and renew your knowledge of the available tools and new communication and collaboration strategies so that the above statement is possible.

Another area of interest is how VET educators are improving their digital pedagogical practices and how are they using digital resources for their continuous professional development.

The research showed that VET educators tend to implement a mixture of autonomous researching and assessing online as well as a more formal approach attending to conferences, seminars, and courses. In general, participants get their information from official sources, such as websites of the ministries, academic articles, and conferences. Other secondary sources of information can be found on social media: YouTube, Facebook, and LinkedIn.

One issue to point out is that most VET teachers and trainers do not report collaboration and exchange of experiences with other educators as a way of developing reflective practice, or they report it as a secondary method. This could be an indicator of a lack of digital channels or online opportunities to help educators exchange knowledge and work together to improve their educational practice, and therefore a lack of these competences on the part of teachers.

Dimension 3: Specific Competences

Dimension 3.1: Organisational communication

Organisational communication	To use digital resources to improve communication with learners, teaching institutions, and third parties involved in the educational and labour world. Meaning to providing better and more efficient communication, as well as to contribute with and share organizational strategies for communication.
-------------------------------------	--

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would rarely make use of digital tools and platforms for communication, and rather prefer to support their communication with learners and the rest of the VET community with analogic solutions. The ones that do make use of it, do it on a very basic level, they are aware of some resources for digital communication and use them with some of the parties involved in the educational process, i.e., learners, families, stakeholders and third parties of the labour market, colleagues, or support staff.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) can use digital solutions for communication in an effective way and attend to the main principles of security and ethics online. They also choose different digital technologies according to the situation, meaning that they adapt to the needs of the specific target groups and the purpose of the communication when choosing the communication technic and tool. At this level, educators have an extensive directory of digital resources, and they consider aspects to adapt to the needs of the recipient.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to organise communication strategies and tools, can evaluate and assess the adequacy of communication strategies, and involved other experts in the discussion. They also provide benefits to the recipients of communication that could not be achieved by using more traditional approaches to communication, meaning that they use technology to make processes with colleagues, learners and third parties easier, transparent, and more efficient. The

more advance educators can also create and redesign the adopted communication strategies to improve them for their professional practice and for the leverage of all parties involved in their educational community.

The advance level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for organizational communication and reach higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To use digital technologies to communicate organisational procedures to learners, i.e., rules, appointments, events, evaluations, programmes, etc.
- To use digital technologies to inform and communicate with learners on an individual basis, meaning using technologies to facilitate the process of providing specific tutoring and recommendations for students.
- To use digital technologies to communicate with colleagues.
- To use digital technologies to communicate with third parties, i.e., experts to be invited, companies and other employers.
- To communicate via official and recognisable channels with possible learners, stakeholders, and others, i.e., corporate, or institutional social media channels and/or websites, e-learning platforms with communication tools incorporated, etc.
- To contribute to collaboratively developing and improving organisational communication strategies for your educational community.

It is important for VET educators nowadays to also be digital facilitators, as they teach in an area that must be highly adapted to the requirements of the labour markets and to have and transfer to their students the digital competences that are required in the world of work, and that employers demand from employees. As we lived in a world that is increasingly globalised and digitalised, every competence required both in education and in the labour market, such as communication skills, must now be adapted to the use of digital technologies.

Dimension 3.2: Professional collaboration.

Professional collaboration	To use ICTs to collaborate with other educators, to improve the exchanges of knowledge and experiences, and to work collaboratively in the improvement of teaching techniques and pedagogical approaches.
-----------------------------------	---

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would rarely make use of digital tools and platforms for collaboration, and rather prefer to support it with analogic solutions. The ones that do make use of it, do it at a very basic level, they are aware of some resources for digital collaboration and use them to share and exchange practices with their colleagues from their teaching institutions.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) can use digital solutions to share and exchange good practices and knowledge, and to learn new pedagogical techniques from the educational community beyond their organisation, i.e., using online communities to exchange practices. They also implement digital resources to collaboratively work on new ideas in a more effective and convenient way.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to professionally collaborate through the usage of digital technologies constantly explore new methods and processes to improve their teaching, they incorporate the acquired knowledge into their practices and disseminate the gained experience to

help others improve as well. Therefore, they are constantly improving their resources to collaborate online. They also participate in the collaborate process of creating new methods for digital collaboration and share them with their peers.

The advance level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for professional collaboration and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To use digital technologies to collaborate with other educators in specific projects, to improve their knowledge and practices, and with the goal of improving the collective or individual learning process of common students.
- To use digital technologies to share their experience, knowledge, and new ideas with other colleagues from their organization and beyond.
- To use digital technologies to improve their teaching by learning from other educators, new innovations and techniques that are available in digital educational communities.
- To use digital technologies to collaboratively develop educational resources and improve the learning process of students, involving their peers but also their learners' opinions and those of key stakeholders.
- To use professional collaborative networks to explore and reflect on new pedagogic practices and methods as well as to be up to date with the requirements of employers.

Dimension 3.3: Reflective practice

Reflective practice	To reflect, assess, develop, and improve your own digital pedagogical practices for your individual professional development, but also in the aspects that involve learners and the educational community.
----------------------------	--

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would be aware of their need to improve and assess their current skills but would have difficulties identifying specific gaps in their practice and/or would not know where to start their professional development journey. The ones that do actively practice self-reflection and self-improvement do it in a restrictive way, meaning that they do assess their digital and pedagogical practices and improve their development but only know or access a minimum number of digital resources.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) can use techniques such as peer review and autonomous research to actively improve their digital pedagogical practices. At this level, educators experiment with new digital solutions and support their development by accessing a less or more wide range of digital sources and resources. They also seek advice and attend seminars and courses.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, educators who are fully competent in reflective practice, continuously enhance and improve both their digital and pedagogical skills, renew the repository of digital resources and communities where it is possible to improve their practice and incorporate the latest innovations and research findings into their teaching. They also help peers from their organizations and beyond to improve their development as educators. The more advance educators develop research and innovative process regarding digital and pedagogical practices, that they incorporate into their teaching and continuously improve.

The advance level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of reflective practice of educators by using digital technologies educators need to:

- To critically reflect on their own digital and pedagogical practice, what are their gaps and where they need to improve.
- To know where to find ways of self-development and how to research and be up to date with new and innovative techniques regarding the improvement of their practice.
- To develop a repository of resources and online communities that is in constant growth and will facilitate the process of constant improvement, as well as invite other colleagues.
- To know and access specific training for their needs regarding digital and pedagogical opportunities.
- To collaborate with their peers to exchange knowledge and help each other in their development journey as educators and digital facilitators.
- To provide feedback and/or actively contribute to developing organisational practices, policies, and ideas on the use of digital technologies.

Dimension 3.4: Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD)

Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD)	To use digital resources for your continuous professional development as an educator.
--	---

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would make little use of the Internet to update their knowledge. The ones that do actively include online sources do it in a restrictive way, meaning they do not update the sources they research, but they do access the internet for updating their knowledge of their subject and/or pedagogical approaches.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) can use the internet to search for seminars, conferences and courses that will allow them to continuously develop professionally. Some of them also attend webinars and online courses and access online materials and tutorials. They do not only use the internet to search for learning opportunities but engage in learning online.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent in regard to digital continuous professional development (CPD) consult a wide range of resources and websites that allow them to be up to date with the latest learning opportunities, that they assess critically to learn in the most fruitful and effective way possible. They consider their teaching style, the target group of learners and subject-specific requirements when choosing a course, seminar or downloading some learning material. They also participate in online training and actively exchange knowledge with peers. The more advance educators are the ones that provide continuous learning opportunities to others by creating their own online communities, websites, material and resources or courses.

In a nutshell, to improve their Digital Continuous Professional Development (CPD) capabilities and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To identify training and professional development sites that provide training opportunities that are adequate for the educator's specific characteristics, considering their field of teaching and their own professional development needs.

- To successfully search for sources and resources online that provide training and to assess their quality and effectiveness correctly.
- To use digital professional communities as a source of professional development.
- To use online training opportunities, e.g., seminars, video tutorials, courses, webinars, etc.
- To use digital environments to provide training opportunities for other educators, i.e., courses, seminars, blogs, websites, etc.

Area of competence 2: Digital Resources

Dimension 1: What is and why is important to introduce digital resources for educators?

The expectations of society for high-quality educational services must be considered in today's educational processes, along with trends in science and technological progress. Purposeful use of digital educational resources is perhaps one of the most efficient methods.

Digital resources are the applications (apps), software, programs, or websites that involve students in learning activities and support their learning objectives. Furthermore, digital resources can be defined as materials that have been conceived and created digitally or by converting analogue materials to a digital format.

Any instructional content that is kept on digital media is referred to as a digital educational resource. According to L. L. Bosova's (n.d.) definition of the term, "digital educational resources" means "Digital educational resources necessary for the educational process and to the digitized resources, namely, photographs, video sequences, static and dynamic models, role-playing, objects, objects of virtual reality and interactive modelling, maps, sound recordings, symbolic objects and business graphics, text documents and other educational materials selected in accordance with the content of a specific tutorial attached to lesson planning and provided with necessary methodical recommendations".

In the framework of updating and transforming the worldwide educational environment, the digitalization of education is a powerful trend. All forms of information (texts, sounds, visual pictures, videos, and other data) must be converted to a digital language to be considered digital.

Digital resources competences imply:

Selecting digital resources	To find, evaluate, and choose digital materials for education. While choosing digital resources and organizing their use, consider the learning purpose, setting, educational method, and learner group.
Creating and modifying digital resources	To add to and make modifications to already-existing openly licensed materials and other resources where it is allowed. To develop new digital learning materials alone or in collaboration. When creating digital resources and organizing their use, consider the learning purpose, setting, pedagogical method, and learner group.
Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources	To arrange digital information so that students, parents, and other educators may access it. Properly safeguard delicate digital material. Should adhere to and properly enforce copyright and privacy laws. To comprehend the production, usage, and correct attribution of open licenses and open educational materials.

Currently, there are several digital (educational) materials available to teachers that they may use for their lessons. Understanding this variety, effectively identifying resources that best suit their learning objectives, learner group, and teaching style, structuring the wealth of materials, establishing connections, and modifying, expanding, and developing their own digital resources to support their teaching are all critical competencies that educators must develop (DigCompEdu, 2017).

They must also understand how to utilize and handle digital information appropriately. When using, changing, and sharing materials, they must adhere to copyright laws and safeguard private information like grades or digital tests. Access to technology, professional development (PD) in the use and integration of digital resources, time constraints, limited opportunities to find and adapt digital resources, and traditional teaching methods that frequently do not prioritize equitable instruction or the support of diverse learners are additional challenges.

Digital educational resources are re-engineering the vocational education system, increasing the proportion of active learning. The immediate demands of students engaged in independent study of the course's theoretical content are addressed by the electronic educational tools provided by professors. Additionally, digital resources are created as a tool for students to use to improve their digital capabilities, which are crucial for students to have in the 21st century (Volkodav 2021).

Source: eLearning Industry

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

Teachers today have access to a multitude of digital (educational) materials that may be used in their lessons. One of the key skills any educator needs to develop is the ability to deal with this variety, to efficiently identify resources that best suit their learning objectives, learners' group, and teaching style, to structure the wealth of materials, establish connections, and modify, add to and develop their own digital resources to support their teaching.

Regarding the factors that are taken into consideration when choosing digital tools, there are two relevant categories: pedagogical approach and features of educational tools.

Pedagogical approach

Most VET teachers feel that it is substantial to choose digital resources in accordance with pedagogical principles. The overall responses to this question focused on choosing educational digital tools depending on the lesson aim, such that they facilitate its achievement. Moreover, educational digital tools are chosen in conformity with learners' needs and characteristics: age, preferences, previous knowledge and existing digital skills.

Some VET teachers and trainers allude to the notion of “autonomous learning” which describes educational digital tools that allow students to learn without trainers’ directions.

Features of educational tools

In this regard, most VET teachers indicate that accessibility is one of the key principles when choosing an educational digital tool. In addition to this, the price of educational digital tools is vital, the favourite ones being those which are free. As well, it is major that all students can access digital resources, no matter the devices they possess or the Internet connection they have. Furthermore, digital resources with a user-friendly interface are preferred. In the end, another aspect that is taken into consideration when choosing educational tools is its language. If both categories (trainers and students) have language skills, then they have access to a larger number of educational resources.

It can be seen from the data above that choosing digital resources is not a simple decision. It must respond to a series of characteristics to be accessible for both teachers and students. As a teacher, it is imperative to choose a tool that best respects the pedagogical principles to positively respond to the goal of the lesson and students’ needs. As a student, it is mandatory to have a useful tool and be able to use it.

Dimension 3: Specific Competences

Dimension 3.1: Selecting digital resources

Selecting digital resources	To find, evaluate, and choose digital materials for education. While choosing digital resources and organizing their use, consider the learning purpose, setting, educational method, and learner group.
------------------------------------	--

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would make little use of the internet to find resources. They will hardly ever utilize the internet to discover teaching and learning tools. More than that, they can become aware and make basic use of digital technologies for finding resources. Also, they can find digital information that is appropriate for teaching–learning activities and use straightforward internet search techniques. What is more, they are aware of popular educational websites that offer educational materials.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence, regarding selecting digital resources, identify and assess suitable resources using basic or complex criteria. They can modify the search tactics in response to the outcomes, use relevant criteria to filter results and evaluate the value of digital resources on fundamental standards. Furthermore, they can find, edit, and adapt materials, such as games and/or applications, focusing on the applicability to the target learner audience and their particular learning goal. Moreover, it can be provided criticism and suggestions on selected sources.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to select digital tools can comprehensively identify and assess suitable resources, considering all relevant aspects and promoting the use of digital resources in education. These people assess the acceptability and dependability of information using a variety of factors while also confirming its neutrality and correctness. In the end, they can advise colleagues and create their own, properly annotated, and graded library of materials, making it accessible to their co-workers.

In a nutshell, to properly select digital resources and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to evaluate the quality of the digital learning resources following the next sections:

- academic quality: information reliability and relevance;

- pedagogical quality: pedagogical formulation, construction, strategies and assessment methods;
- didactic quality: the veracity of learning activities and content of the educational tool;
- technical quality: design, browsing, technological ingenuity.

The number of digital learning tools is rising quickly because of the opportunities provided by information and communication technology (ICT) in today's classrooms. When using digital learning resources, learning takes place in a very different environment than when using conventional learning resources, where human interactions are mediated. Careful attention to the quality of the given digital material is especially crucial in these new settings when the student is alone in front of the computer.

Dimension 3.2: Creating and modifying digital resources

Creating and modifying digital resources	To add to and make modifications to already-existing openly licensed materials and other resources where it is allowed. To develop new digital learning materials alone or in collaboration. When creating digital resources and organizing their use, consider the learning purpose, setting, pedagogical method, and learner group.
---	--

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would create and modify resources using basic tools and strategies. They occasionally use digital materials, but they don't normally modify or produce my own. Once this competence is better reached, they can create and edit worksheets, tests, and digital slideshows for teaching reasons.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of this specific competence, can create, and modify digital resources using some advanced features. They can adjust the digital learning resources to the learning context and make some fundamental changes, such as modifying or removing pieces. Moreover, they can adapt advanced digital resources to a concrete learning context, such as mixing and creating existing materials to design learning activities for a specific learning context, objective, and learners' characteristics.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to create and modify digital resources can create, co-create, and modify resources according to the learning context, using a range of advanced strategies. They use a range of sources outside search engines, such as official repositories, collaborative platforms, etc. Furthermore, they assess the acceptability and dependability of information using a variety of factors, while also confirming its neutrality and correctness. In the end, they can create complex, interactive digital resources and develop their own applications and games.

In a nutshell, to reach a higher level of creating and modifying digital resources, educators need to improve the outcome of a series of activities, such as:

- Provide effective searching methods in order to locate digital resources for research, teaching, and learning;
- Consider the unique learning context and learning purpose and choose appropriate digital resources for teaching and learning;
- Assess the authority and dependability of online sites and materials;
- Take into account any limitations that may apply to the usage or reuse of digital resources (such as copyright, file type, technological specifications, legal constraints, and accessibility);
- Evaluate the effectiveness of digital resources in meeting the learning purpose, the selected pedagogical technique, as well as the competency levels of the specific learner group.

Technology now plays a crucial part in the instructional processes in the modern era of learning. Most educational resources today are "born digital," meaning that they are physically digital files before they are put into print or any other format. This emphasises the importance of educators'

competence to create and modify digital resources to achieve the lessons' aims and facilitate the teaching-learning process both for trainers and trainees.

Dimension 3.3: Managing, protecting, and sharing digital resources

Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources	To arrange digital information so that students, parents, and other educators may access it. Properly safeguard delicate digital material. Should adhere to and properly enforce copyright and privacy laws. To comprehend the production, usage, and correct attribution of open licenses and open educational materials.
---	--

Managing, protecting, and sharing digital resources means arranging digital information so that students, parents, and other educators may access it. properly protect sensitive digital material. To adhere to and properly enforce copyright and privacy laws. To comprehend the production, usage, and correct attribution of open licenses and open educational materials.

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would not employ strategies for sharing resources. They can organize and save digital materials for later use. Moreover, they would create and modify resources using basic tools and strategies. These people can provide links or email attachments with instructional information, and they are aware that some materials made available online are protected by copyright.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of this specific competence, can effectively share, and protect resources using basic strategies. They can disseminate instructional information in virtual learning settings by uploading, sharing, or embedding. Also, they can successfully preserve sensitive material, such as tests and student reports. Moreover, they are aware of the copyright policies governing the digital materials (including photos, text, audio, and video) used for academic purposes. Once this competence is better reached, people professionally share resources. They can distribute materials by integrating them into digital settings, implement access restrictions, secure data, and accurately cite works that are protected by copyright.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to manage, protect and share digital resources can create, co-create, and modify resources according to the learning context, using a range of advanced strategies. To accomplish it, they assemble thorough digital material archives and make them accessible to students or other instructors. Furthermore, they grant licenses to online resources. In the end, they professionally publish self-created digital content. These people can annotate the digital materials they distribute, making it possible for others to review, comment on, edit, rearrange, or contribute to them.

In a nutshell, to reach a higher level of creating and modifying digital resources, educators need to improve the outcome of a series of activities, such as:

- Where allowed, alter and change already-existing digital content;
- If it is allowed, to merge and mix already-existing digital content or portions thereof;
- Develop fresh digital learning materials;
- Collaborate on the creation of digital learning tools;
- When modifying or developing digital learning resources, one should take into account the individual learning purpose, setting, pedagogical method, and learner group;
- Comprehend the many licenses that are applied to digital materials and the effects on their reuse.

Characteristics of Learning:

- Learning is growth.
- Learning is adjustment.
- Learning is intelligence.
- Learning is active.
- Learning is the product of the Environment.
- Learning is both individual and social.
- Learning is Purposeful.
- Learning is organising experience.

Teaching and learning go together. Effective teachers continually improve their skills by learning about the latest trends in the field of education.

Teaching is the process of imparting information. Learning is the process of receiving knowledge as evidenced by a positive or negative change which lasts for a long time. Teaching is associated with more authority, autonomy, and expertise. The teaching and learning policy promotes best practices and establishes consistency in teaching and learning across the whole school. It aims to ensure that all children are provided with high-quality learning experiences, leading to a consistently high level of pupil achievement and attitude.

Digital education is the innovative use of digital tools and technologies during teaching and learning and is referred to as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) or e-Learning. Digital tools and platforms are becoming more integral to our personal and working lives. Digital learning increases access to education and knowledge while empowering students with a mindset and capabilities that set them up for success in their present and future. To support both teaching and learning, technology infuses classrooms with digital learning tools, such as computers and handheld devices; expands course offerings, experiences, and learning materials; supports learning 24 hours a day, 7 days a week; builds 21st-century skills; increases student engagement and offers them with:

- Efficiency. Online learning offers teachers an efficient way to deliver lessons to students.
- Accessibility of Time and Place.
- Affordability.
- Improved Student Attendance.
- Suits a Variety of Learning Styles
- Technology Issues
- Sense of Isolation.
- Teacher Training

In many studies, it is reported that online learning could increase student participation, improve discussion quality, and foster online interactions. The discussion forum could support students and improve learning by solving difficult problems. Well-known examples include social media, online games, multimedia, and mobile phones. Digital learning is any type of learning that uses technology. It can happen across all curriculum learning areas.

The scope of how digital products and services can be used for educational purposes is limitless, and it has some incredible benefits for students, such as immersive learning, accessible long-distance learning, or a personalised education experience, among others.

According to the DigiCompEdu Framework (2017), we can the following digital competencies for educators in Assessment:

Teaching	To prepare lesson plans enhanced with digital tools and resources and to use them efficiently in the process of teaching. To use digital tools to motivate and engage them in the lesson actively. Using new technologies in school subjects makes digital-born students more active and participating in the courses and this will lead teachers to develop new formats and pedagogical methods for instruction.
Guidance	To use digital technologies and services to enhance the interaction with learners, individually and collectively. To guide and assist the students timely while using digital technologies. To develop new forms and formats for better guidance and support.
Collaborative Working	To use digital technologies to foster and enhance learner collaboration. This enables learners to use digital technologies as part of collaborative assignments, as a means of enhancing communication, collaboration, and collaborative knowledge creation.
Self-Regulated Learning	To use digital technologies to support self-regulated learning processes, i.e., to enable learners to plan, monitor and reflect on their own learning, provide evidence of progress, share insights, and come up with creative solutions

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

Digital technologies can enhance and improve teaching and learning strategies in many ways. However, whatever pedagogic strategy or approach is chosen, the educator's specific digital competence lies in effectively orchestrating the use of digital technologies in the different phases and settings of the learning process.

Of interest in the area of VET teaching and training is how digital facilitators design, plan and implement new digital technologies that help learners self-regulate their own learning. The project research showed the following:

- The teachers plan their learning activities according to the students' perception, comprehension and learning abilities and they use artificial intelligence due to the content of their teaching and learning topic. However, those teachers mostly prefer to use already planned and designed AI tools rather than designing them by themselves. And they recommend their students use mobile applications in their tasks and studies.
- Teachers and trainers have an idea about AI and use them (e.g., Siri, DeepL, Google Translate, Write, and Improve, Speak, and Improve etc) in their teaching activities and focus on the importance of AI in this digitalized world. Teachers also use online evaluation tools, Kahoot in which students can see their own progress.
- Teachers and trainers can learn how to use AI-based tools not only by attending in-service training courses but also by watching tutorial videos several times before implementing them in their courses.

With the beginning of Covid-19, teachers met distant e-learning platforms and many other digital tools of Data Analysis, Artificial Intelligence and Gamification. Most of the teachers integrated them into their courses but still, there are some teachers who either do not show any interest to learn and use them or do not know them. But all teachers are aware of the importance of using AI, databases and gamification apps and tools in their courses to make their learning and teaching more engaging and efficient.

Artificial intelligence is used at a small scale in the participants' educational route. It is implemented through the usage of Siri, Alexa, and Cambridge tools, participating directly in the learning process.

Artificial intelligence is also indirectly incorporated through other commonly used tools such as DeepL, and Google Translate.

In terms of designing learning activities, VET teachers and trainers have two options:

- In a traditional way (teacher-centred) or
- Learner-centred

Although there are common approaches to designing learning activities there are slight differences, too.

The teachers know that learner-centred lesson plans and the participation of students in learning ensure that what they learn is more permanent and practical. In fact, training is not only about the trainer's delivering learning materials, but about the trainee getting the desired knowledge, skills, and attitudes (i.e., achieving the learning outcomes). Each person has a different learning style and teachers can implement a questionnaire (Kahoot, Mentimeter, etc) to assess students' learning styles during the first session and design the learning activities according to their learning needs and styles. This will improve students' motivation, engagement, and participation in the class.

The research shows that most VET teachers adopt gamification to their courses especially to improve students' engagement and increase their participation in the course. Teachers are keen on finding the right digital tools and the associated training methods to meet trainees' expectations, learning needs and styles. Although, it is not possible to use digital tools in all courses or in all classes teachers mostly prefer to use them in their courses.

Gamification is used in various forms. Some facilitators have it in mind when building training as a sequence of stories, and some useful tools to implement it. In terms of tools and methods, they use animated videos, Kahoots, puzzles, role plays, and mobile apps.

Moreover, the digital facilitator tends to use using video and audio communication tools (WhatsApp groups, zoom, Moodle platforms, and Facebook) to share information, documents, and ideas. Communication improves collaboration and teachers use different types of collaborative tools to assign tasks or projects to students to work in peers or groups. Improving collaboration skills is a very important qualification in professional life. Gaining this skill at school period makes finding a job easier for the students too. For good communication and collaboration, teachers can provide students with Google Docs or Google Spreadsheets and ask them to answer forum questions and comment on each other's posts. Such activities improve students' creative, and collaborative skills. Giving the task of creating a simple web page (or a blog) or an account on social media that disseminates the topic to be covered, is usually another good method of collaborative work among a group of students. Besides the topic itself, the students also learn other transversal skills such as teamwork, communication, divulgation skills and digital skills.

Digital facilitators encourage collaborative work by setting up communication channels, such as WhatsApp groups, Moodle forums, and shared Google docs. Learning via Zoom is also an opportunity for students to work together.

Allowing students to research a specific topic together is a great way to engage with the subject and to work with others before the teacher offers his notes.

Dimension 3: Specific Competence

Dimension 3.1: Teaching

Teaching To prepare lesson plans enhanced with digital tools and resources and to use them efficiently in the process of teaching. To use digital tools to motivate and engage them in the lesson actively. Using new technologies in school subjects makes digital-born students

more active and participating in the courses and this will lead teachers to develop new formats and pedagogical methods for instruction.

Digital education is an innovative use of digital tools and technologies during teaching and learning and is often referred to as e-learning or technology-based learning. In the 21st century it is expected that, since new generations are in a continuous transformation, they are required to have an advanced level of digital competence. The learning habits of 21st century students have changed. Their needs and circumstances are not the same as the students of 10 years ago. So for the schools at each level and type it is essential that they can learn how to provide an educational, didactic and safe response to the needs of students. And to achieve that schools need to work with teachers who are updated in training and possess a degree of digital competence to undertake the teaching-learning process of students and to promote the acquisition of key competencies in students.

A teacher at the A1 level makes little use of digital technologies for instruction. They either do not know how to use digital tools in school education or use it very rarely. Some teachers use only available classroom technologies, e.g., digital whiteboards, projectors, and PCs.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, teachers at (Integrator) B1 or (Expert) B2 have the competence of integrating available digital technologies meaningfully into the teaching process and use digital technologies purposefully to enhance pedagogic strategies. They have the capability of organizing and managing the integration of digital devices (e.g., classroom technologies, students' devices) into the teaching and learning process and also set up learning sessions or other interactions in a digital environment.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Teachers who are competent enough to use different types of digital tools in their lesson plans can easily structure their sessions. These sessions can be structured as teacher-led or student-led according to the topic of the lesson and the learning needs of the students. Student-centred and digitally structured lessons will re-enforce the learning objectives. Teachers at the leader or Pioneer level can structure and manage content, contributions, and interaction in a digital environment. During their sessions, they can also easily evaluate the effectiveness of digitally enhanced teaching strategies and revise their strategies according to them.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell to plan and implement digital devices and resources in the school education process and lesson plans administrative should put some objectives and take precautions to enhance the effectiveness of teaching interventions. They should orchestrate digital teaching interventions, especially at VET schools to manage the educational system appropriately. In order to realize that educators need to:

- To use technologies and digital tools in the classroom to support instruction, e.g., smart boards, mobile devices, and classroom devices.
- To reinforce learning objectives with teacher-led or student-led digital activities.
- To prepare and form lesson plans, learning activities and interactions in a digital technological world.
- To prepare digital content and collaborate, communicate, and interact in a digital world.
- To utilize face-to-face or virtual educator-led digital interferes to support the learning objectives.
- To adjust methods and strategies reflecting on the effectiveness and appropriateness of the digital pedagogical strategies.
- To use innovative and pedagogical methods in their teaching way. (e.g., flipped classroom-project-based learning).

In the 21st century all teachers, especially VET teachers and trainers should be kept on track in digital education and keen on applying and implementing digital tools in their courses. Because the VET sector is huge and VET students should be equipped with the needs of labour markets and the world of work. Teaching and learning how to adapt digital tools to your courses or how to apply them to your topic, especially with project-based learning methods will lead to real learning.

Dimension 3.2: Guidance

Guidance To use digital technologies and services to enhance the interaction with learners, individually and collectively. To guide and assist the students timely while using digital technologies. To develop new forms and formats for better guidance and support.

On one hand, teachers who have this basic guidance competence make little use of digital technologies for interacting with students. To interact with their students, they employ basic digital strategies. They either do not communicate with their students or communicate very rarely through digital means like email, chat, and texting to respond to their questions or assignments.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigCompEdu Framework, 2017.

Digital technologies are the perfect means of interaction with students, and this enhances monitoring and guidance as well. Interacting with learners in collaborative digital environments is a perfect means of monitoring their behaviour and providing individual guidance and support as needed. Teachers and trainers should experiment with new forms and formats for offering guidance and support, using digital technologies.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, teachers who are competent to employ digital technologies strategically and purposefully to provide guidance and support can set up learning activities in digital environments. They can foresee students' needs for guidance and cater for them, e.g. with help or FAQ section, or with video tutorials. Teachers can easily monitor students' work or his/her behaviour digitally and then they can offer guidance whenever needed. Digital guidance gives you many opportunities to be more objective and act and monitor the students like a fly on the wall. And new needs may lead to the development of new forms and formats for offering guidance and support, using digital technologies.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for guidance and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To use digital communicative tools to give respond answers to the students' questions, assignments, performance, or project works.
- To better guide to foresee the students' needs and set up learning activities according to their needs.
- To interact with students in the collaborative digital world.
- To monitor students digitally during the learning activities and guide them whenever they need.

Guidance, especially digital guidance is highly important at school and in social life. Teachers can assign school homework, projects, or any tasks to students. It is easier for VET teachers to assign immediate tasks to students at ateliers or classes. Teachers can monitor students' behaviour and working discipline digitally and can also learn more about the development of students' soft skills.

With digital guidance, teachers can be a fly on the wall and this will give them a perfect chance to monitor the students and get their real needs.

Dimension 3.3: Collaborative Working

Collaborative Working

To use digital technologies to foster and enhance learner collaboration. This enables learners to use digital technologies as part of collaborative assignments, as a means of enhancing communication, collaboration, and collaborative knowledge creation.

Teachers who have this basic competence make little use of digital technologies in collaborative learning activities. They never or very rarely think about how students could use digital technologies in their assignments or activities that should be done collaboratively. In such circumstances, teachers should encourage students to use collaborative digital tools to realize their assignments and presentations.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework.

According to the CEFR framework at the next level, the teachers are expected to implement digital technologies into the design of collaborative activities to support collaborative learning. Teachers can design and set up collaborative activities for students to exchange information or realize tasks; digital presentations, videos, ebooks, e-newspapers, wikis, moodle, teams, google meet, websites or blog posts. While students are working collaboratively in a digital environment teachers can monitor and guide them digitally, too. During collaborative work, students can receive and give peer feedback and also do self-assessments.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

On the other hand, teachers use digital technologies to innovate and develop students' collaborative learning and peer assessment. At this level, teachers can design and manage various collaborative learning activities in which students collaboratively conduct research, document findings, and reflect on their virtual or face-to-face learning. During collaborative learning, teachers can monitor and guide students and at the same time collaborative learning is a perfect environment to get peer and self-assessment.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in designing and setting digital technologies for collaborative learning, educators need to:

- To implement collaborative learning activities in which digital devices, resources (e.g., wikis, blogs, LMS) or digital information strategies are used.
- To make use of collaborative digital tools to exchange knowledge among students and colleagues.
- To monitor and guide students while they are realizing learning activities/tasks collaboratively and assist and give guidance whenever needed.
- To use digital evaluation and assessment tools for peer feedback and support for collaborative learning.

Dimension 3.4: Self-Regulated Learning

Self-Regulated Learning

To use digital technologies to support self-regulated learning processes, i.e., to enable learners to plan, monitor and reflect on their own learning, provide evidence of progress, share insights, and come up with creative solutions.

Understanding the way of their own learning and taking responsibility for their own learning are very important skills. And digital tools improve self-regulated learning via activities or tasks. At this level, teachers either do not or rarely consider how students could use digital technologies in self-

regulated activities or assignments and encourage them to use digital technologies to support their individual learning activities and assignments, e.g., for information retrieval or presenting results.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework.

Integrators and expert teachers have the capability to implement digital technologies into the design of self-regulated learning activities and use them to comprehensively support self-regulated learning. At this level teachers encourages students to use digital technologies to collect evidence and record progress in producing video or audio recordings, photos, texts, e-portfolios, learner's blogs, etc. Such digital learning and teaching activities also allow students to manage and document all stages of their learning, e.g. planning, information retrieval, documentation, reflection and self-assessment. With the support of digital technologies teachers also help students to develop, apply and revise criteria for self-assessment, with the support of digital technologies.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, teachers who have competence in using digital technologies can easily foster self-regulated learning and can develop various innovative digital formats or pedagogies for self-regulated learning. In addition, they foster their self-regulated learning and enhance their strategies. Developing digital skills improves hard skills as well as soft skills both for teachers and students in this digital world.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in developing innovative digital formats or pedagogies for self-regulated learning, educators need to:

- To use digital technologies (e.g., blogs, diaries, planning tools) to allow learners to plan their own learning.
- To use digital technologies to allow learners to collect evidence and record progress, e.g., audio or video recordings, and photos.
- To use digital technologies (e.g., ePortfolios, learners' blogs) to allow learners to record and showcase their work.
- To use digital technologies to enable learners to reflect on and self-assess their learning process.

Area of competence 4: Assessment

Dimension 1: What is and why is important to foster Assessment competencies in educators?

Assessment and evaluation have been key parts of teaching and learning for centuries, nevertheless, they have been notoriously used incorrectly to measure the knowledge memorized by students instead of a way to monitor their development and skills gained. At the same time, these two concepts have been confused and used as synonyms on many occasions, when evaluation is just one part of the process of assessment. To continue with a delimited definition of what is an assessment we will take the definition of Brown (1990), which describes assessment as a process that includes four basic components:

- 1.** Measuring and assessing improvement over time.
- 2.** Motivating students to learn.
- 3.** Evaluating the teaching methods.
- 4.** Ranking the students' capabilities in relation to the whole group evaluation.

As said before, Assessment is a significant part of education and therefore it is very important to integrate digital technologies into this process but considering that it is vital to enhance and improve existing assessment techniques and incorporate digital technologies just when it is necessary. Technology must always be a supporting tool for teaching and learning and not a burden for students or educators that hinders or generalise the process of assessment.

Source: Digitalbizmagazine

In addition, digital resources can be used to make the process of assessment easier and faster, to make it more creative for students, to assess aspects that would be impossible without it, to monitor the learner's progress in a more effective way and to provide feedback between educators and students to each adjust their approaches to teaching and learning consequently.

According to the DigiCompEdu Framework (2017), we can the following digital competencies for educators in Assessment:

Assessment strategies	To use digital technologies for formal assessment. To enhance the diversity and adaptability of assessment processes.
Analysing evidence	To generate, collect, critically analyse, and interpret the results of learners. To monitor the progress and performance of learners in a more accurate and diverse way using digital technologies.
Feedback and planning	To use digital technologies to provide better, more personalized, and timely feedback to learners. This means providing learners with advice based on their performance, and monitoring the incorporation of said advice. To enable learners to understand the evidence provided by digital technologies and use it for decision-making.

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

In the following, we expand upon the views of VET teachers and trainers on Assessment and how this is influenced by digital technologies in the day-to-day practice of an educator. In other words, how educators manage the assessment and storing of data from their learners.

As a general conclusion, most participants use Excel to store data. However, where the opportunity for an e-portal is being given, teachers choose to use it. With Moodle, for example, participants can track very easily the progress of a course. Other tools to collect and store data: are Google Forms, Doodle, Mentimeter, and MailChimp.

In general, educators choose different digital resources to assess students' progress and store the data collected depending on the educator level of digital skills, accessibility given, i.e., some courses have an e-learning platform associated that provides sufficient assessment functionalities, and the specific needs determined by the course specific learning objectives and level of complexity.

It is then interesting to see at what level are educators analysing the data obtained from students through digital technologies, as well as how are they using this information to further improve their teaching and general decision-making. Some teachers perform analysis of data in Excel or analyse the results generated from Moodle or other e-learning platforms used. The results are reflected upon or even discussed with other teachers and students to find solutions to any problem that might arise.

Overall, we can conclude that VET educators and trainers have a basic and intermediate level of competencies in relation to assessment. Some of the issues that might be the reason for the lack of more advanced competencies are lack of time to research more complex techniques and resources for data analysis, the diverse needs of the different courses that they teach as well as among their students, which makes the process of developing once specific strategy for assessment and data analysis more difficult, and the lack of information available on courses and other learning opportunities to improve these competences.

Dimension 3: Specific Competences

Dimension 3.1: Assessment strategies

Assessment strategies To use digital technologies for formal assessment. To enhance the diversity and adaptability of assessment processes.

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would rarely make use of digital tools and platforms for assessment activities, and rather prefer to use analogic solutions. If they do make use of digital technologies to assess students it is often for creating assessment tasks or tests that are later provided on paper to learners, i.e., for creating a test easier or to provide a calendar for students with the deadlines of tasks.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) can use existing digital solutions for formative assessment, i.e., digital quizzes, e-portfolios, and games, and they can adapt or choose a specific tool according to their learning objectives and the goal of the assessment. Some have a wider range of options, tools, and *software* that they can implement depending on the requirements and target group needs, they can also properly analyse the adequacy and quality of the tools they implement.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to implement digital assessment tools and processes can adopt, modify, and create their own digital assessment formats. They can calculate the impact of using digital technology for assessing students and determine in which situations the digital approach is more beneficial. A more advanced group of educators can develop innovative digital assessment formats, using digital technologies, and share them with their teaching community.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for assessing learners and their progress and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To use digital assessment tools to monitor the progress of learners and obtain data regarding their performance.
- To use digital technologies to enhance and improve formative and summative assessment strategies, i.e., making them more attractive to learners, providing more effective ways of collecting results, etc.

- To use a variety of digital and non-digital assessment formats and to understand how to use them appropriately to benefit students and not simply for the sake of implementing technology, meaning to critically assess the adequacy and quality of tools and strategies used.

Dimension 3.2: Analysing evidence

Analysing evidence	To generate, collect, critically analyse, and interpret the results of learners. To monitor the progress and performance of learners in a more accurate and diverse way using digital technologies.
---------------------------	---

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would rarely make use of digitally obtained data from their students to monitor their development. If they do make use of digital technologies to assess and monitor students it is often the most basic data that can be obtained both through digital resources and analogically, such as test scores, attendance, interventions, etc. They use the data to provide individual feedback to students.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) use the data obtained through the digital resources or platform provided for these purposes, to monitor their student's progress and activity, and to provide them with direct feedback on their performance. Some of them would go a step further and implement the digital monitoring tools that they find necessary to generate the information they need to monitor their learners.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent in the analysis of teaching and learning evidence make use of data collection and assessment to improve the learning strategies of students and reflect on the learning content they create, and the pedagogical techniques used. They often use multiple digital data collection tools, that they choose according to the course and learners' needs, and they use this information obtained to provide individual feedback and solutions to students. The more advanced educators in the use of analytics will go a step further and implement more advanced data generation and visualization processes and discuss and reflect on the adequacy of different methods as well as continuing research to improve their knowledge and continue to include innovations.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for analysing evidence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To implement processes that allow generating and collecting important data from their students' performances.
- To use digital technologies to collect, organize, visualised, evaluate and measure the significant data collected.
- To analyse and draw conclusions from the evidence collected that will ultimately help the learners improve their capabilities or learning methods, improve the teaching content and approaches, or identify specific issues and provide solutions.

Dimension 3.3: Feedback and planning

Feedback and planning	To use digital technologies to provide better, more personalized, and timely feedback to learners. This means providing learners with advice based on their performance and monitoring the incorporation of said advice. To
------------------------------	---

enable learners to understand the evidence provided by digital technologies and use it for decision-making.

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would rarely make use of digitally obtained data from their students to prove them with feedback and planning. The ones that do make use of digital technologies to inform feedback, tend to provide more basic information on the learner's progress.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of competence (intermediate level) use digital technologies to provide different forms of feedback to students and try to facilitate access to information on learners' performance to the students. They would try to improve the effectiveness of the feedback given by incorporating the usage of digitally obtained data. They would also do a follow-up of the feedback provided to help students plan accordingly and thus improve their learning progress.

The intermediate level corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent around feedback and planning would personalise the feedback as well as the follow-up support and planning they provide to the individual student, supporting these actions with more advanced data assessment techniques that allow them to obtain and assess more information in a more efficient way. They would also use the data obtained to reflect on their teaching, and some of these educators would make improvements to their teaching strategies based on the information collected through digital assessment, thus continuously innovating and adjusting their teaching.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for feedback and planning and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To use assessment management systems and processes to enhance the effectiveness of feedback provision.
- To use digital technologies to monitor learners' progress and provide support when needed, and to individualise this support as much as possible to tailor it to the gaps and needs of everyone.
- To adapt, modify and innovate their teaching and assessment practices, based on the data generated by the digital technologies used.
- To enable learners to evaluate and interpret the results obtained through all kinds of assessments.
- To assist learners in identifying areas for improvement and jointly develop learning plans to address these areas, and to use the information obtained for more long-term decisions regarding their choices in education, and career-wise.

Area of competence 5: Empowering Learners

Dimension 1: What is and why is important for educators to empower learners?

A change from a learner-centred to a teacher-centred approach, from information transmission and memorization to knowledge acquisition and application, is what defines the postmodern educational paradigm. The student takes an active role in the educational process by learning how to gather

knowledge, evaluate it critically and use it ethically and creatively to solve problems that arise in daily life. The educator, in turn, transitions from being a knowledge provider to someone who works with and helps learners.

The inquisitive mind is more satiated than ever before because of improvements in eLearning technology and straightforward search engines like Google. It takes only a few mouse clicks to learn new information and abilities. With the ability to study on their own, individuals are driven to learn more (and more, and more) to be better equipped for a changing work environment. This indicates that they actively and consistently try to comprehend what, why, and how.

The term "empowered learner" now has a broader connotation. An atmosphere and activities that boost one's sense of self-efficacy and energy are provided as part of the empowerment process, which is described as the process of establishing intrinsic task motivation. Motivated and inquisitive, empowered learners see chances for both professional and personal improvement. This indicates that they always strive to improve all facets of their lives.

Digital technologies' capacity to enhance learner-centred pedagogical approaches and increase students' active participation in and ownership of the learning process is one of its primary benefits for education. So, while studying a subject, trying out various possibilities or solutions, comprehending connections, coming up with original solutions, or making an artefact and commenting on it, for example, digital technology may be utilized to support learners' active involvement.

Competencies for empowering learners imply:

Accessibility and inclusion	To make learning materials and activities accessible to all students, including those with special needs. To consider and address learners' (digital) expectations, capabilities, uses, and misunderstandings as well as any environmental, physical or cognitive limitations on how they utilize technology.
Differentiation and personalisation	To utilize digital technology to meet the various learning needs of students, allowing them to progress at varied rates and levels while adhering to their own unique learning goals.
Actively engaging learners	To encourage students' active and imaginative involvement with a subject topic by using digital technology. To include digital tools into pedagogical approaches that encourage learners to think critically, and creatively and employ cross-disciplinary abilities. To expose students to fresh and authentic settings for learning that include them in practical tasks, scientific research, challenging puzzles, or other methods to get more actively involved in difficult subject matters.

Engagement and empowerment are very different. Engagement is defined as mobilizing institutional and student time, effort, and resources to improve the student experience, learning outcomes, and institutional reputation. This suggests that the institution or the trainers have the primary burden of ensuring that the trainees are engaged.

Empowerment, on the other hand, denotes a transfer of learning responsibility from the institution or instructors to the students. It is not the only responsibility of trainers to plan engaging activities for their classes to keep students interested; rather, they must provide the circumstances necessary to ensure that students feel inspired to study due to the course's inherent design.

While participation suggests a more general emphasis, empowerment often has a narrower definition. Although empowered students are constantly active in their work, engaged students are not always empowered.

By providing learning activities customized to each learner's level of competency, interests, and learning requirements, digital technology may also assist classroom differentiation and personalized education. But at the same time, it's important to provide accessibility for all students, especially those with special educational needs, and to avoid escalating already-existing disparities (such as in access to digital tools or digital skills).

Source: Edmentum Blog

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

Of importance for empowering learners is finding the factors that are taken into consideration when identifying students' needs and abilities, i.e. how do VET teachers identify learners' different needs and abilities (considering physical or cognitive constraints) when implementing digital instruments. This question has a special focus on those students who present physical or cognitive constraints.

In this regard, it appears that the most important is for the VET digital facilitator to evaluate the students' constraints. This brings to attention two aspects: the moment of the evaluation and the types of evaluation.

Moment of the evaluation

The majority of those who responded to this item felt that it is suitable to identify learners' needs and abilities at different moments. This idea leads to initial and formative evaluation. On one hand, the initial assessment is the process of determining a person's learning and support requirements to enable the creation of a personalized learning plan that will give their education some structure. It establishes the learner's beginning point for their learning program. In order to acquire the information that is needed, the trainer takes data through the registration process, surveys, and questionnaires that are filled out before the start of the course. On the other hand, formative

evaluation is intended to support the learning process by giving the learner feedback that may be utilized to pinpoint strengths and weaknesses and thereby enhance future performance³. It is agreed that the trainer focuses during the program on the students, identifying their needs.

Types of evaluation

The research shows that it is viable to discover students' needs through observation. In the field of education, observation is frequently utilized as a method to enhance learning and growth. Moreover, this is a suitable method for gathering data that may be used to analyse educational contexts, assess the efficacy of instructional strategies, and formulate improvement strategies. Directly asking the students is the alternate method and one of the interviewee's common answers. This method can be correlated with metacognition, the process which explains knowledge and understanding of your own thinking.

To conclude, most digital facilitators take into consideration different moments and different strategies of evaluation.

Dimension 3: Specific Competences

Dimension 3.1: Accessibility and inclusion

Accessibility and inclusion	To make learning materials and activities accessible to all students, including those with special needs. To consider and address learners' (digital) expectations, capabilities, uses, and misunderstandings as well as any environmental, physical, or cognitive limitations on how they utilize technology.
------------------------------------	---

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would be concerned about inclusivity and accessibility and their related issues. They can be worried that integrating digital tools into the classroom would make it much harder for already underprivileged pupils to engage and stay up with the rest. At the same time, they recognize how crucial it is to give every student access to the same digital tools and that digital technology may help or hurt accessibility

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of this specific competence would address accessibility and inclusivity. They are aware of social and economic disparities caused by access to digital technology as well as how these factors affect how pupils utilize it. Also, they make sure that all the pupils can use the digital tools they employ, being aware of those students who require more help, such as those in need. Moreover, these educators would enable accessibility and inclusivity. It means that they use digital educational tactics that consider the learners' digital surroundings, such as time constraints or the type of device accessible. When choosing, altering, or developing digital resources, they take accessibility into account and address any possible problems. They also offer alternate or compensating tools or techniques for students with special requirements. What is more, they use digital tools and techniques, such as assistive technology, to address the accessibility issues that certain learners, such as visual or auditory disabilities, may have.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to ensure accessibility and inclusion would enhance both. They can choose and deploy digital pedagogical tactics that are appropriate for learners' technological uses, competencies, expectations, attitudes, and misuses. Also, they can utilize design concepts, such as font size, colour, language, style, and structure, to make materials and digital learning settings more accessible. Furthermore, they can provide innovative strategies for

³ Yambi, T. A. C. (2018). Assessment and evaluation in education. Research Gate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342918149_ASSESSMENT_AND_EVALUATION_IN_EDUCATION

accessibility and inclusion. These people can consider, debate, redesign, and develop approaches for inclusion and equitable access to digital education.

In a nutshell, to reach a higher level of creating and modifying digital resources, educators need to improve the outcome of a series of activities, such as:

- Ensure that all the pupils can use the digital tools that are being used.
- Imply assistive devices for students who require extra help, such as those with physical or mental disabilities or learning difficulties.
- Always keep an eye on how well the accessibility improvement measures that are put in place are working and adjust the approach as necessary.

Taken together, these results suggest that inclusion comprehends people's involvement and empowerment. People are valued and respected when they are included. When they are being their true selves, employees perform at their best. One must feel included in order to be one's true self.

Dimension 3.2: Differentiation and personalisation

Differentiation and personalisation	To utilize digital technology to meet the various learning needs of students, allowing them to progress at varied rates and levels while adhering to their own unique learning goals.
--	---

On one hand, individuals who have this basic competence would be uncertain about the ability of digital technology to differentiate and personalize. They have no information about technologies as an instrument that offers personalised learning opportunities. Also, once they get a little bit more advanced, they would become aware of the possibilities for differentiation and personalization offered by digital technology. They are aware that digital technologies, such as those that offer activities at various levels and speeds, can assist differentiation and personalization.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of this specific competence would employ digital technologies for differentiation and personalisation. They can choose and employ various learning exercises, such as games or quizzes, that let students move at different rates, choose varying degrees of difficulty and/or redo exercises that they didn't complete successfully the first time. Moreover, these educators would also judiciously employ a variety of digital tools to differentiate and personalize. Those people can employ a variety of different digital technologies when creating learning and assessment activities, and I adjust and modify them to take into consideration various requirements, levels, speeds, and preferences. Moreover, they consider diverse learning paths, levels, and speeds when sequencing and putting learning activities into place and nimbly adjust their techniques to suit emerging conditions or demands.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to ensure accessibility and inclusion would implement differentiated and personalized learning completely and thoughtfully. In partnership with students and/or parents, they can personalize and create learning plans that let each student use the right digital resources to match their unique learning requirements and preferences. Also, they consider how well the differentiation and personalization are fostered by the teaching tactics used and they adjust their teaching techniques and digital activities accordingly. In the end, they would use digital technologies to differentiate and personalize marketing efforts. As a final stage, these educators can consider, debate, redesign and create pedagogical approaches for individualized learning through the use of digital technology.

In a nutshell, to reach a higher level of creating and modifying digital resources, educators need to improve the outcome of a series of activities, such as:

- Employ digital technology to meet the unique learning demands of each student, such as those with dyslexia, ADHD, or overachievers.
- Consider various learning routes, levels, and rates when creating, picking, and putting into practice digital learning activities.
- Create personalized learning strategies and utilize digital tools to assist them.

With the increased use of technology in classrooms in recent years, individualized learning and differentiated teaching have become popular aspects of the education sector. Nearly everyone agrees that it is advantageous for schools to accommodate more and more the individual requirements of each student.

Dimension 3.3: Actively engaging learners

Actively engaging learners	<p>To encourage students' active and imaginative involvement with a subject topic by using digital technology.</p> <p>To include digital tools into pedagogical approaches that encourage learners to think critically, and creatively and employ cross-disciplinary abilities.</p> <p>To expose students to fresh and authentic settings for learning that include them in practical tasks, scientific research, challenging puzzles, or other methods to get more actively involved in difficult subject matters.</p>
-----------------------------------	---

On one hand, educators who have this basic competence would make little use of digital technologies for learner engagement and would use these very rarely. Also, once they get a little bit more advanced, they would use digital technologies to engage learners. They can make use of digital technology, such as animations and films, to help students understand new ideas in a fun and engaging way. Also, they can use interesting and stimulating digital learning activities, such as games and quizzes.

On the other hand, people who reach a reasonable level of this specific competence would be encouraging the active usage of digital tools by students. They can place the instructional process' active use of digital technology at the centre. Also, they select the resource that will best promote student active involvement in a particular learning setting or with a certain learning purpose. Moreover, they would utilize digital tools to encourage active learning about the subject. In order to build a relevant, rich and successful digital learning environment, they make use of a variety of digital technologies, such as addressing various sensory channels, learning styles, and techniques, as well as methodologically modifying activity kinds and group compositions. Furthermore, they consider how well the instructional techniques are used to promote active learning and learner engagement.

Ultimately, people who are fully competent to ensure accessibility and inclusion would put into practice active learning methodologies completely and critically. They can choose, create, utilize, and coordinate the usage of digital tools in the learning process based on how well they can encourage students' active, imaginative, and critical engagement with the subject matter. Also, they consider how effective the many digital tools they employ boost students' active learning and they modify their techniques and decisions as necessary. In the final stage, trainers are supposed to develop new digital methods for active learning. They can consider, talk about, redesign, and create new pedagogical techniques for getting students to actively participate.

In a nutshell, to reach a higher level of creating and modifying digital resources, educators need to improve the outcome of a series of activities, such as:

- Utilize digital tools to create interesting and stimulating visualizations and explanations of new ideas.

- Use interesting and compelling digital learning environments or activities.
- Place the active use of digital tools by students at the heart of the teaching process.
- To choose the best digital tools for a certain learning situation or a particular learning goal to promote active learning.

In general, therefore, it seems that active learning is an important technique in the modern classroom, especially with the various benefits and opportunities it brings. Active learning supported by the development of digital skills is crucial for learners in the digital world.

Area of competence 6: Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence

Dimension 1: What and why is it important to Facilitate Learners' Digital Competence?

In the case of European policy recommendations, there are two slightly different definitions of 'competence'. In the Key Competences Recommendation, 'competence' is defined as a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes appropriate to the context (European Parliament and the Council, 2006). In the European Qualifications Framework recommendation, 'competence' is seen as the most advanced element of the framework descriptors and is defined as the proven ability to use knowledge, skills and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations and in professional and personal development. Furthermore, in the context of the European Qualifications Framework, competence is described in terms of responsibility and autonomy (European Parliament and the Council, 2008).

Pixabay

Digital competence means that the teacher has to master communication in the digital environment, share resources and tools, share, interact and participate in communities and networks. It is one of the key competences and refers to the confident and critical usage of the full range of digital technologies for information, communication and basic problem-solving in all aspects of life.

Digital competence is one of the transversal competencies that educators need to instil in learners. Whereas fostering other transversal competencies is only part of educators' digital competence in as far as digital technologies are used to do so, the ability to facilitate learners' digital competence is an integral part of educators' digital competence. It is also considered that "as a transversal competence, digital competence also helps us master other key competences, such as communication, language skills, or basic skills in maths and science.

The following competences are important to facilitate learners' Digital Competence:

Information and media literacy

Knowing how to reach the correct information at the right source and media literacy are top topics in this digital age and necessary to incorporate learning activities, assignments and assessments which require students to articulate information needs.

Besides teaching school subjects' teachers should also guide students to find information and resources in digital environments. They can also lead students to organise, process, analyse and interpret information to compare and critically evaluate the credibility and reliability of information and its sources.

Digital communication and collaboration

Students need to use digital communication and collaboration tools effectively and in civic participation to incorporate learning activities, tasks, assignments, and assessments. Such activities encourage students to interact through a variety of digital technologies. They can understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context and share data, information, and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies.

In the global digital world, students will be able to seek opportunities for self-empowerment and for participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies.

Digital content creation

Students should incorporate digital learning activities, tasks, assignments, and assessments to express themselves through digital means, and to modify and create digital content in different formats. Students should be aware of internet rules and ethics how copyright and licenses apply to digital content, and how to reference sources and attribute licenses. Creating and editing digital content improves students' encouragement in realizing their tasks in future, too. They will gain the skill of understanding how to plan and develop a sequence of understandable instructions for a computing system to solve a given problem or perform a specific task.

Responsible use

Teachers should take measures to ensure students' physical, psychological, and social well-being while using digital technologies as well as empower them to manage risks and use digital technologies safely and responsibly.

Teachers should encourage students to use digital technologies with a positive impact in a creative and critical manner. Although it serves lots of positive effects on our school and social life, digital technology also contains and faces various risks and threats. Students should know internet safety and security measures to protect their personal data and privacy in digital environments to avoid health risks and threats to physical and psychological well-being while using digital technologies

Digital problem solving

Students can identify and solve technical problems or transfer technological knowledge creatively to new situations. Students can identify technical problems when operating devices and using digital environments, and solve them. They can easily adjust and customise digital environments to personal needs. They can identify, evaluate, select, and use digital technologies and possible technological responses to solve a given task or problem and use digital technologies in innovative ways to create knowledge. With such qualifications, students can understand where their digital competence needs to be improved or updated and support others in their digital competence development.

Dimension 2: Needs of VET educators

Digital competence is one of the transversal competences educators need to instil in learners. Whereas fostering other transversal competences is only part of educators' digital competence in as far as digital technologies are used to do so, the ability to facilitate learners' digital competence is an integral part of educators' digital competence.

Fostering the use of technologies in the educational environment is different from the use of digital tools or apps in social life, especially during one's free time. The common idea is that in the virtual classroom environment generally, except for very rare events, bullying or misinformation does not occur, as it is fully monitored by the teacher throughout the whole process. The digital tools and e-learning platforms are mostly experienced by the teachers before they are adapted to classroom activities or recommended to students to realize their tasks or projects and performance works.

The relevant digital competences of learners include media literacy, privacy rules and internet ethics, cyberbullying, and digital addiction at the beginning of the educational year. Moreover, teachers should encourage students to take advantage of digital media, as they are a great source of immediate information, but always stress the importance of knowing how to filter sources and emphasising that they should always speak with respect and tolerance, as this will be the personal and professional brand that they will build for their future.

When it comes to learners expressing themselves online, digital facilitators should encourage students to learn as much as possible about cybersecurity, but also promote respectful behaviour. Online platforms, such as Moodle, or even WhatsApp groups, can be managed to avoid conflicts and educate the members through set rules.

Dimension 3: Specific Competences

Dimension 3.1: Information and media literacy

Information and media literacy

Knowing how to reach the correct information at the right source and media literacy are top topics in this digital age and necessary to incorporate learning activities, assignments and assessments which require students to articulate information needs.

Besides teaching school subjects' teachers should also guide students to find information and resources in digital environments. They can also lead students to organise, process, analyse and interpret information to compare and critically evaluate the credibility and reliability of information and its sources.

At this level, teachers make little use of strategies to foster students' information literacy and encourage them to use digital tools to search for the necessary information they need. In fact, they do not think much about guiding students to reach reliable sources of information or resources.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

Teachers of these level implement activities to foster students' information and media literacy and use a range of pedagogic strategies for it. Moreover, they use different types of pedagogic strategies to enable students to compare and combine information. Teachers implement learning activities where students can use digital tools to reach correct and reliable information.

This is the intermediate level, and it corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

At this level, teachers plan their courses with activities improving students' critical and comprehensive thinking abilities. They use innovative formats to foster students' information and media literacy. Teachers, according to their proficiency level, reflect, discuss, design and re-design their innovative pedagogic strategies to create and improve students' awareness of information and media literacy. eTwinning and Scientix platforms are great platforms in this sense. Teachers can run international eTwinning projects to improve students' knowledge of media literacy and improve their use of digital tools.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for facilitating learners' digital competence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To articulate information needs and according to their needs they develop personal search strategies for a better quality of the information found.
- To analyse, evaluate and compare the credibility and reliability of sources of data, information, and digital content.
- To organise, store and retrieve data, information, and content in digital environments.

Dimension 3.2: Digital communication & collaboration

Digital communication and collaboration

Students need to use digital communication and collaboration tools effectively and in civic participation to incorporate learning activities, tasks, assignments, and assessments. Such activities encourage students to interact through a variety of digital technologies. They can understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context and share data, information, and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies.

In the global digital world, students will be able to seek opportunities for self-empowerment and for participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies.

At this level, teachers show their progress by making little use of strategies fostering learners' digital communication and collaboration and encouraging them to use digital technologies for communication and collaboration. While some teachers do not or very rarely think of fostering students' digital communication and collaboration some teachers really encourage their students to use digital technologies to interact with other students, their teachers or trainers, management staff and third parties.

The basic level corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, some teachers show their progress by implementing various educational activities to foster students' digital communication and collaboration. And while preparing these activities they use different ranges of pedagogies. Those learning activities are mostly based on using digital tools for communication and teachers guide students in respecting behavioural norms, appropriately selecting communication strategies and channels, and being aware of cultural and social diversity in digital environments. Teachers who are more skilful at this level use a range of different pedagogic strategies in which students use digital technologies for communication and collaboration. Such teachers support and encourage students to use digital technologies to participate in public discourses and to use digital technologies actively and consciously for civic participation.

This is the intermediate level, and it corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

On the other hand, more skilful teachers on digital communication and collaboration incorporate assignments and learning activities which require learners to use digital technologies for communication, collaboration, knowledge co-creation, and civic participation effectively and responsibly. They critically reflect on how suitable their pedagogic strategies are in fostering learners' digital communication and collaboration and adapt their strategies accordingly due to that reflection, they discuss, re-design and innovate pedagogic strategies for fostering learners' digital communication and collaboration.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital technologies for digital communication & collaboration competence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To know the appropriate and the right digital communication tools to interact, and share data and information and digital content.
- To know referencing and attribution practices and participate in society using public and private digital services.
- To seek opportunities for self-empowerment and participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies.
- To use digital tools for collaborative learning activities.
- To use digital tools to be aware of behavioural norms.
- To be aware of cultural and generational diversity in digital environments and to adapt communication strategies to the specific audience.
- To be able to use more than one digital identity and protect them.

Dimension 3.3: Digital content creation

Digital content creation

Students should incorporate digital learning activities, tasks, assignments, and assessments to express themselves through digital means, and to modify and create digital content in a different format. Students should be aware of internet rules and ethics how copyright and licenses apply to digital content, and how to reference sources and attribute licenses. Creating and editing digital content improves students' encouragement in realizing their tasks in future, too. They will gain the skill of understanding how to plan and develop a sequence of understandable instructions for a computing system to solve a given problem or perform a specific task.

At this level, while some teachers encourage students to use digital content creation by producing texts, images, and videos but some of them do not or only very rarely consider it.

This is the basic level that corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, teachers implement educational activities in which students use digital tools to produce digital content, e.g., in the form of text, photos, other images, videos, etc. They encourage learners to publish and share their digital productions. Some more skilled teachers at this level use different pedagogic strategies to enable students to express themselves digitally, e.g., by contributing to wikis or blogs, or by using ePortfolios for their digital creations. They encourage and enable students to understand the concept of copyright and licenses and how to re-use digital content appropriately

This is the intermediate level, and it corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately some teachers detect and counteract plagiarism, e.g., by using digital technologies. They critically think about the suitability of their pedagogic strategies in fostering their students' creative digital expression and adapt their strategies to it appropriately. They guide their students in designing, publishing, and licensing complex digital products, e.g., creating websites, blogs, games or apps. And according to the feedback of students and the evaluation of how the effectiveness of the implied formats teachers improve it.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using digital content competence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To prepare and edit digital content in different formats and use them to express themselves.
- To modify, refine, improve, and integrate already existing and necessary knowledge.
- To develop original and content-relevant modules and know how copyright and licenses apply to data, information, and digital content.
- To plan and develop understandable instructions for a computing system to solve a given problem or perform a specific task

Dimension 3.4: Responsible use

Teachers should take measures to ensure students' physical, psychological, and social well-being while using digital technologies as well as empower them to manage risks and use digital technologies safely and responsibly.

Responsible use

Teachers should encourage students to use digital technologies with a positive impact in a creative and critical manner. Although it serves lots of positive effects on our school and social life, digital technology also contains and faces various risks and threats. Students should know internet safety and security measures to protect their personal data and privacy in digital environments to avoid health risks and threats to physical and psychological well-being while using digital technologies

On one hand, teachers make little use of strategies to foster their students' digital well-being since they know digital technologies can positively and negatively affect learners' well-being. However, some teachers foster students' awareness of how digital technologies can positively and negatively affect health and wellbeing, e.g., by encouraging them to identify behaviour (of their own or of others) that makes them happy or sad. I foster learners' awareness of the benefits and drawbacks of the openness of the internet.

This is the basic level that corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, teachers with more skills give practical and experience-based advice on how to protect privacy and data, e.g., using passwords, adjusting the settings of social media and assisting them in how to protect their digital identity and managing their digital footprint. Teachers at this (intermediate) level develop strategies to prevent, identify and respond to digital behaviour that negatively affects learners' health and wellbeing (e.g., cyberbullying) and encourage them to create a positive attitude towards digital technologies and be aware of possible risks and limits. The students become confident enough that they can manage possible risks and limits.

This is the intermediate level, and it corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately students understand the digital risks and threats in the digital environment like identity theft, bullying, fraud, stalking, and phishing and how to react to them appropriately. Teachers adapt their strategies to foster students' digital well-being. And, some teachers innovate approaches to foster students' ability to use digital technologies for their own well-being and discuss and re-design it due to their needs.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in using responsible use competence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To protect digital devices and digital content and understand digital risks and threats in digital environments.
- To be aware of digital safety, internet risks, internet security and safety measures to be taken and understand it.
- To know details on not leaving digital footprints in the digital world and how to protect themselves and others from any damage.
- To know and learn much about digital well-being.
- To monitor students in the digital world, especially in collaborative and communicative tasks and give prompt feedback or reaction to any digital threat.

Dimension 3.5: Digital problem solving

Digital problem solving

Students can identify and solve technical problems or transfer technological knowledge creatively to new situations. Students can identify technical problems when operating devices and using digital environments, and solve them. They can easily adjust and customise digital environments to personal needs. They can identify, evaluate, select, and use digital technologies and possible technological responses to solve a given task or problem and use digital technologies in innovative ways to create knowledge. With such qualifications, students can understand where their digital competence needs to be improved or updated and support others in their digital competence development.

On one hand, teachers do not consider much, or very little, on how to foster students' digital tools using ability and how to solve any digital problems whenever they faced them. Besides teachers encourage students how to solve technical problems using trial and error. They encourage them to transfer their digital competence to new situations.

This is the basic level that corresponds to the levels Newcomer (A1) and Explorer (A2) of the CEFR framework adopted in the DigiCompEdu Framework, 2017.

On the other hand, teachers implement learning activities in which students use digital technologies creatively and develop their technical knowledge and skills on it. Teachers also encourage students to collaborate and learn from each other. Teachers also implement different pedagogic strategies to enable students to apply their digital competence to new situations and encourage them to reflect on the limits of their digital competence and help them identify suitable strategies for further developing it

This is the intermediate level, and it corresponds to levels Integrator (B1) and Expert (B2) of the CEFR framework.

Ultimately teachers at this level enable students to seek out different solutions for digital and technological problems, make use of its benefits and gain the skills of critical and creative thinking to solve problems. Teachers also enable students to apply their digital competence in unconventional ways to new situations and creatively come up with new solutions or products.

The advanced level corresponds to levels Leader (C1) and Pioneer (C2) of the CEFR framework.

In a nutshell, to improve the level of competence in problem-solving competence and reach a higher level of this specific competence, educators need to:

- To adjust and adapt digital technology and tools to personal needs and identify digital problems while using digital tools and to solve them.
- To solve a given task or problem, teachers should identify, evaluate, select, and use digital technologies and possible technological solutions.
- To create necessary knowledge teachers should use digital tools in an innovative way and they must improve their needed competence and update it.
- To develop their digital competence in order to be up to date.

Gamification

What is gamification

Traditional schooling is perceived as ineffective and boring by many students. Although teachers continuously seek novel instructional approaches, it is largely agreed that today's schools face major problems around student motivation and engagement (Lee & Hammer, 2011). The use of educational games as learning tools is a promising approach due to their ability to teach and reinforce not only knowledge but also important skills such as problem-solving, collaboration, and communication. Games have remarkable motivational power; they utilize a number of mechanisms to encourage people to engage with them, often without any reward, just for the joy of playing and the possibility to win.

Today's learners are digital natives and have new profiles. They grew up with digital technologies and have different learning styles, new attitudes to the learning process and higher requirements for teaching and learning. Teachers are facing new challenges and have to solve important issues related to the adaptation of the learning process towards students' needs, preferences and requirements. Teachers have to use different teaching methods and approaches that allow students to be active participants with strong motivation and engagement in their own learning. Modern pedagogical paradigms and trends in education, reinforced by the use of ICT, create prerequisites for use of new approaches and techniques in order to implement active learning.

According to Kapp gamification is "using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve problems." (Kapp, 2012) Gamification is the use of game thinking, approaches and elements in a context different from the games.

The use of game mechanics improves the ability to learn new skills. Game approaches lead to a higher level of commitment and motivation of users to activities and processes in which they are involved. The main problems in modern education are related to the lack of engagement and motivation of students to participate actively in the learning process. Because of that, teachers try to use new techniques and approaches to provoke students' activity and motivate them to participate in training. One possible solution is to reward the efforts and achieved results with awards, which leads to increased motivation for participation and activity. That decision is based on the use of game elements in the learning process.

Gamification in education is the use of game mechanics and elements in the educational environment. E-learning, based on ICT, creates favourable conditions for the implementation of gamification – the processes of processing students' data and tracking their progress are automated and software tools can generate detailed reports. Implementation of game elements in education is logical since there are some facts that are typical for the games and training. Users' actions in games are aimed at achieving a specific goal (win) in the presence of obstacles. In education, there is a learning objective, which has to be achieved by performing specific learning activities or interacting with educational content. Tracking the players' progress in games is an important element because the next steps and moves are based on their results. In education tracking the students' progress is essential to achieve the learning objectives. Collaboration in education is a milestone for the effective implementation of active learning. Unlike training, games possess a strong competitive element. The focus in the learning process should be rather towards developing skills for collaboration and teamwork and responsibility for the performance of the group instead of competition between students. Gamification is not directly associated with knowledge and skills.

Gamification affects students' behaviour, commitment and motivation, which can lead to the improvement of knowledge and skills (W. Hsin-Yuan Huang, D. Soman, 2013).

Games have some distinctive features which play a key role in gamification:

- Users are all participants
- Challenges/tasks that users perform and progress towards defined objectives;
- Points that are accumulated as a result of executing tasks;
- Levels which users pass depending on the points;
- Badges which serve as rewards for completing actions;
- Ranking of users according to their achievements.

The development of an effective strategy for the implementation of gamification in e-learning implies a depth analysis of existing conditions and available software tools. The main steps of the strategy include:

- 1) Determination of learners' profiles.
- 2) Definition of learning objectives.
- 3) Creation of educational content and activities for gamification.
- 4) Adding game elements and mechanisms.

There are many tools for gamification. Some of them are web-based (cloud services) and do not require the installation of special software and allow access at any time and from any location. The most popular gamification tools are Socrative, Kahoot!, FlipQuiz, Duolingo, Ribbon Hero, ClassDojo and Quizlet, Qizzizz, Mentimeter, and Kialo Edu.

Gamification tools

Kahoot⁴

What is Kahoot?

Kahoot is a quiz-based learning platform that works for hybrid learning and flipped classroom situations by making learning fun and engaging. It's a question-based website that a teacher can use in class. The main goal of Kahoot is to ask questions entertainingly. Kahoot! is a cloud-based quiz platform that is ideal for students and teachers. Since the game-based platform allows you to create new quizzes from scratch, it's possible to be creative and offer bespoke learning options for students. Kahoot! offers a question and then optional multiple-choice answers. This can be accompanied by rich media such as images and videos to add more interactivity.

Kahoot is an online game-based learning platform. It allows teachers, organizations, and parents to set up fun web-based learning for others. This could include your coaches, athletes, or parents. Kahoot can be used as a fun trivia activity to do with members of your organization or coaches to use with their sports players or it can be just a series of fun questions.

What can Kahoot do?

- Online quizzes which can be used in face-to-face, hybrid and online education
- Multiple choice questions
- Quizzes can be accompanied by rich media such as images and videos
- Live or self-paced quizzes
- Timer-based quiz mode switched on or off
- Contests with response analytics and winners

How is Kahoot working?

On the Kahoot website - www.kahoot.com, there are two main ways in which you can set up a game which is outlined as follows:

1. Classic Kahoot (host live) – the organizer of Kahoot, would set up a series of questions/trivia, and each participant would need access to a device (laptop, iPad, phone, etc). Questions would be posted and participants have a set time to answer the questions. Everyone plays at the same time. The organizer of the Kahoot would need to be able to share their screen with the participants as the questions only appear on the organizer's screen. There are a variety of question types that can be used from multiple choice to puzzle to open-ended questions. The Classic Kahoot can be used as a fun social activity through an online meeting/chat module (i.e. – Zoom)

2. Student-paced challenge – organizers set up a series of questions/trivia for the participants to play at their own pace at home. Participants would see both the question and possible answers or space to submit an answer on their screen. The student-paced challenge could be used as a way to challenge players on their knowledge of the game or just as a fun activity for them to do at home with questions related to the sport they play. Kahoot can be used for free or premium packages can be purchased for a fee.

While Kahoot can be used in the classroom, it's ideal for remote learning use. Teachers can set a quiz and wait to see the scores as students complete it. Or they can carry out a live hosted quiz using

⁴ What is Kahoot! and How Does it Work for Teachers? <https://www.techlearning.com/how-to/what-is-kahoot-and-how-does-it-work-for-teachers>

video – with third-party apps such as Zoom or Meet – to be there as students are working through the challenges.

Source: Kahoot

While there is a timer-based quiz mode, you can also choose to turn that off. In that instance, it's possible to set more complex tasks that require research time.

Teachers can also review results and run analytics from game reports for formative assessments so as to better judge progress being made in the class.

To get started head to getkahoot.com and sign up for a free account. Select "Sign Up," then pick "Teacher" followed by your institution's level "school," "higher education," or "school administration." You are then able to register using your email and a password or with a Google or Microsoft account – ideal if your school already uses Google Classroom or Microsoft Teams.

BookWidgets⁵

What is BookWidgets?

BookWidgets is an easy-to-use platform for creating interactive exercises like exit slips, games, timelines, photo- and video-based activities, and more. It integrates with other programs like Google Classroom, Canvas, and Moodle. A diverse library of widgets can be used to support all subject areas. Widgets are grouped by test and review (exit slips, flashcards, quizzes, timelines, and worksheets), games (bingo, memory, and crosswords), pictures and videos (hot-spot image, YouTube player, and image carousel), and math (active plot, charts, and arithmetic). Teachers can also embed PDFs, Google Maps, and Wikipedia articles.

⁵ BookWidgets: Design Interactive and Engaging Digital Content

<http://www.edtechroundup.org/reviews/bookwidgets-design-interactive-and-engaging-digital-content>

What can BookWidgets do?

- Interactive exercises like exit slips, games, timelines, and photo and video-based activities
- Integrates with other programs like Google Classroom, Canvas, and Moodle
- Customise 40 different widgets
- Embed PDFs, Google Maps, and Wikipedia articles
- Share widgets as a link or embedded
- Simple assessments with flashcards, puzzles, or games such as hangman or bingo
- 30+ types of quiz questions suitable for students' self-grading

How is BookWidgets working?

Teachers can customize each of the widgets, and a wizard walks them through the building process. Teachers can share finished widgets as a link or embed them on any website or through Google Classroom. Analytics allows teachers to track and assess student activity. A weekly teacher blog suggests new approaches and practical applications.

The graphic features a blue background with white text. At the top, it says "Create your own interactive exercises and auto-graded assignments in minutes!". Below this, there is a list of five benefits, each preceded by a checkmark: "Motivate your students", "Formative & summative evaluation", "Follow student progress in realtime", "Save time grading", and "Differentiate and give personalized feedback". To the right of the list is an illustration of a teacher standing at a whiteboard, pointing at it, with two students sitting at desks in front of the board. At the bottom left, there is an orange button that says "Start for free". At the bottom center, there are two yellow arrows pointing downwards.

Source: BookWidgets

BookWidgets allows teachers to create a ton of different types of interactive content. Examples of each type of widget are available to use as a template to start out, and a tutorial walks you through the steps. There are 40 different widgets you can create that can be shared through a link, a QR code, an email, and Google Classroom. Simple assessments you can integrate include exit slips, quizzes, and worksheets. Kids can practice and review skills with flashcards, puzzles, or games such as hangman or bingo.

Create a blended/flipped learning approach with personalized materials that can be easily assigned through your Google Classroom. When creating quizzes, select from over 30 types of questions for all content areas. Include answers in the setup so that quizzes can be self-grading and students can gain instant feedback. Differentiate digitally by creating versions of one worksheet and assigning it to groups of students in Google Classroom. The WebQuest widget is especially useful for a blended approach; within the widget, you can embed instructional videos, games, and quizzes.

Creating interactive classroom activities and engaging teaching materials is mostly a breeze with BookWidgets. Though the organization of widgets may be clunky and confusing, it's generally straightforward and easy to understand, saving teachers' valuable preparation time. The variety of 40+ widgets encourages teachers to try digital lessons with a step-by-step guide when starting out.

Examples of all widgets are also available and can be copied for use. Since there's such a wide variety of widgets, teachers can create simple lessons and activities for all learning needs, though the activities themselves -- especially the games -- tend to prioritize memorization and recall.

Teachers can individualize lessons and activities to meet the needs of students and engage them with a digital approach. The assessment options are useful: exit slips, quizzes, and worksheets offer immediate feedback, especially since they can be created as self-checking. Teachers can also see what student work has been turned in to continually monitor progress.

PlayBrighter⁶

What is PlayBrighter?

In this technological age where kids have access to, and are able to immerse themselves in high-quality game environments that test their gathered knowledge, acquired skills and ingenuity in engaging and fast-action situations, it is a constant struggle for teachers to monitor and assess learning in engaging and stimulating ways that are relevant to students of the digital age – it's now a fact that the photocopied 20 question hand-out just doesn't cut it anymore as the students don't place any value on what they see as an out-dated method of assessment.

There is also the chore of having to mark countless, test papers that are sometimes scruffy, illegible and have the potential to get mislaid. Surely, in this day and age, there must be a better way. Well, there is and it's called PlayBrighter!

What can PlayBrighter do?

- Set students 'missions'
- Assess learning in engaging and stimulating ways
- Provides analytics for students' progress and results

How is PlayBrighter working?

Playbrighter is a game-based learning environment, which contains over 20,000 curricula-based questions to get teachers started and which they can then add to if they want to, allowing them to test their students on any subject area they wish. The subjects that are covered include:

- English (Key Stages 2, 3 and 4)
- Mathematics (Key Stages 2, 3 and 4)
- Key Stages 2 and 3 Science
- GCSE Biology, Chemistry and Physics
- Key Stages 3 and 4 Geography
- Key Stage 3 and 4 R.E
- Key Stage 3 and 4 PSHE and Citizenship

There are differentiated questions so that missions can be tailored to suit students of varying abilities, either from a group-wide point of view or on an individual-student basis. On 'PlayBrighter', teachers set their students 'missions', which challenges them to play one of the games. They progress through the game by answering the questions that the teacher has set. So, as PlayBrighter state on their website for instance, "In the French room, students might release a Number One single by mastering the passé composé or defeat an international conspiracy by conjugating "avoir" or in the science area, students may be successful by calculating the speed of an object or stating the formula for Carbon Dioxide.

⁶ PlayBrighter – Educational games for your class <https://www.whiteboardblog.co.uk/2012/09/playbrighter/>

When students are successful on their 'missions' they are rewarded by earning some of the game environment currency. They can use this to personalise different aspects of their avatar by purchasing new clothes or having a different hair colour etc.

Now for teachers, 'PlayBrighter' automatically marks the work of the students as they complete each mission saving teachers huge amounts of valuable time that they would otherwise spend marking. The teacher area also offers a complete detailed breakdown of those assessments, including informative charts that track individual students' progress. This applies to whether the teacher runs tests within the classroom or sets the 'missions' for homework.

The most fantastic aspect of 'PlayBrighter' is that it is completely free, all teachers have to do is sign up a group of students and set them a mission. Students will find the game enjoyable, engaging and immersive and will probably forget that they are actually learning, as they will find 'PlayBrighter'.

Kialo Edu

What is Kialo Edu?

Kialo is an online public discussion platform launched in 2017. It is designed to facilitate reasoned online debates about complex topics in the classroom.

Kialo Edu is a free platform where educators can engage their students in thoughtful discussions. It is a powerful argument mapping tool used by teachers and professors worldwide to boost their student's critical thinking and reasoning skills. Its clear, visually compelling format makes it easy to follow the logical structure of a discussion and facilitates thoughtful collaboration.

With Kialo, you can start discussions on any topic, no matter how big or small, and examine the location of the topic in depth through discussion. You can create special discussions for the class or contribute to the most controversial topics in the world and gain a universal perspective.

With Kialo Edu, teachers can have engaging and well-structured classroom discussions with their students about any given topic. The students will be able to write claims, cite sources, collaborate, comment, and vote on the impact of each other's contributions. Teachers can assign specific tasks for the discussion and give specialized teacher feedback that can be either private or visible to all.

What can Kialo Edu do?

Kialo's mission is to transform the world into a more thoughtful environment.

Teachers can use Kialo Edu to:

- Help students get to the core of the issues they are discussing
- Put their knowledge into action
- Sharpen their critical reasoning skills
- Demonstrate their understanding
- Engage constructively with each other

Take the classroom discussions online, break down complex subjects for students, and shake them up with new types of assignments.

Teachers can create discussions for their, students where they can put their knowledge into practice, develop their own views on classroom contents, and consolidate what they've learned. In a Kialo discussion, every student has a voice-there is no talking over each other, and students have the space to explore arguments at their own pace. Kialo's collaborative platform encourages students to work together to find the best way to express each idea.

In addition, the topology of the debate allows you to graphically display the general trends in the debate. The green colour and its shades in the discussions reflect the degree of support and support for the opinion, while the red colour and its shades indicate the opinions and degrees of opposition to the opinion.

How is Kialo Edu working?

With Kialo, discussions and debates are clearly visualized as an interactive tree of pro and con arguments. At the top of every discussion is the thesis, which is supported or challenged by pro and con claims. Each one of these claims can in turn branch into subsequent claims that support or challenge them.

It is a perfect collaboration tool. Each claim has a comment section underneath that allows you to give students feedback, suggest improvements, and ask questions without cluttering the surface of the discussion. Similarly, students can easily collaborate with each other to improve their arguments, examples, and phrasing.

You can set up teams for each of your classes to easily share and organize the content you want your students to see. All content on Kialo-Edu.com is private, and accessible only to the people you share it with.

And educators can use this collaborative tool that improves creative and critical thinking just by having an account.

Quizlet

What is Quizlet?

Quizlet is a digital learning tool that can be used by students, parents and teachers. This site has more than 100 million sets of study materials created by other users on a very large scale of topics, from Landmark Supreme Court Cases to Structures of the Heart. The site is available in English, Spanish and German. But it also supports many international languages/keyboards for those who want to input text in many languages. These study sets are free to use and the users can create their own quizlets.

Quizlet takes information and converts it into flashcards, quizzes, and games so that users can study the same information in various forms. And users aren't constrained to using just text – images and audio are easy to include in study materials. The best of all is that all study materials can be shared with students, classmates, parents, and teachers.

What can Quizlet do?

Quizlet is a web-based application developed to help students study information through interactive tools and games. Quizlet's mission is to help students and teachers practice and master what they're learning. It is a tool that can be used for all courses but is especially useful for courses that is heavy with terms and definitions and/or a course with no textbook.

Textbooks often include an online site where students can access practice quizzes and flashcards among other tools to help self-assess their knowledge and to study for upcoming tests/exams. Quizlet provides these same practice-type tools and can be customized by the course instructor. In addition, Quizlet can also be used "live" in a classroom setting for active engagement with course materials and for reviewing concepts. The benefits of Quizlet are:

- Question sets will help students prepare for tests and exams
- Students can have fun studying by using the game formats that Quizlet has to offer

- Great for online and hybrid courses to make the material more engaging
- For face-to-face classes, the live version allows students to collaborate and compete
- Students can download the Quizlet app to study on the go
- You can create multiple, custom question sets

How is Quizlet working?

In order to use the Quizlet tool in our courses both teachers and students need those resources.

- Laptop or computer with internet access
- An account with Quizlet (free)
- A question set

You can create a single question set each time by clicking “create” at the top of the Quizlet screen. Or you may also want to create a folder (if planning to make multiple sets for a certain class) by clicking on “create folder” on the left-hand side of the Quizlet home page.

- If using “live”, students need to have their own electronic device (phone, laptop or computer)

Quizlet modes include timed games, which are great for getting those competitive-natured students in your classroom actively involved in their learning, instead of passively trying to memorize a list of vocabulary. Students, their parents and teachers can track their progress to determine what material needs to be focused on to achieve mastery.

Skills and competences for using gamification tools

Today's learners are digital natives and have new profiles. They grew up with digital technologies and have different learning styles, new attitudes to the learning process and higher requirements for teaching and learning. Teachers are facing new challenges and must solve important issues related to the adaptation of the learning process towards students' needs, preferences, and requirements. Teachers must use different teaching methods and approaches that allow students to be active participants with strong motivation and engagement in their own learning. Modern pedagogical paradigms and trends in education reinforced using ICT, create prerequisites for use of new approaches and techniques to implement active learning. Gamification in training is one of these trends.

According to Kapp gamification is “using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve problems.” (Kapp, 2012)

Gamification is the use of game thinking, approaches, and elements in a context different from the games. Using game mechanics improves motivation and learning in formal and informal conditions (GamifyingEducation.org). Various definitions overlap and we can summarize gamification as: Gamification is an integration of game elements and game thinking in activities that are not games.

Implementation of game elements in education is logical since there are some facts that are typical for the games and training. Users' actions in games are aimed at achieving a specific goal (win) in the presence of obstacles. In education, there is a learning objective, which must be achieved by performing specific learning activities or interacting with educational content. Tracking the players' progress in games is an important element because the next steps and moves are based on their results. In education tracking the students' progress is essential to achieve the learning objectives. Students' learning path is determined by the achieved levels of knowledge and skills (Glover, 2013). Collaboration in education is a milestone for the effective implementation of active learning. The focus in the learning process should be rather towards developing skills for collaboration and teamwork and responsibility for the performance of the group instead of competition between students. Gamification is not directly associated with knowledge and skills. Gamification affects students' behaviour, commitment, and motivation, which can lead to the improvement of knowledge and skills (W. Hsin-Yuan Huang, D. Soman, 2013).

Gamification refers to an innovative technology that meets the modern requirements of a digital society. Recently, the elements of gamification are actively introduced into the educational processes of schools, and educational organizations of secondary vocational, and higher education. To use gamified digital tools in school subjects successfully teachers need to have some general skills and improve their competences in this area. The required skills and competences are:

- To be interested in the gamification tools that can be adapted to the 5E Teaching and Learning model.
- To use game-based mechanics, aesthetics, and game thinking to engage students in the teaching topic, promote their learning and solve any educational problems.
- To distinguish and use motivating and entertaining gamification tools that attract students with weak proficiency into participating in classroom learning.
- To use collaborative gamification tools to increase the soft skills of the students has the same importance as their hard skills.
- To choose a gamified LMS that aligns with his/her current teaching method, the topic of the teaching theme or unit, the profile of students and the other educational resources.
- To acquire a working knowledge of how gamification tools/platforms operate and their varied features and options.
- To create a variety of assignments that will be appealing and challenging to students with different profiles of students.
- To use gamified video or audio collaborative digital tools not only to improve students' collaborative skills but also to give them tasks for co-construction and co-creation of resources and knowledge in order to improve students' creative skills.

- To consider the level of their students, teaching objective and each course's requirements before choosing a gamification tool and planning its implementation, especially when it's the first time they are implementing it.
- To protect sensitive digital content, apply privacy and copyright rules, to understand the use and creation of open licenses and open educational resources and their proper attribution.
- To help students to deal with failure as part of the learning process – in a gamified learning process, failure can be part of learning avoiding students experiencing anxiety when facing the chance to fail.
- To apply game elements and game thinking in schools' activities will help to provide flow to students.
- Create challenges tailored to the student's level of knowledge, increasing the difficulty of these challenges as the student acquires new skills.

Gamification is an innovative technology, considered a leading trend in education at all levels. It has significant potential in the formation of digital skills in students and in increasing their motivation to learn. Teachers teaching students at all grades and with different skills need to improve their digital skills and competences to keep up to date. And they have various opportunities to improve their professional development in that area. They can attend in-service training, and learn from their colleagues or students, they can make use of many didactic videos on YouTube or at virtual free training activities.

Resources and further reading

[What is gamification?](#)

[Gamification in Education: What is it & How Can You Use It?](#)

[Gamification For Learning: Strategies And Examples](#)

Video materials

What is Gamification? A Few Ideas: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BgyvUvxOx0M>

eLearning Gamification: How to apply it: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k2W4G0zSomU>

Self-reflection

What gamification examples have you come across in your activity? How was your experience?

Artificial intelligence

What is artificial intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. These processes include learning (the acquisition of information and rules for using the information), reasoning (using rules to reach approximate or definite conclusions) and self-correction. AI applications include expert systems, natural language processing (NLP), speech recognition, and machine vision.

The history of AI dates back to the early 1950s when the first use of the term “artificial intelligence” was coined. Since then, AI has become an increasingly popular field of research and development, with advancements such as AlphaGo, the AI computer program developed by Google DeepMind that beat the world’s Go champion in 2016. Over the years, AI has been used to solve complex problems, from creating autonomous vehicles to providing medical diagnostics.

In the early days of AI, the focus was primarily on creating machines that could mimic human behaviour and perform specific tasks. This included creating chess-playing machines and programs that could recognize handwriting. As computing power increased, engineers were able to develop more complex algorithms and programs that could complete more sophisticated tasks. This included natural language processing, facial recognition, and robotics. Today, AI is used in many industries, from healthcare to finance, to provide insights and provide solutions to complex problems.

There are several types of AI that are used in various applications. The most common type of AI is rule-based AI, which uses a set of rules to determine how to respond to certain situations. Rule-based AI is used in many applications such as facial recognition, language processing, and image recognition. Another type of AI is machine learning, which uses data to learn how to recognize patterns, make predictions, and solve problems. Machine learning is used in self-driving cars, medical diagnosis, and fraud detection.

The third type of AI is reinforcement learning, which is used in robotics and autonomous vehicles. In reinforcement learning, the AI is “rewarded” for taking the correct action and is “punished” for making mistakes. This type of AI is used to teach robots how to interact with their environment and make decisions. Finally, there is deep learning, which is a type of AI that uses multiple layers of neural networks to learn from data. Deep learning is used in applications such as image recognition and natural language processing.

The benefits of Artificial Intelligence (AI) are numerous and far-reaching. AI can be used to automate tasks that are tedious or time-consuming for humans, such as data analysis and processing. This can lead to increased efficiency and accuracy in a range of industries. AI can also be used to make predictions and provide insights into data that would otherwise be impossible for humans to process. This can lead to improved decision-making and more efficient operations.

AI also has the potential to revolutionize healthcare, with the ability to diagnose diseases, recommend treatments, and even provide personalized medical advice. AI can also be used to identify fraud and provide security for digital transactions. Finally, AI can be used to create more intuitive user experiences by providing personalized recommendations and content. In short, AI can be used to improve efficiency and accuracy in a range of industries while providing insights and improving user experiences.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is not without its challenges. One of the biggest challenges faced by AI is its ability to interpret data accurately and make decisions that are free of bias. AI algorithms are often

based on existing data, which can be incomplete or skewed. This can lead to inaccurate results and biased decisions. In addition, AI systems are often not as transparent as they should be, making it difficult to understand how they make decisions and identify and correct errors.

Another challenge faced by AI is its ability to handle changes in the environment. AI systems need to be able to adapt to changes in data, user preferences, and other factors in order to remain effective. Finally, AI systems can be vulnerable to cyber-attacks, which can lead to data breaches and other security issues. These challenges are important to consider when developing and deploying AI systems.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become increasingly popular in education, with applications ranging from personalized learning to automated grading. AI can be used to create personalized learning experiences for students based on their individual needs and preferences. This can include providing targeted content and recommendations, as well as adapting the learning experience to their individual level of mastery. AI can also be used to automate grading, providing feedback to both students and instructors in a timely manner.

AI can also be used to analyse student data and provide insights into student performance. This can be used to identify areas of improvement and identify strategies for helping students succeed. Finally, AI can be used to create virtual learning environments, allowing students to learn in a safe and collaborative environment. The applications of AI in education are numerous and can help to create more effective and personalized learning experiences for students.

The future of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is bright, with potential applications ranging from healthcare to finance. In the near future, AI is expected to become more prevalent in everyday life, with applications such as autonomous vehicles, virtual assistants, and smart home devices becoming more commonplace. AI is also expected to become increasingly integrated with the internet of things, allowing devices to communicate with each other and learn from data.

In the long run, AI is expected to become even more powerful and versatile, with the potential to revolutionize the way we live and work. AI is expected to help us make better decisions, automate mundane tasks, and create more efficient processes. In addition, AI is expected to become more intelligent and capable of understanding context and making decisions based on a deeper understanding of the environment. This could lead to the development of more intelligent robots and smarter machines that can interact with humans in more natural ways.

The future of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education is exciting, with potential applications ranging from personalized learning to automated grading. AI has the potential to revolutionize the way students learn and make education more accessible to everyone. AI can be used to create virtual learning environments, and personalized learning experiences, analyse student data, and automate grading. In the future, AI will become increasingly integrated with the internet of things, allowing devices to communicate with each other and learn from data. AI has the potential to make education more effective, efficient, and accessible to everyone.

Artificial intelligence tools

Alexa Skill Blueprints

What is Alexa Skill Blueprints?

Alexa Skill Blueprints are a new way for you to customize your Alexa experience by adding personalized Alexa skills and responses. Personalized skills and responses make Alexa even more

knowledgeable, delivering a delightful experience that is unique to you and your family or classroom. You can create your own Alexa skills and responses in minutes with easy-to-use templates – just fill in the blanks. Choose from the different blueprints to see what kind of skill you'd like to make. What is interesting is that there's no limit to the number of skills you can make, so create as many as you like.⁷

What can Alexa Skill Blueprints do?

- Receive reminders when a student's class period or activity begins/ends.
- To hear Alexa summarize the school schedule, say, "Alexa, open School Schedule."
- Request to hear a student's schedule for any day of the week - "Alexa, what's Jacob's school schedule this Friday?"
- Challenge your students with open-ended questions.
- Create a story and test your memory.
- Create and access a personal list of facts on any topic.
- Learn in "review mode" to hear terms and definitions.
- Switch to "test mode," where Alexa reads the term, then you say the definition.

How is Alexa Skill Blueprints working?

Speech recognition software is used to convert verbal language into text form using algorithms. Speech recognition has become one of the widely used technologies, as it offers a great opportunity to interact and communicate with automated machines. Voice assistants, or virtual assistants, are more than just the cool, often-female voices that respond to verbal requests to play a song or check the weather. Speech recognition has become one of the widely used technologies, as it offers a great opportunity to interact and communicate with automated machines. Precisely, it can be affirmed that speech recognition facilitates its users and helps them to perform their daily routine tasks, in a more convenient and effective manner.⁸

Common inventions that use voice assistants are the famous assistants from our phones that let people control their devices with spoken commands. People can easily open an app, navigate, and edit text hands-free using just their voice. Examples of voice assistants are Amazon Alexa, Google Assistant, Apple Siri, Microsoft Cortana, and Samsung Bixby.

⁷ Alexa Skills Blueprints. <https://blueprints.amazon.com/home>

⁸ Khaled M. Alhawti (2015). *Advances in Artificial Intelligence Using Speech Recognition*. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1106879

IBM SkillsBuild

What is IBM SkillsBuild?⁹

IBM SkillsBuild for organizations provides integrated learning opportunities for students (13-18) or job seekers with free digital training, project-based learning, and coaching to help them build the skills they'll need to be career-ready. SkillsBuild for Students is a digital learning platform where people can find, plan, manage, and track all their learning and the badges they earn. SkillsBuild for Students offers a wealth of learning recommendations through channels, hot roles & skills, and programs & resources. And when you're ready to grow or switch your role, people will find job recommendations just for them.

What can IBM SkillsBuild do?

- Promote continuous learning.
- Free resources.
- Curriculum maps.
- Fun, self-placed learning for students.
- Track student progress and evaluate.
- Assign learning activities and establish due dates.
- Digital badges.
- Learning activities.
- Offers a toolkit for trainers and students too.

What is more, IBM Skills for Students makes learning suitable for everyone because it has recommended learning. Their machine learning algorithms recommend channels to students based on what they know from their profiles, their job roles, and other users like them.

How is IBM SkillsBuild working?

Today there are many services suggesting in-the-moment recommendations, as they use artificial intelligence for analyzing interactions of the users and find visually proper products that will interest any individual customer. Due to AI, recommendation engines make quick and to-the-point recommendations tailored to each customer's needs and preferences. Classic recommender system processes data through these four steps: collecting, storing, analyzing and filtering.

Another good example of recommendation engine usage in Media is done by YouTube and Netflix. YouTube with its "Recommended Videos" and "Other Movies You May Enjoy" by Netflix are lived examples of AI recommendation engine usage.¹⁰

⁹ IBM SkillsBuild. Retrieved from <http://www.skillsbuild.org/>

¹⁰ How Does AI Work With Product Recommendation Systems? Retrieved from <https://www.smarthint.co/en/ai-product-recommendation-engine/>

Chatfuel

What is Chatfuel?

Chatfuel is first and foremost a powerful chatbot builder that focuses on automation and versatility. Its main focus is building bots that can do it all, from answering questions to collecting emails.

Example of a chatbot made by Chatfuel

Chatfuel can be used for just about anything related to Facebook Messenger chatbots. Many businesses use it to increase conversions or generate leads, but you can also use it to optimize your overall engagement with your audience.¹¹

Conversational learning via bots represents an entirely new chapter in the evolution of how we educate young people. Education chatbots allow educators to populate lesson materials, answers to frequently asked questions and other engaging resources to assist your students in learning.¹²

What can Chatfuel do?

- Answer questions.
- Give clear answers.
- Extract and export useful data.
- Students don't wait in line to get an answer to their questions.
- Help students understand a subject better.
- Classroom sessions are more dynamic.
- Students enjoy their educational experience more with the bot.
- The customizable tags let the trainer provide the right content to students.
- Set up reminders (homework, class news, lesson details and other important messages).⁸

¹¹ *Chatfuel review*. Retrieved from <https://www.chatbots.org/chatfuel>

¹² *Transform your teaching with a chatbot* (2021, June 13). Retrieved from <https://www.cta.org/educator/posts/transform-teaching-with-chatbot>

How is Chatfuel working?

Chatfuel also has an AI component where you can instruct the bot to respond to certain keywords. This is another common feature that most chatbots have, and Chatfuel takes a nice, straightforward approach to it.⁸

A chatbot is a software that can talk with users automatically in a humanlike, conversational style.¹³ Chatbot makers utilize artificial intelligence and the latest conversational design to create bots that can communicate with students on all subjects of elementary, secondary, high school and up to university levels.

Furthermore, another good example of a chatbot that can be used in teaching is Botsify.

Gradescope

What is Gradescope?

Gradescope is an online grading system that allows instructors to manage, grade, and analyze student work quickly and accurately. It provides an intuitive interface that allows instructors to easily create and grade assignments, track student progress, and provide feedback. Gradescope also includes features such as auto-grading, plagiarism detection, analytics, and student collaboration.

The graphic features three icons on the left: 'EXAMS' with a document icon, 'HOMEWORK' with a document and a bar chart icon, and 'CODE' with a code editor icon. Arrows from these icons point towards the right. On the right, the text reads 'Deliver and Grade Your Assessments Anywhere'. Below this, a paragraph states: 'Gradescope helps you seamlessly administer and grade all of your assessments, whether online or in-class. Save time grading and get a clear picture of how your students are doing.' At the bottom right, there are two buttons: 'Sign Up for Free' and 'Get a Demo'.

Gradescope is a powerful and flexible grading system designed to help instructors save time and increase accuracy in their grading process. It can be used for programming assignments, multiple-choice questions, and essay questions. Gradescope also integrates with popular tools such as Canvas, iClicker, and Piazza, allowing instructors to seamlessly manage their classrooms. Additionally, Gradescope provides an easy-to-use interface for instructors to share feedback and grades with students, allowing them to easily track their progress.

What can Gradescope do?

- Create detailed rubrics and assignments quickly
- Automatically grade and provide feedback on programming assignments
- Manage and track student progress
- Analyze data and view student performance trends

¹³ Getting started. Retrieved from <https://docs.chatfuel.com/en/articles/2568024-getting-started>

- Detect plagiarism in student work
- Provide instructors with an intuitive interface for grading
- Integrate with popular tools such as Canvas and Piazza
- Allow students to easily access their feedback and grades

How is Gradescope working?

Gradescope's intuitive interface enables instructors to quickly create and grade assignments, track student progress, and provide feedback. The system also includes features such as auto-grading, plagiarism detection, analytics, and student collaboration.

Gradescope automates the grading process by providing a rubric-based system for instructors to grade their assignments. Instructors can customize their rubrics to fit the needs of their classes and assignments. Through the auto-grading feature, instructors can set up criteria for the system to grade a student's work, saving time and providing more accurate feedback. Gradescope also offers plagiarism detection, allowing instructors to identify any cases of plagiarism in their classes.

To use Gradescope, instructors should first create an account and log in. From there, they can create an assignment for their students to complete. After setting up the assignment, instructors can create a rubric with the criteria for grading each question. Once the assignment is created, instructors can upload the student's work to Gradescope. Instructors can then review the student's work and grade it using the rubric. Gradescope also offers auto-grading, allowing instructors to set up criteria for the system to grade the student's work. Finally, instructors can provide feedback to the student and view analytics on their performance.

Linguaskill

What is Linguaskill?

Linguaskill is an online assessment platform designed to measure and evaluate language proficiency. The platform offers a range of tests, including those for reading, writing, speaking, and listening, to assess language ability in a variety of contexts. Tests are tailored to the student's language level, providing a reliable measure of their abilities. Test results are delivered in an easy-to-understand format, providing an accurate assessment of language proficiency.

Linguaskill is designed to be user-friendly, helping students to easily take the test from any device. The platform also provides detailed feedback on areas of strength and weakness, allowing students to identify areas for improvement. Additionally, the platform offers support for a range of languages, making it an ideal choice for language learners of all levels. With its comprehensive assessment and detailed feedback, Linguaskill is a powerful tool for measuring language proficiency.

What can Linguaskill do?

- Measure and evaluate language proficiency
- Offer a range of tests, including reading, writing, speaking, and listening
- Tailor tests to the student's language level
- Provide an easy-to-understand report of results
- Allow students to take the test from any device
- Offer detailed feedback on areas of strength and weakness
- Support a range of languages
- Offer a comprehensive assessment of language proficiency

How is Linguaskill working?

Linguaskill is an online assessment platform designed to measure and evaluate language proficiency. The platform offers a range of tests to assess language ability in a variety of contexts, tailored to the student's language level. Tests are designed to be user-friendly, allowing students to take the test from any device. The platform also provides detailed feedback on areas of strength and weakness, allowing students to identify areas for improvement.

The accurate English test with fast results

This website allows an institution or an employer to check the authenticity of the Linguaskill Test Report. By filling in details from the Test Report, you can check if it matches the results we hold for the candidate on our database.

Check a Test Report

Fast results

Results you can trust

In-depth reporting

The platform offers support for a range of languages, making it an ideal choice for language learners of all levels. Test results are delivered in an easy-to-understand format, providing an accurate assessment of language proficiency. The platform also offers a comprehensive assessment, helping students to gain an understanding of their language abilities. With its user-friendly interface and detailed feedback, Linguaskill is an invaluable tool for language learners.

To use Linguaskill, students should first create an account and log in. From there, they can select the language and level of the test they want to take. Once the test is selected, students can take the test from any device. During the test, students will answer multiple-choice and fill-in-the-blank questions, depending on the type of test. Once the test is completed, students will receive an easy-to-understand report of their results, including an assessment of their language proficiency. Additionally, Linguaskill offers detailed feedback on areas of strength and weakness, allowing students to identify areas for improvement.

Skills and competences for using artificial intelligence tools

Artificial intelligence in its many forms is becoming more and more prevalent in our daily lives, accompanying us in practically all our actions. We constantly have smart gadgets that track our activity and provide advice for a better life, from using GPS to locate our way to measuring our heart rate when participating in sports.

To better implement this interaction, it is important to know the skills and competences that are required. How AI will influence the future of mankind and education is a crucial subject that must be answered. Reviewing the effects of AI to reinvent knowledge and education within the guiding principles of inclusion and fairness in access to high-quality learning opportunities is necessary to provide an answer.

We must now endeavour to teach people how to create a notion of the artificial mind considering AI's expanding influence. We must emphasize how the human mind differs from an artificial one. Such skills will call for comprehension of both computational thinking and the workings of AI, as well as human-centred awareness of what each technology can and cannot do.

The importance of education, colleges and universities, instructors, and teaching cannot be overstated in relation to any of these. A report from UNESCO (2021) describes AI skills and it is predominantly focused on academic AI instruction competencies.

There were proposed four categories of AI competencies:

Engineering and design thinking	As well as representation and reasoning, algorithms, and coding, are all examples of computational thinking AI abilities
Technology-oriented competences	Such as knowledge of AI methods, tools, and applications
Maker-oriented competencies	Designing AI applications and contextual data/algorithm-based problem solving
Human-oriented skills	Understanding the special nature of human intelligence, the ethical and societal implications of AI and data regulation and justice

These competences can be developed on three different levels:

- at the national inter-sectoral level, which entails selecting the appropriate AI competencies and creating a budgeted master plan;
- in the educational sector, which entails creating textbooks and assessments;
- by training teachers.

Finally, AI literacy can be developed as part of lifelong learning, which includes informal and non-formal initiatives like coding clubs and hackathons. From a different angle, AI literacy entails a wide range of AI knowledge, such as:

- What AI can and cannot do, as well as the crucial role that humans play in all of AI's technological advancements.
- AI skills, such as creating and using AI;
- AI values, such as when AI is useful and when it should be questioned.

A combination of technological and human-oriented skills is required for AI literacy. The human-oriented competences focus on issues such as data justice and regulation, the history, present, and potential futures of AI, the uniqueness of people, the ethics of AI, and its societal implications. The sophisticated AI knowledge and abilities required to design, manipulate, implement, and interpret AI, on the other hand, are technology-oriented competences, which focus on AI methodologies, technologies, and applications.

Source: Pixabay

In a nutshell, because AI is being utilized more frequently and influences our everyday decision-making throughout our lives, it is important for us to grasp what we need to accomplish it. From one perspective, AI competencies include AI knowledge, what AI can do, and what it cannot do; skills, creating and using AI; and values, when AI is useful and when it should be questioned. From another perspective, AI competencies include human-oriented competencies, computational thinking AI competencies, technology-oriented competencies, and maker-oriented competencies.

Resources and further reading

[What is artificial intelligence?](#)

[Eight Ways AI is Used in Education](#)

[Ten Roles For Artificial Intelligence In Education](#)

Video materials

What Is Artificial Intelligence? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ad79nYk2keg>

How is AI used in education? <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xW1jg1UiVwo>

Self-reflection

What artificial intelligence tools have you come across in your activity? How was your experience?

Data analysis

What is data analysis

Data analysis in the educational context includes the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their context in order to understand and optimise learning and the environments in which it occurs.

Any educational institution offers a wealth of data beyond academic results. In particular, data analysis can use student demographic information (age, ethnicity, gender, etc.), how many students are enrolled full or part-time, whether they are taught face-to-face, online or e-blended; course data, such as the number of students enrolled, grades achieved and completion rates; teacher data, such as teacher demographic information (age, ethnicity, gender, etc.), teacher salary, and teacher levels, such as the number of students enrolled, the number of students enrolled, the number of students enrolled, the number of students enrolled, the number of grades achieved and the completion rates; teacher data, such as teacher demographic information (age, ethnicity, gender, etc.), teacher salary, and teacher levels.), salary and productivity levels; facilities data, such as the use of face-to-face or virtual classrooms and resource allocation (e.g. a number of hours per week each classroom is used, etc.).

All of this information can be interpreted from a big data perspective to transform educational institutions for the benefit of teaching and learning processes. The term big data refers to the immense amount of information that is created and collected on a daily basis. This volume of data must be collected and analysed using robust data analysis software.

This interpretation helps decision-makers create and foster data-driven decision-making, leading to more successful outcomes. It also enables easier access to information, because data analysis tools rely on the same technology that is used to capture, store and organise the information. In other words, it improves the time it takes to locate it, as all the data is in one place.

This way of working allows educational institutions to help their students to identify possible problems or obstacles that they may encounter in their academic careers. In other words, it allows the school to predict the probability of success or failure in order to anticipate the reinforcement or support that each individual student may need. For example, advising to postpone the presentation of assessments in certain cases to avoid possible academic failure.

Another possibility offered by data analysis is to apply it to school guidance. Making the right decisions throughout their academic career is a concern for almost all students because of the implications for their entire professional and personal lives. Big data can be used to gather open and public data that can be accessed from a website with information on enrolment numbers, class sizes, student/teacher ratios, academic results, etc.

It is important to support students through engagement opportunities where the quality of engagement is an issue, i.e. learning process analytics can offer adaptive learning enhancement through the optimisation of learning resources on an individualised basis and the organisation of courses. These should provide learners with resources relevant to their learning profile and objectives, information about their own study habits and recommendations for improvement.

For teachers, this data can be used to map the knowledge domains of students, which can be used for the corresponding assessment, i.e. not whether a student remembers a given definition of a concept, but whether he/she can correctly apply this concept.

Data analysis in education is conceived as a flow of information in which the system receives and uses various inputs. The outputs depend on the use of the input data. When data are interpreted effectively, they contribute to the understanding of individual learners' needs and the effective use of teaching strategies at all levels.

As Schoker (2008) points out, big data can only be useful in transforming schools when it provides meaningful data that stakeholders can use to ask questions, identify problems and make informed decisions.

The quality of decision-making in different domains will foster educational innovation and differentiation of actions aimed at improving student outcomes. To ensure the quality of decisions, a number of data collection practices should be followed:

- Data collection should be accurate and timely, i.e. as far as possible in real-time. This is especially significant in the case of assessments, as they provide opportunities for corrective instruction and demonstration of understanding. Assessments provide real-time data at the end of each term or year that can help teachers understand the teaching and learning process that has taken place and the gaps along the way.
- The data collection process must ensure accuracy by training teachers and administrators to effectively collect and evaluate data (research, collection, validity, relevance, etc.). This implies that the groups involved should know and manage common tools and work systems so that they can collaborate and learn from each other to enable easy access and proper understanding of the data.

These two elements result in data that are consistent and transparent and facilitate the implementation of necessary changes. Continuous feedback loops between stakeholders are essential to maintain and refine the whole process of communication and commitment to improving learning goals.

In addition, the use of data allows for a more effective evaluation of programmes, resources and interventions that support student and school success. The education system uses data to create legislation that focuses on student achievement and progress and on meeting their specific needs.

Understanding the dynamics of data and its role is fundamental to ensuring systemic functionality and cultural integration of its use. Learning process analysis is about optimising teaching, learning and the assessment of both. It is not a substitute for existing education, but a working tool yet to be harnessed.

Data Analysis tools

Easyclass¹⁴

What is Easyclass?

Easyclass is a Learning Management System (LMS) that allows educators to create digital classes and store materials online; manage class discussions; create assignments, quizzes and exams; monitor due dates and results; and provide students with feedback, all in one place.

¹⁴ Easyclass. Retrieved from: <https://www.easyclass.com/about>

Easyclass is an easy-to-use tool, but at the same time, it is a powerful open technology solution in education. Easyclass has announced that they believe that an LMS should not be a closed system but should be a platform that connects everyone in education and promotes learning anytime and anywhere.

What can Easyclass do?

The main features available in Easyclass are intended for:

- Creating assignments and other activities online and managing notes and corrections conveniently.
- Share and store resources, content or notes online and have 24-hour access.
- Create discussion groups among students in a given class.

One of the most useful functions that this platform provides is The Integrated Gradebook feature. This feature automatically adds to students' results when a new assignment is posted in a new column of the grade book. The Gradebook stores every grade assigned by the teacher. Then, data analysis is used successfully to track students' progress and to help the teacher manage assignments.

Source: Easyclass

Easyclass allows for creating many types of activities, including debates, assignments, tests, and posts on a class wall. Through the platform, educators can easily monitor students' participation and do a follow-up on how these different activities are welcomed by students. This useful information can be then used to improve lessons to better achieve the learning objectives and to adapt to the characteristics of our students.

The platform has many channels to allow communication between teachers and students, making it easy and quick to provide feedback to students on their performance.

How Easyclass works?

- Digital classes are created and managed by teachers
- Teachers have administrative rights over students' participation in their classes.
- Students need an access code to join the class.
- Teachers can delete messages and remove class members.

- Teachers can choose to receive automatic notification of student posts in the class before they are published.

One of the main benefits of this platform is its security. It comes with a secured cloud-based SaaS with no advertisements, keeping privacy and safety in the foreground. All content created within the online classes' platform can be viewed by only the class members.

Plickers¹⁵

What is Plickers?

Plickers is an assessment tool that allows teachers to collect on-the-spot formative assessment data. Teachers can use this tool with previous planning or on the go as needed, and it is a useful tool both in face-to-face, distance learning and in hybrid learning. It is a useful data collection tool that provides teachers with the information needed to inform their instruction.

What can Plickers do?

Plickers main function is to create fun and interactive activities for students to keep them engaged and motivated, and at the same time collect useful data that the educator can use to improve their lessons, identifying the questions or explanations that are not comprehended by students and need to be modified, to adapt them to students needs and personalise them to individuals if appropriate, to evaluate students learning process and provide them with feedback when necessary.

Plickers' features that allow implementing data collection in teachers' lessons are:

- Different question types are available.
- Easy distribution in phases: ask phase, accept answers phase, stop answers phase, review phase.
- Answers from students are received in real-time.
- Stats from students' answers are produced by the application immediately after all students have answers, allowing teachers to adapt their lessons on the go, based on students' understanding.
- Possibility to add the Timer option and a countdown option.
- The "Now Playing" page shows an overview of students' answers; it shows the percentage of right and wrong answers per question, as well as to which students the answer belongs.

Source: Plickers

¹⁵ Plickers E-Learning. Retrieved from: <https://help.plickers.com/hc/en-us/articles/1260804067889-Overview-Plickers-E-Learning>

How Plickers works?

The application is intuitive and user-friendly, teachers can choose to programme questions or to do them as they go during a lesson, and this collects useful information to improve the quality of their instruction.

- Teachers need to create an account and create links for each of their students to enter Plickers.
- Different subjects can be created, and they will appear to the students of that class.
- The screen for students will appear on the students' devices, and teachers have their private view.
- Privacy: The teacher only has to provide First, Last name, email, username and password. Student information is not required to use the tool. The privacy policy states how location, use and cookies are used. Students' answers are also private.
- Accessibility: The Plickers app is free for both iOS and Android. The app can be used on phones and tablets.

Lessons Plan - Symbaloo

What is Lesson Plan?¹⁶

The Lesson Plan editor of Symbaloo allows educators to create personalised digital learning paths for students that take them to the different activities of their learning itinerary. You can use a wide range of digital resources and build the pathway block by block so that your students can learn at their own pace.

You can include resources such as videos, articles, questions and even blocks created in your Symbaloo web mixes. You can redirect students to any type of resource or even assignments and exams, thus all the content of a lesson or course can be included in the Lesson Plan that can be customised for students individually if necessary.

What can Lessons Plan do?¹⁷

The itinerary elaborated with Lesson Plans allows including multiple elements to make the learning experience more fun and immersive for students. Teachers can add different game elements such as game graphics, awards, and visual representations for students, include clues and additional explanations during assessment activities, and more.

Once elaborated the learning itineraries in the Lesson Plan, educators can access a data analysis page where data collected from students' actions is integrated in real-time, having always access to actualize information from students' performance.

By accessing the Statistics page educators have access to:

- What point of the itinerary students are.
- The number of questions answered correctly and incorrectly
- The time needed to complete each question
- Access to more detailed information from each individual student.

¹⁶ Lesson Plan. Retrieved from: <http://lessonplans.symbaloo.com/?lang=es%20 blank>

¹⁷ Statistics in real time (Lesson Plans). Retrieved from: <https://es.help.symbaloo.com/portal/es/kb/articles/%C2%A1m%C3%A1s-informaci%C3%B3n-para-tus-alumnos-27-3-2018>

Source: Symboloo

How Lessons Plan works?¹⁸

- Teachers need to register in the Lessons Plan.
- Once the itinerary is created, access “Assign and start monitoring” and obtained a code for the itinerary.
- Share the access code with students through the different options available, such as google classroom, email, QR, or link.
- Start the lesson plan and monitor in real-time your students’ progress.
- Privacy: students do not need to register in Lessons Plan to access.

Socrative¹⁹

What is Socrative?

Socrative is an application created with the aim of including smartphones in pedagogies. The main function of the app is to manage students’ participation in classroom activities in real-time. It allows the development of multiple types of evaluation activities such as tests, quizzes, and projects, and immediately provides feedback to students. Educators can monitor activity results in real time or use the outcomes of the activity to evaluate students. Then, teachers can use all the data collected by Socrative to analyse students’ progress thanks to the breaks down of responses into reports.

¹⁸ Statistics in real time (Lesson Plans).

¹⁹ Bello Pintado, A., & Merino Díaz de Cerio, J. (2017). Socrative: A tool to dinamzye the classroom. *WPOM-Working Papers on Operations Management*, 8, 72–75. <https://doi.org/10.4995/wpom.v8i0.7167>

Source: Socrative

What can Socrative do?

Socrative provides the opportunity to create tailored assessment activities that students can easily respond to from any device and receive immediate feedback with the results obtained in each task by the app, as well as further feedback from the educator. Educators can also use Socrative to measure students' participation, and it can even be used to develop a continuous evaluation for students. All the data gathered by the app is stored, so that educators can easily access all information collected and use it to monitor students' progress, evaluate their performance, and identify trouble areas for specific students and the class as a whole.

The creative activities are not only useful to evaluate the knowledge gained by students but they can also be used to motivate students, improve communication between classmates or encourage a spirit of self-learning and self-assessment. Through the test and quizzes of Socrative students can:

- Evaluate their progress or knowledge
- Check their progress and acquired core ideas and competencies against established criteria
- Assess progress by comparing current understanding with prior knowledge
- Answer open-ended questions by using observations, evidence, and previously accepted explanations.

The main features of Socrative are:

- Creation of 1 public room with a capacity of 50 students
- Possibility to create quizzes, rankings, and multiple question types available (multiple choices, true/false and short answer).
- Space Race assessment: questionnaires with timer.
- Access to the online help centre.
- Real-time access to activities results by the educator.
- Visual sharing of assessment results through the app reports.

- Compatible with most devices and available in multiple languages

How is Socrative working?

1. Register and create a class (with an access code for students).
2. Create activities and tasks for students through the intuitive and easy-to-use app.
3. Set deadlines for students to complete the task and access their results to evaluate them.
4. Use the simplify app reports to assess and monitor students' progress.

Eduflow – Peer Review

What is Eduflow?

Eduflow is a very easy-to-use platform with great accessibility from any type of device that allows one to design and develop complete online courses with personalised features and activities. Between its activities, we find question-and-answer exercises, virtual debates, group tasks, self-assessment activities and more. It is especially relevant because it has a Peer review option that allows students to review each other works and share feedback and ideas.

What can Eduflow do?

The Peer Review option of this application will encourage students to collaborate and help each other, give feedback to other students, as well as reflect on their own learning by reading and assessing other students' work. The app will foster their motivation and engagement, support them to learn to work independently, help them understand the intention behind the work they do, and improve their critical thinking capabilities.

EduFlow incorporates a Dashboard area where educators can monitor their courses and easily visualize students' progress. This section incorporates graphs and organize data on activity completion, active learners through time, and rubric question insights. Additionally, it is possible to visualize, and organize the Peer Review tool, set up and monitor these activities and assess how useful the feedback received is for students in each task.

The following are the main features of Eduflow Peer Review:

- Space for students to submit their work, and multiple types of assignments are possible.
- Establish deadlines
- Allow students to review a defined number of other submissions using a rubric presented in a question format.
- Enable different options to review and score students' work. Open or close-ended multiple-choice questions can be introduced, as well as a grading option.
- Possibility to enable an additional academic review to be provided by the educator.
- Possibility to add the self-review to the peer review option.
- Use the Feedback Reflection option for students to read, reflect and incorporate the feedback received from their peers.
- Possibility to resubmit the work after the feedback from peers is incorporated.

How is Eduflow working?

1. Creating an Eduflow Account and Course.
2. Adding Content and Submission Activities.
3. Creating a Peer Review Activity.
4. Creating Feedback Reflection and Scoring Activities.
5. Developing and Incorporating Feedback.
6. Monitoring the activity and analysing results through the Dashboard area

Source: Eduflow

Skills and competences for using data analysis tools

Educators, like many other professionals, can make use of data analysis to improve the quality of their teaching methods, as well as to facilitate their daily tasks. Investing time and resources in upskilling their data skills can have a positive impact on their work, their teaching pedagogies, and the lives of their learners

Source: Portafolio.co

1. Data analysis to improve teaching methods

Most educators already have a certain level of skills in data management and analytics, they consider elements such as grades, attendance, or participation as valuable information to track the progress of their students. However, seeing data through a more informed lens gives a new meaning to these words.

A more skilled data analysis educator can take a lot of insight from these pieces of information, especially if they use the right digital tools, they can use this information to reveal what topics they should go back to because they have not been understood, what topics are students more interested on, how to modify their teaching strategy to adapt to learners needs, etc. In addition, there are so much more pieces of information that can be collected to assess, monitor, and analyse students' performance, as well as your own as an educator. To facilitate this process, and since many classes

take place online or using e-learning platforms, we can make use of automatic generated data through these platforms, i.e., Moodle, or other learning management systems (LMS). These online educational systems generally hold the data those skilled educators can extract and manipulate to design better educational experiences for learners.

2. Data analysis to simplify tasks

In using data analytic tools to support teachers' tasks they can have the information they required to assess learners' progress in a more effective way. Many platforms generate not only data but also statistics and comparisons that can facilitate the process of recording data by the educator. The automation of this part of data analysis will make the process much easier than manually tallying statistics like the numbers of right and wrong answers in a test.

A mixture of pedagogical and technical skills are necessary for educators to implement data analysis in their teaching and benefit from it, such as the ability to know and choose the right digital tool to generate the data you required, the ability to separate the pieces of information that are valuable to measure a specific indicator, to be able to organize and visualize the information, to assess and draw conclusions from the collected data, and to transform the information obtained in actions such as feedback to learners, modifications in the teaching methodology, and future planning of lessons.

Hereafter, there is a collection of specific competencies necessary for educators that want to introduce data analysis in their practice:

- To choose the digital tools that are necessary to generate and extract the information we required, meaning to use the e-learning platforms, LMS, and digital evaluation tools (quizzes, e-portfolios, etc) that can provide the information we aim to collect to monitor our learners, that can vary depending on the learning objectives of the course and the characteristics of the target group.
- To use the already organize data that is provided by many e-learning platforms and other digital environments. These platforms already offer statistics of learners' progress, of tests or tasks performed, as well as assistance or time spent in a course.
- To be able to distinguish the trivial information for the data that can be useful to you as an educator.
- To be able to organize all the data collected from different means to be easier to assess and visualize. Many educators use tools such as excel, or the functions already provided by their learning platforms that automatically organize information.
- To draw conclusions from the collected data from learners' progress, meaning to identify students that are struggling, to be able to determine where the subject is not being correctly understood, when questions or tasks have not been adjusted to the level of the student being too easy or too difficult, etc.
- To plan and modify your teaching methods in accordance with the conclusion that you have achieved by analysing students' data. It is important to translate all this information into actions, which can be changed in a curriculum, approaching tasks or tests questions in a different way, individually providing specific feedback to students, mentoring students that are struggling for personal or academic reasons, providing more explanations to some topics or your subject or to try and make the process of learning a topic more interactive or creative.

Educators are in the position to help the student learn better, more efficiently and deeper. Using data analysis will aid educators in the tasks of identifying issues, tracking progress, and many other

actions. Digital data analysis tools can also be introduced to make the process of generating, organizing, and assessing data simpler and require less effort and skill.

Resources and further reading

[What is data analysis?](#)

[The Role of Data analysis in Education: Possibilities & Limitations](#)

[Seven Applications of Data analysis in Education](#)

Video materials

Learning analytics in a nutshell: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XscUZ8dIa-8>

How Data Help Teachers: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cgrfiPvwDBw>

Self-reflection

What data analysis tools have you come across in your activity? How was your experience?

VET digital facilitation into practice. The 5E Model

From an academic perspective, instructional design is defined as “the systematic and reflective process of translating principles of learning and instruction into plans for instructional materials, activities, information resources, and evaluation.”²⁰ Evidently, the starting point of instructional design consists of the clarification of what students should learn (Norbert, Thomas, Patrick, & Oleg, 2017, p. 1). In other words, instructional design is creating learning or instructional experiences that facilitate the acquisition of new knowledge.

Instructional designers create and deliver educational and training materials to learners from all walks of life in a variety of ways. They work with traditional paper materials, such as handouts and manuals, as well as eLearning technologies and multimedia. Their work can be seen in elementary and secondary schools universities and adult training facilities. They're also found outside the academic sector in a range of industries including health care, retail and the military.²¹

Instructional design in practice presupposes specialised and highly applied knowledge. The knowledge needed for the design of effective learning environments not only contains knowledge about particular subject matters to be taught (i.e., content knowledge). To design effective instruction and/or learning environments one needs also to possess knowledge about various generic strategies and methods of instruction, diagnostics, testing, and assessment (i.e., general pedagogical knowledge). Last, there is the need for knowledge about didactical and diagnostic potentials of content-specific tasks and idiosyncratic experiences concerning useful forms of presentation and representation, an understanding of what makes a specific content easy or difficult to learn, as well as basic knowledge about preconceptions with which learners of different age and social background enter the learning environment (i.e., pedagogical content knowledge). (Norbert, Thomas, Patrick, & Oleg, 2017, p. 20)

There are numerous ID models that instructional designers can use as their foundation when developing various learning exercises. The five most common and widely used instructional design models are Bloom’s taxonomy, ADDIE Model, Iterative Design, SAM Model, and Learning Circle Framework. Instructional design practices call for all instruction to include three primary components that form the Magic Triangle of Learning: (1) learning objectives – the goals are outcomes for the student and they should describe what the learner will be capable of at the end of a course, (2) learning activities – the actions which the instructional designer plans during the design phase. When creating both objectives and activities keep the learner in mind, (3) learning assessments – It is imperative that they are aligned with both the learning objectives and learning activities.²²

Instructional design is most effective and learning outcomes are most successful when these three pillars are built with the “intention of interdependence,” or in a way that all three support each other. Using the theories of instructional design to build teaching exercises can elicit numerous positive benefits for learners: creates focused/customised programs, encourages more student participation, sets clear and measurable objectives, creates consistency, and simplifies learning for students.

The 5E Model has been used to help frame the sequence and organisation of programs, units, and lessons and consists of the following phases: engagement, exploration, explanation, elaboration, and

²⁰ University of Santiago, “What is instructional design?”. <https://onlinedegrees.sandiego.edu/what-is-instructional-design-examples/>

²¹ Purdue University, “What is instructional design?”. <https://online.purdue.edu/blog/education/what-is-instructional-design>

²² Wengroff, J. (2019, 21 June), “What is the Magic Triangle: Aligning Learning Objectives, Training Activities and Assessment Methods”. <https://getsynapse.com/blog/what-is-the-magic-triangle-aligning-learning-objectives-training-activities-and-assessment-methods/>

evaluation. Each phase has a specific function and contributes to the trainer's coherent instruction and the students' formulation of a better understanding of scientific and technological knowledge, attitudes, and skills.

This model was developed in 1987 by the Biological Sciences Curriculum Study and it promotes collaborative, active learning in which students work together to solve problems and investigate new concepts by asking questions, observing, analysing, and drawing conclusions. 5E instructional model moves from a traditional model of instruction to a next-generation model of instruction:

Engage means that the trainer is not showing or telling the students what to do anymore. The activity should make connections between past and present learning experiences, expose prior conceptions, and organise students' thinking toward the learning outcomes of current activities.

Explore gives the students the opportunity to unpack problems, develop models or gather data. The trainer is not the one who gives, demonstrates or shows the model. During the exploration phase, students actively explore new concepts through concrete learning experiences.

The Explanation phase allows the students to think and understand how they did something. Now, it means digging deep into where the question has been answered or the problem solved and using evidence to support claims.

The elaborate step is less about reading, watching or introducing new ideas. The trainer lets the students make valuable connections: concept-to-self, concept-to-concept and concept-to-world connections that help tie anchor and investigative phenomena together.

Evaluate cannot simply mean vocabulary assessments or graded journals anymore; now it means reflecting critically on the investigative process, the hypothesis, and the anchor phenomena.

As can be seen, the 5E Model is based on the constructivist theory of learning, which suggests that people construct knowledge and meaning from experiences. By understanding and reflecting on activities, students are able to reconcile new knowledge with previous ideas. This model allows educators to create a unique learning experience for students. Trainers who can incorporate instructional models like the 5E Model into their classrooms help students build a strong foundation of knowledge through active participation. In the classroom, constructivism requires educators to build inquiry, exploration, and assessment into their instructional approach. In many ways, this means the trainer plays the role of a facilitator, guiding students as they learn new concepts.

1. Engage

The educator works in the first step of the learning cycle to gain an understanding of the previous experience of the students and recognizes any knowledge gaps. Fostering an interest in the upcoming topics and hooking the attention of children to that topic and subject is important.

To take the attention of the students to the teaching topic teachers may assign students to open questions or write down what they already know about the subject. This is also when the notion is presented for the first time to the learners.

The engagement part is the first and arguably the most important part of the 5E model. The main goal of this step is to catch students' attention to the topic. In order for students to be more interested in the title, the teacher should cover more than a single aspect of their students. There are different aspects that a teacher needs to take into consideration while teaching students such as the different backgrounds of students, also their tendencies to different topics. Though each student has their own interests, and in order to make them reach some outcomes, a teacher has to consider more than one aspect. Therefore, the main goal of the teacher should be to help as many students reach the required point.

Asking a question, defining a problem, showing a discrepant event, and acting out a problematic situation are all ways to engage the students and focus them on the instructional task. The teacher's role is to present the situation and identify the instructional task. The teacher also sets the rules and procedures for establishing the task. Successful engagement results in students being puzzled by, and actively motivated in, the learning activity. Here, the word "activity" refers to both mental and physical activity. For further implementation, teachers can use books and videos from reputable sites or sources, books that correlate to the concept, real-life pictures effective discussion, and brainstorming.

There are several ways to effectively engage students in a lesson. You might create or use an existing video, a book, or just pictures. Engaged students think in depth when teachers encourage effective questioning about the concept. Using students' prior knowledge through discussion, about everyday examples, might help them to understand or explore the concept.

In this digitalized education system teachers can prefer to use web 2.0 tools to draw the attention of all students to the topic, to take their attention and to provide reflections on the subject at the

beginning of any training program, lecture or lesson. With a variety of voting/quiz/right false, yes-no, or free word or sentence options, the interest of the class and the level of readiness can be quickly measured. The results are shown to the group instantly so that they have instant information about the information, need and motivation degree on the subject in the group.

For example, if the word cloud activity is done, a short discussion is provided on the subject based on the most repetitive words. If short sentences related to the subject, concept or terms are requested, these will be shared with the class and a productive introduction will be made to the course through correct or false highlighting. If the test is done, the readiness of the class for the course can be seen together from the correct and incorrect answer rates given to the questions and the necessary level can be continued. The tools listed below can also be used as a means of measuring attention in the later stages of the lesson and as a means of repetition/reinforcement or reminder at the end. The most important benefit/feature of these tools is to get feedback from the whole group very quickly, to analyze and show it to the group. All tools can also be used in distance learning or webinars.

Mentimeter

Why Mentimeter?

In a world of online teaching and distance learning, teachers are trying to keep students engaged and connected in new ways. Mentimeter is a perfect tool to increase classroom engagement and to make sure that everyone's voice is heard. Mentimeter can be used as an engagement tool at the beginning of the lesson to see the readiness of the students and also to create formative assessments, spark discussions and test knowledge with fun quiz competitions. It can be used in all types of education and training with people from different age groups.

What to expect from the students?

Mentimeter enables students to engage in the lesson using live polls, word clouds, quizzes, multiple-choice questions and more. It is also used to see the background of the students on the topic that is going to be taught. In order to join Mentimeter, students do not need to download the Mentimeter app or have an account to join. It is interactive and one can join the event by writing the code. Since it is interactive the responses will immediately appear on the screen as dynamic and colourful visuals, helping them better connect with the group.

Mentimeter step by step

1. Create an account on <https://www.mentimeter.com/>
2. Create a Mentimeter quiz
3. Choose a question type and write your question
4. Write options and choose the correct option
5. Create a code
6. Share the code with the students and ask them to enter menti.com with that code.

Mentimeter features

- Easy to join
- No need to download the app or have an account
- Can be used online and face to face
- Engaging and enjoyable
- Quick feedback

Wordwall

Why Wordwall?

Wordwall is a free online tool for creating learning activities. With Wordwall, teachers can enter the topic that they would like to cover in class into the Wordwall and receive a variety of ready-made, fully customisable activities such as quizzes, word games, maze chases and much more. Wordwall is designed to help teachers create an array of interactive and engaging class activities for students in person or online. This platform provides various templates for teachers to select from.

What to expect from the students?

Even if the teachers or the students are not perfect at using technology it wouldn't take so much time to use it in the classroom. It is a perfect tool to engage students in the topic of the lesson with its ready-made templates to create well-known activity types such as multiple choice, groupings, matching or more complex games and quizzes. Wordwall is web-based and with a good internet connection, one can create activities quickly and easily in minutes and share in different ways.

Wordwall step by step

1. Create an account on the webpage <https://wordwall.net/>
2. Create a customized resource with just a few words and a few clicks.
3. Select a template due to your teaching topic or theme

Wordwall features

- Easy to use
- Just need a computer or tablet
- There are many templates to use and shareable

Plickers

Why Plickers?

Plickers is a simple web 2.0 tool that makes it easy to solve test questions. While solving the questions you also have fun at the same time. While using Plickers you do not need to be in a computer lab and each student does not have to have a mobile phone or a tablet. It is a tool that every teacher can use in his classroom and that is why it is preferred so much. Plickers is an application that will make a difference in the classroom and ensure that your students participate in

the class with pleasure. You can use Plickers as an engaging and motivating tool at the very beginning of the lesson for engagement or as an evaluation tool at the end of the lesson. It also attracts the attention of the students who do not like to solve tests and participate in the lesson/activity.

Plickers is one of the tools that win the hearts of teachers with its features such as being used for every grade level, including primary school, not requiring many devices, instant viewing of results, practical use

What to expect from the students?

It is an engaging tool that increases motivation and competition in a way. While using this tool students do not have to have a tablet or a mobile phone or need internet. They only need to read the questions carefully and keep the printed QR code sheets. These code sheets, which are very similar to each other, have a card number and 4 answer options. Whatever the answer is, the students show their papers so that it stays on that stylish top.

After the questions are prepared teachers to distribute the cards to the students according to their names and start to apply. After downloading the Plickers app to your phone or tablet, you select the class. The questions you select from the questions assigned to that class will be displayed on the screen when the 'Live View' section of Plickers is selected on your teacher's computer. When students read the question and remove the correct answer, it will be reflected on this screen as you scan the QR codes with the camera of your phone or tablet, and the students will see if they answered correctly.

Plickers step by step

First, you need to have an overview of Plickers and using Plickers in class

1. Have an account on Plickers <https://get.plickers.com/>
2. Add your classes and students
3. Create content by building sets of questions
4. Print or purchase your Plickers card
5. Open the Now Playing window
6. Open the Plickers app and start your quiz
7. Enter the scanner
8. Scan your students' answers
9. View instant results
10. Move on to your next question or end the session

Plickers features

Plickers allows teachers to check in on students understanding

It is a free, interactive tech tool that uses printable “paper clickers” instead of clicker devices

- With the data collected from the students at the engagement state teacher can direct his/her lesson plan and its content to the level of students' readiness.
- Students stay engaged in the lesson as they watch to see if their cards were scanned, and their answers displayed.
- The cards can either be bought online or downloaded and printed.

Blendspace

Why Blendspace?

Blendspace is a digital learning platform for teachers to access various resources and forge bundled and interactive lessons. It is the easiest way to blend your classroom with digital content. It is a free and collaborative web.2 tool which can be used to create interactive presentations, quizzes, worksheets, events, projects, and discussion environments in a very short time. It can be used as an engagement tool at the beginning of the lesson to see the readiness of the students on the topic and to increase their motivation. It can be used as an evaluation tool at the end of the course. Teachers prepare digital contents that support in-class or out-of-class learning activities. Blendspace is compatible with mobile devices.

What to expect from the students?

Blendspace is a time saver tool. It avoids teachers and students from fumbling with flash drives, losing valuable class time, and opening emails and attachments. It is a perfect tool to flip the classroom and to save that vital classroom time for student interactions, engaging activities, or having students work independently while teachers facilitate their activities and provide feedback one-on-one.

Blendspace step by step

1. Create an account
2. Create an online session
3. Organize the settings –Choose a grade level for your students - Give your lesson a title
4. Organize the content
5. Drag&Drop Resources
6. Share the Lesson - Collaborate
7. Test the lesson

Blendspace features

- Avoids time-consuming
- Interactive and collaborative
- Enjoyable

2. Explore

Students consciously explore the new concept during the discovery process through concrete learning experiences. They may be asked to go through the scientific method and collaborate and make observations with their peers.

This stage enables learners to learn in a hands-on way.²³

Exploration: Once the activities have engaged the students, the students have a psychological need for time to explore the ideas. Exploration activities are designed so that the students in the class have common, concrete experiences upon which they continue formulating concepts, processes, and skills. Engagement brings about disequilibrium; exploration initiates the process of equilibration. This phase should be concrete and hands-on. Educational software can be used in this phase, but it should be carefully designed to assist the initial process of formulating adequate and scientifically accurate concepts. The aim of exploration activities is to establish experiences that teachers and students can use later on to formally introduce and discuss concepts, processes, or skills. During the activity, the students have time in which they can explore objects, events, or situations. As a result of their mental and physical involvement in the activity, the students establish relationships, observe patterns, identify variables, and question events. The teacher's role in the exploration phase is that of facilitator or coach. The teacher initiates the activity and allows the students time and opportunity to investigate objects, materials, and situations based on each student's own ideas of the phenomena. If called upon, the teacher may coach or guide students as they begin reconstructing their explanations. The use of tangible materials and concrete experiences is essential.²⁴

²³ <https://lesley.edu/article/empowering-students-the-5e-model-explained>

²⁴ https://bscs.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/bscs_5e_full_report-1.pdf

Slatebox

Why Slatebox?

Slatebox is an online collaboration and drawing tool which delivers a simple mechanism for drawing, collaborating and sharing content. It is a perfect tool for the Explore stage of the 5E model.

It offers a variety of good-looking templates and intuitive tools for designing and editing mind maps and charts. Creating a mind map is a simple matter of selecting a template and using the visual editor to place text and images in boxes. Those boxes can be resized and rearranged using the drag-and-drop editor. If you need more text boxes, simply add more.

What to expect from the students?

Slatebox is an interactive tool to do brainstorming in the classroom. It can be used on the interactive whiteboard, too. When students plan a project or diagram a concept teachers can offer Slatebox, it is a fast and responsive mind mapping tool. If you just want to create organization templates for your students to use offline, you can use Slatebox for that too. Create your template, download it as an image, and print it out.

Slatebox step by step

1. Registration is free for individual users of Slatebox.
2. You have the ability to create unlimited mind maps ("slates") which can be private or public.

3. In order to save the slates do not forget to close the welcome screen so that you can access more of the menu.
4. Even with the individual option, you can collaborate with one person by sharing a provided link.
5. The premium versions of Slatebox will give you more flexibility as edits can be made and viewed in real time by multiple collaborators.

Slatebox features

Slatebox can be used to implement a variety of instructional strategies:

- Brainstorm ideas
- Develop a course outline, learning module, or research project draft
- Develop story ideas or even develop a digital story
- Develop a mental model of a subject
- Map the steps of a procedure
- Map the relationships between elements of a process
- Illustrate organizational relationships
- Collaborate in real-time.

MindMeister

Why MindMeister?

Concept maps are individual learning tools. They are concrete graphs that indicate the connections of a single concept with other concepts in the same category. It is used to make meaningful connections between one's previous knowledge and the newly gained information. It functions such as visualization, association, concretization, and classification of information and also it can be used effectively in defining the scope of the new units to be learned, determining the readiness levels of the students, revealing and eliminating conceptual misconceptions and revealing how the students structure the information.

MindMeister allows us to create very nice solutions and concept maps in 10-15 minutes with less effort. It is an online interactive tool in which each participant can interfere, let others change the mind maps you create and also create online brainstorm. For example, by sharing the concept map we have created, you can direct your students to this service and create a common concept map. Thus, a product will emerge as a result of Student-Teacher work. Or we can divide them into project groups and enable our students to create a common concept map. You can also decide whether the people you invite can only view or edit your maps by them.

What to expect from the students?

It is a collaborative work in which student-student or student-teacher can collaborate. It is a perfect tool to see what the students already know about the topic of the lesson and to make connections with the topic that will be learned. Students of all ages can utilize MindMeister to study more efficiently, unleash their creative potential, and get ahead in their educational careers.

MindMeister step by step

1. Visit www.mindmeister.com to access the MindMeister dashboard.
2. Click the plus icon (+) at the top of the dashboard to create a new mind map.

3. Double-click the central (root) topic in your mind map to name your map.
4. Press ENTER to create sibling topics.
5. Press TAB to create subtopics.

MindMeister features

- Students can create their own mind maps including keywords, links, branches, and hierarchical levels to help them brainstorm ideas for essay writing.
- Maps can be shared with others for easy collaboration.
- Templates are provided to easily start a new mind map.
- Can be accessed easily in Teams and use SD72 Microsoft login to create accounts

Storyjumper

Why Storyjumper?

Storyjumper is an application where students at different levels, from preschool to higher education, can create digital storybooks individually or in groups. The application can be used for different purposes such as concept learning, authorship, creativity, development of collaborative working skills, and story-based subject learning.

It is a platform that allows you to create digital stories through a website. Story Jumper offers a wide range of users and offers you fairytale-like environments, characters, objects and pictures to use in your stories. Thanks to this platform, you can edit your digital story as you want with the visuals on Story Jumper and transfer it to the reader. With Story Jumper, users can both publish their own stories and read other users' stories. The most important feature that distinguishes Story Jumper from other book-creation tools is that the pages can be created with sound when you want. So you can create digital stories with sound on Story Jumper, which allows you to add voice-overs to your stories.

What to expect from the students?

With Story Jumper, users can add their own characters, their own environments and different voices to their digital stories created by using their imaginations. Users can share the digital stories created or read a shared story. If you're a teacher, you can create your own class and add students on StoryJumper. You can follow the stories your students have made and make corrections if you wish. By giving your students group or individual assignments, you can support the development of their imaginations. You can offer your students a draft digital book and direct them to improve it. It is an amazing and engaging way of improving students' digitalization and imagination at the same time. Also, a perfect collaborative instrument to work with peers, in groups or in class. A good tool representing 21st Century Skills.

Storyjumper step by step

1. Visit www.storyjumper.com and sign up for an account
2. Plan your lesson
3. Create a book
4. Add your classes
5. Add students or teachers
6. Students create books
7. Review the books
8. Publish books and share them with the target group (parents-students-school managers and teachers)

Storyjumper's features

- Brings authors and readers together who mutually support and encourage each other to create amazing new books
- Improves imagination and using digital tools
- Improves collaborative skills and writing skills
- A good way of process evaluation

Animoto

Why Animoto?

Animoto is a cloud-based video creation service that produces video from photos, video clips, and music into video slideshows, and customized web-based presentations. It is a Web 2.0 tool that allows users to produce videos that blend photos, video clips, text and music. Teachers can use Animoto in their classes by examining their existing curriculum to decide where the use of Animoto will support their learning objectives. It is a great choice for those who need to create videos on the fly. For someone who is complexly new to video and editing, this tooling process is a major resource. No matter if you are a casual user, a professional, or need video editing for YouTube videos, Animoto can cover all needs.

What to expect from the students?

Students who are interested in the course can easily learn the learning topics with Animoto. With the Animoto web 2.0 tool; teachers can remarkably share subheadings or important parts of the topic with their students when switching to a new topic or a new unit. With the Animoto web 2.0 applications, you can prepare it in advance to use during the lecture and use it to explain the crucial parts of the subject. In this way, the most important parts of the subject are permanently learned. With the Animoto web 2.0 applications, teachers can process their lessons more efficiently with interactive materials by creating their course streaming video. With Animoto web 2.0, teachers can

ensure that the students learn permanently by repeating the important points of the subject at the end of the lessons. For project and performance assignments, teachers can ask their students to do them from the Animoto app. Thus, the students; By using their interest in technology, teachers can allow them to have a more fun homework process for them, help develop their creative abilities, and make their students experience the happiness of having produced something.

Animoto step by step

1. Visit <https://animoto.com/> and create your account. It is easy and Quick
2. Select a template or start from scratch
3. Add images and video clips, either by uploading your own or browsing our Getty Images stock library.
4. Create videos using photos and video clips from your phone, camera, Facebook, and more. Choose from over 70 unique video styles
5. Caption photos, trim video clips, add text
6. Easily share on any social media account

Animoto's features

- Independent, active learning.
- Differentiated instruction.
- Real-world applications
- Student engagement.
- Peer collaboration.

3. Explain

The 5E's Model Explain phase focuses on allowing students to synthesise the newly acquired knowledge and ask questions if more clarity is needed. This is a process led by trainers, they should ask students to share what they learned during the Explore process for the Explain phase to be successful before presenting technical knowledge in a more direct way. This is often when educators use video materials, applications for computers, or other aids to improve comprehension.

The explanation phase is an essential, minds-on part of the 5E Model. The explanation phase enables students to describe their understanding and ideas and pose questions about the concepts they have been exploring. Before the educator attempts to provide a deeper explanation, the students must first have the opportunity to express their own explanations and ideas.²⁵

Source: Femxa

Therefore, the Explanation phase has two differentiated and consecutive parts. During the first part, students have a distinctive opportunity to articulate their own understanding of the concepts encountered during the lesson cycle thus far. The educator must be a facilitator and asks and guides students through their explanations of the concepts gained during prior phases. During the second part, the teacher helps focus students' attention on a particular aspect of their exploration experiences by providing scientific explanations, introducing important vocabulary, or discussing and clarifying misconceptions. Formal definitions, notes, and labels are provided. The teacher may also decide to integrate videos, or other visual aides to help with student understanding.²⁶

The explain phase allows educators to help students organise the new knowledge acquired during exploration, as well as provide them with technical and more advanced concepts and ideas to build

²⁵ Ballone Duran, et al., 2004, p. 49

²⁶ Duran, et al., 2011, p. 57

on the student's knowledge. It is important to provide students with an opportunity to organise their knowledge in a way that facilitates the acquisition of new knowledge and skills, and the ability to later apply the lessons learned. When students are given an organisational structure which fits new knowledge, they learn more effectively than when they are left to infer this conceptual structure by themselves.²⁷

Popplet²⁸

Why Popplet?

Popplet is an online tool that offers a digital platform to collaboratively create graphics – synchronously or asynchronously - and to organise our ideas, resources, images, etc. It has multiple functions as we can create virtual walls, concept maps, compilations of resources, timelines, etc. with a visually clear and attractive result. The tool allows users to capture facts, thoughts and images and create relationships between them. Popplet allows students to elaborate visual representations of the knowledge and interconnected concepts they have learned, and educators can use it as a tool to help students better comprehend new knowledge.²⁹

What to expect from your students?

Popplet helps students develop a framework for organising their knowledge about a subject by providing visuals and key vocabulary words. At the same time, it can be used as a pre-lesson strategy by inviting students to share what they already know about a particular concept. After or during the development of the lessons, teachers should ask students to help add to the map as a group. This provides a visual aid for building upon their prior knowledge with the newly acquired information. Popplet can be a useful resource to help students:

- Model how to identify the major ideas or concepts in a text, publication, or lesson.
- Organise their ideas and knowledge in categories, timelines, etc. And include links to resources as they discover more about a specific subject.
- The mapping of concepts constitutes a visual aid to represent and reflect the different interconnections between ideas and concepts.

Popplet step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Make a new Popplet with a Title and a colour and start adding bubbles or “Popples”.
3. Add users to work collaboratively. There are different strokes, and options to add content.
4. Export and share your Popplet.

²⁷ Ruíz-Martín, et al, 2022.

²⁸ Popplet. Retrieved from: <https://www.popplet.com/>

²⁹ Arrausi, J.; Ribosa Martínez, J.. «Driving maps: El uso de mapas mentales para orientar el Aprendizaje Basado en Proyectos a través del Design thinking». Gráfica, 2018, Vol. 6, no 11, pp. 25.

Source: Popplet

Popplet's features

- It is structured in the form of a desktop in which we can create bubbles, "Popplets", in which text, strokes, images, maps, videos and more can be introduced.
- It allows collaborative use in real time.
- It is available in over 100+ languages.

Editable online KWL Grid³⁰

Why Editable online KWL grid?

A KWL grid is a simple visual learning tool that can be filled prior to, during and after learning a new topic or theme to show: What is already known (K), What would like to be known (W) and What has been learnt (L). Children and adults can use this as a working document and share it through collaborative online tools to discuss the subjects with the class or exchange notes with other students.

KWL charts are designed to encourage reading or guide a learning session. This resource can be used as an online resource or in a paper, and it is especially useful for distance learning as it helps to refresh your knowledge about a certain topic or identify knowledge gaps in an easily organised way.

What to expect from your students?

KWL grids allow students to activate prior knowledge, develop a purpose for learning through interests and summarise what they have learned. This allows students to compare new knowledge with what they already know to construct meaning from what they've been learning. This allows them to monitor their learning and identify any knowledge gaps.

By taking notes during each stage of the learning process (current knowledge, questions or areas of interest, and learnings), KWL grids help teachers tailor their lessons to what the students feel they

³⁰ Twinkl. Retrieved from: <https://www.twinkl.es/resource/t-c-6811-editable-kwl-grid>

need to know. Not only does this ensure students are not left with knowledge gaps, but it also makes students feel involved with the learning process.

Editable online KWL grid step by step

1. Download a customizable KWL grid template that adapts to the objectives of your subject. You can download free templates available in multiple languages on platforms such as [Twinkl](#)
2. Give clear instructions for students to individually or collaboratively (e.g., using an online collaborative tool such as Blackboard) fill each field.
3. Collect the grids and use the information to design your lessons around students' knowledge, gaps and misconceptions; or to initiate a discussion between students.

Editable online KWL grid features

Source: Twinkl

- Allows students to organise their knowledge around a specific subject, and their gaps, and to determine their own learning objectives.
- It can be used collaboratively, thus allowing students to compare and exchange their notes.
- It can be customizable to fit each class and subject-specific needs, for the information collected to be more useful for both teachers and students.

Playposit³¹

Why Playposit?

Playposit is an application for creating interactive videos, either selected from YouTube or another platform, or using one of your own, and enriching it with activities, images or comments, establishing a series of pauses during its duration for students to solve, investigate or reflect on it. It allows

³¹ Playposit. Retrieved from <https://go.playposit.com/>

students to enrich the learning process of students by extending and/or consolidating their knowledge in an iterative and fun way. Playposit is an example of a digital tool that allows educators to develop flipped classroom strategies, that is, a teaching method where students become the protagonists of their learning.

What to expect from your students?

Playposit is an intuitive and easy-to-use tool that, with fewer digital skills, allows educators to create powerful learning resources for students, and tailor to the learning objectives and to the diversity of needs of the group of students. Its benefits include the following:

- Promotes deeper and more meaningful learning.
- It favours the development of competences and consolidates knowledge through individual and interactive work.
- It motivates students.

Students will be able to develop their critical thinking and problem-solving skills through the solutions to the different questions. The application helps students to focus on the content and consolidates it by resolving the multiple questions that educators add to the videos. It also allows comments and links to external resources during key moments of the video, that students can access to deepen their knowledge of the subject or resolve their doubts.

Playposit step by step

1. Create an account with the classroom profile.
2. Create an activity by uploading a video and editing it. Multiple types of questions, pauses, and comments can be added.
3. Invite students to register. Students will have to create their profile and access the classroom content by introducing the code number visible in the classroom profile.
4. Set up deadlines to complete the video lessons by students and monitor their progress. The teacher can keep track of what each student has answered.

Playposit's features

- Edit interactive videos for students. Educators can upload videos to include multiple types of questions: multiple choice, fill-blank, short responses, etc. They can also add comments, and insert reflexive pauses or links to other online resources.
- Students can rewind the videos if they need to watch a part they did not understand again.
- Playposit allows you to monitor students' results. Educators can check the results for each student and the time needed to answer them. It is possible to view graphics of the responses and, thus detect if a question is too complicated or poorly explained.
- There is a chat option that allows students to interact with each other while performing the tasks, as well as with the teacher. This allows us to extend the conversation when doubts arise or in order to continue the discussion on an issue and go deeper into it.

Source: YouTube

*Wooclap*³²

Why Wooclap?

Wooclap is a digital tool to create interactive and visually attractive presentations that allow students to participate in the lessons and teachers to view students' responses. With this application, teachers can create presentations or upload their already created ones with PowerPoint or Google Slides and include activities so that they can make students active participants in the lessons, such as surveys, quizzes and more. Students can answer in real-time through any device, including their smartphones, tablets or PCs, and educators will be able to see their responses immediately and use these data to adjust their lessons when necessary.

What to expect from your students?

Introducing interactive activities for students as part of educators' presentations will help to maintain students' focus on the subject being explained. The presentations will be instantly more attractive for listeners both in synchronous and asynchronous lessons. The main benefits of this digital tool are:

- Boost lectures, seminars and conferences.
- Measure the understanding of your learners.
- Stimulate participation and motivate your audience.
- Improve learning and collaboration.

Wooclap step by step

1. Register in Wooclap
2. Create or upload a presentation.
3. Edit the presentation. Educators can include questions, quizzes, and more features to allow students to participate in other ways. There are tutorials available in the same app to guide you through the different possibilities.
4. Save the presentation and use it in your lessons. You can also use it asynchronously by choosing the features that are compatible with this option.

³² Wooclap. Retrieved from: <https://www.wooclap.com/>

Source: Wooclap

Wooclap's features

- Multiple question types to assess the level of understanding of participants, to give your participants the floor, to develop a brainstorming, to develop a competition, and more.
- Anonymous or authenticated participation (with username), to adapt to your audience.
- The answers of participants can be shown in real-time to just the teacher or the audience.
- Students can choose to make questions, like the questions of their peers or respond to them from their devices in real-time.
- The Confuse feature allows students to show they are not following, and the educators can use the data to deepen an explanation.

Pocket³³

Why Pocket?

Pocket is a digital storage tool that allows you to save information offline that you later can review even if you do not have an internet connection. It also allows you to sort the information saved, and it can be accessed by any device. Teachers and students can both benefit from this platform by organising materials for the classroom or interesting website posts, videos, or online articles about a specific subject that can be visited later without connection, to study or work on a project.

What to expect from your students?

Students will be able to easily save the resources searched in their independent research, and to have access to organise resources about specific subjects provided by educators. Pocket allows them to save and organise multiple types of content found online; this will provide students with:

- A safe and accessible way to save online resources.
- An easy-to-use and visually attractive storage application, fostering consulting and reading of useful content.
- Provide clarity and organisation of educational resources through categorization.

³³ Pocket. Retrieved from: <https://getpocket.com/es/>

Source: IOSXtreme

Pocket step by step

1. Create an account. Compatible with PC (extension), smartphone or tablet.
2. Start to save online resources in your account and organise them by categories.
3. Access the pocket to revisit the online content saved and edit your categories.
4. Create a public profile to share your saved resources with students.

Pocket's features

- Storage for videos, articles, websites, photos and anything found online.
- Organisation and visual categorization of the resources.
- Save your Favourites.
- Multiple reading options and the "Text to speech" option, to listen to articles.
- Easy access from any device with and without an internet connection.
- Possibility to synchronise your different devices, so you would have the information saved in all of them.

4. Elaborate

The 5E Model's elaboration process focuses on giving students room to apply what they have learned. It enables them to develop a deeper understanding. To strengthen new skills, trainers can ask students to build presentations or perform additional investigations.

Before evaluation, this stage helps students to consolidate their skills. The exploration phase, meanwhile, allows the students' pre-instructional views to be tested. Based on their exploration in the second phase, students develop a plausible explanation for the phenomenon, with guidance from the trainers. The elaboration phase provides extension activities that enable students to reinforce and use the new knowledge acquired. This phase is characterized by the applications and extension of the concepts learned and skills acquired through conducting new, novel, or additional activities. Essentially, the elaboration phase provides activities for students to apply, develop, extend, or reinforce the newly constructed knowledge and acquired skills (Eng, et al., 2021, p. 173).

In the elaborate stage, students are given experiences to apply their knowledge to new contexts. In other words, the fourth phase, elaborate, seeks to extend and challenge students' understanding of the content they have learned in the previous three phases. Students work through additional activities to develop an even broader and deeper understanding of the content. Students should also directly apply what they learned in the explain phase in a new way (Zackary, 2019, p. 29).

Source: Canva

To better understand, here it is a stimulation for the elaboration stage of the 5E model. Let's suppose that there is a lesson and its topic is the derivation of the formula for the total surface area of a right circular cone. In the elaborate stage, students should apply their gained knowledge by solving several textbook examples calculating the total surface area of right circular cones in pairs (Schallert, Lavicza, & Vandervieren, 2020, p. 11).

During the stage of explanation, learners should articulate their findings, supported by their trainers, who might help learners to find appropriate terms or concepts. Two further essential inquiry features which involve students trying to link their explanation to scientific knowledge as well as communicate and justify explanations could be addressed in the explanation phase. The elaboration phase aims to involve students in additional activities facilitating the transfer to closely related but new situations to generalize concepts, processes or skills. By applying what students have learned during elaboration, students might give priority to evidence in response to questions and formulate explanations from evidence (Schallert, Lavicza, & Vandervieren, 2020, p. 4).

*Kialo Edu*³⁴

Why Kialo Edu

Kialo Edu, or „how to have a classroom debate online”, is the world’s largest argument mapping and debate site, specifically designed for classroom use. Its clear, visually compelling format makes it easy to follow the logical structure of a discussion and facilitates thoughtful collaboration. Kialo’s mission is to promote well-reasoned discussion online, and to that end, it is free for educators to use.

What to expect from your students

With clear visualization of arguments and with powerful, easy-to-use navigation tools, Kialo is the perfect resource to help students master critical thinking and reasoning skills. The students have the opportunity to put their knowledge into action, demonstrate their understanding and engage constructively with each other.

Kialo is a public discussion platform designed to facilitate reasoned debates about complex topics online. Kialo Edu allows educators to curate spaces for students to work through complex subjects together, while giving students the space to ask questions, discuss, and evaluate new ideas. Many academics see Kialo as a solution to the many issues existing in online discourse today.

Kialo Edu step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Invite students: Click on “Teams” – “New Team” – “Name the team” – “Create” – add members by email or sending a link
3. Set up a debate. Click on “Create discussion” and follow the instructions.
4. Assign the discussion to your students.

Kialo’s features

- There can be added a super link to support the given arguments;
- The students can also vote on other students’ arguments. The results of the voting are visible;
- The students can ask for a review;
- The trainer can chat directly with the student;
- The platform offers lesson plans specially made for the trainers;
- Kialo has a discussion tree that is a graphical representation of the debate;
- The trainer can filter the data from their students (e.g. if the trainer wants to follow the progress of a specific student).

³⁴ Kialo Edu. Retrieved from <https://www.kialo-edu.com/tour>

Source: Kialo

This image depicts the discussion tree of the debate. The blue rectangle is the main idea, the debate topic that was chosen by the trainer. The green rectangles represent the pros and the red ones represent the cons.

*Nearpod*³⁵

Why Nearpod

Nearpod is a dynamic student engagement platform with loads of pre-created that the trainer can use with their students. With Nearpod, the trainer can add formative assessments directly into their lesson to drive student engagement. The trainer can start with a resource they already have, or check out the standards-aligned, pre-made lessons. He can get real-time insights into what students know, and access reports after their lessons.

What to expect from your students

A survey of over 2,100 students gives Nearpod high marks on personalization, creativity, and collaboration. The survey reveals that: 89% of students rated Nearpod activities as appropriately challenging. 82% of students feel that they can express themselves creatively using Nearpod, and 42% of students feel that Nearpod allows them to express themselves creatively to a greater extent than other classroom activities. 82% of students feel accountable for the work they do during Nearpod activities, and 50% of students say they participate more when using Nearpod. 73% of students say that during Nearpod activities, they interact with other students in a way that helps them learn.

Nearpod step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Create a lesson (in Google Slides or choose one of their formats).
3. Create activities based on your lesson.

Nearpod's features

The trainer can choose from a variety of exercises, such as:

³⁵ Nearpod. Retrieved from <https://nearpod.com/>

Source: Nearpod

- The trainer can gather data on student understanding by adding formative assessments, simulations, and dynamic media.
- The trainer can add Nearpod to their existing PowerPoints, Google Slides, worksheets, videos etc.
- The trainer can choose from thousands of ready-to-teach, customizable, standards-aligned lessons

What is more, even if there are a lot of free features, for some extra ones they must be paid.

Flipgrid

Why Flipgrid

Flipgrid is a dynamic platform where students can access content and then respond to prompts by creating short videos. The idea behind this educational tool is to use video to create an open platform of discussion and learning that doesn't require a physical classroom to get everyone involved. That makes Flipgrid an ideal remote learning tool as well as a powerful homework-based application for students to use with each other.³⁶

What to expect from your students

This tool has features that trainers in any subject can use to help students connect with each other and share their learning. Once a student creates a video, the rest of the class is able to view and respond to that video. What is more, Flipgrid can be a catch-up solution for students who are absent.

Flipgrid step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Create a classroom: Click on "Let's make a grid".
3. Create an assignment (give the title, select the time, give the instructions and add media resources).

Flip grid's features³⁷

- Students can access Flipgrid from a computer, a tablet or a mobile device.
- The trainer can add a co-trainer (Click on "Add Copilot").
- The trainer can access pre-created assignments (Click on "Disco Library").
- The trainer can see the replies that other students posted to each other.
- The trainer can provide private feedback (video or written).

³⁶ What is Flipgrid and How Does it Work for Teachers and Students?. Retrieved from <https://www.techlearning.com/how-to/what-is-flipgrid-and-how-does-it-work-for-teachers-and-students>

³⁷ Flipgrid Tutorial for Teachers. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aLzX13jw7bw>

- When creating an assignment, the trainer can select the duration of the video.
- The video editor can be used as a board.
- The trainer has a section called “Topic Tip” where they can add tips to help their students in order to give the best answers.
- The trainer can see the hours of engagement of his students.
- Each video consists of a thumbnail (it can be a selfie).
- The video can be edited (add filters, sticky notes, text, and stickers).
- If a student doesn’t feel comfortable recording themselves, they can pixelate their video.

Source: YouTube

Actively Learn

Why Actively Learn³⁸

Actively Learn is an award-winning digital curriculum that drives student engagement and equity through deeper learning. Its flexible features and comprehensive, standards-aligned resources empower trainers to deepen students’ comprehension. Actively Learn allows the trainers to make any video, webpage or text into an interactive learning experience. With Actively Learn, trainers everywhere can help every student achieve deeper learning, improve literacy, and grow.

What to expect from your students

The founders of the app focused on creating an academic program that would promote students’ ability to think critically and reason about complex questions, all in a learning environment where they would be happy and motivated to learn.

Actively Learn step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Set up classes: Click on the + sign next to the *Classes*.
3. Set up assignments (into ELA, Social Studies and Science).
4. Import (an Internet article, a video, a Doc, PDF, Slides).
5. Create a quiz (click in *Insert questions* and choose: *short answer, multiple choice or poll*).
6. Assign: click *Assign*.

Actively Learn’s features

- When creating a class, the trainer can import it from Google Classroom or start a new one.
- Sync the class with other platforms (Google Classroom, Canvas)

³⁸ About us. Retrieved from <https://www.activelylearn.com/about-us>

- The trainer has access to pre-created interactive content.
- The trainer can see how the platform looks from his students` perspective.
- The trainer can make any type of content an interactive text.
- Students can define a word, translate sentences, and hear the text spoken aloud.
- Students can see how their peers responded after submitting their own answers.
- The students can respond to their trainer`s notes.
- Students can highlight any word from the text and add notes.
- There can be added relevant links to some parts of the text.
- The students can't scroll past the question and must answer in order to continue reading.
- When the students choose an answer, they will immediately know if they got it correct or not.
- There are highlighted words and if someone clicks on them, then he can see a note that the trainer left for him.

Source: YouTube

GoConqr

Why GoConqr

GoConqr provides a platform for students to develop, understand and learn key concepts, topics and subject matters. The trainer and the students can create visual study content to aid the learning process and help the students remember the notes better with GoConqr's online study tools: Mind Maps, Flashcards, Study Quizzes and more. The tools allow us to easily develop ideas. Also, the students can even share their study notes with their classmates, easing the trainer's workload and giving him different study perspectives, setting up study goals to help him focus on his study plan.

What to expect from your students

Students can create resources, share them with one another and work collaboratively. They can think about the key elements of a topic and build a Flowchart or Mind Map and get them to present it in a virtual classroom. The trainer can ask the students to create a Flash Card Deck about the topic. Also, the students can build a quiz with GoConqr Quizzes and share it with the other students.

Source: Wikimedia Commons

GoConqr steps by steps

1. Create an account.
2. Create engaging content.
3. Let your student create engaging content.

GoConqr's features

- Test abilities.
- Track progress.
- Connect the Dots with a Mind Map.
- There is an app (on Google Play and App Store)
- Problem-Solving with GoConqr's Flowchart Maker.
- All content created on GoConqr can be shared
- Students can work collaboratively.
- Improving learning by making connections and presenting ideas visually.
- YouTube tutorials are specially made for trainers and students (GoConqr Video).
- GoConqr allows the trainer to try different approaches and get the students to build the content.
- Activity feeds on GoConqr have easy-to-create discussion and comment forums to allow for distance learning and communication.³⁹

³⁹ How to use GoConqr for distance learning and tools that can help you. Retrieved from <https://www.goconqr.com/en/blog/how-to-use-goconqr-for-distance-learning-and-tools-that-can-help-you/>

5. Evaluate

The 5E Model enables both formal and informal evaluation. Trainers will observe their students during this process to see if they have a full mastery of the core concepts and give them feedback on the quality of their work and explanations. Formally, the teacher can also administer a summative evaluation at the end of the learning process. It is also helpful to note when students, based on what they studied, tackle problems in a particular way. Self-assessment, peer assessment, writing assignments, and tests are some of the main types of evaluation that will take place in this phase.

It is important to consider that it is often necessary to implement evaluation activities during other “Es”, meaning that evaluation is not simply something that happens at the end of the learning process, but rather during its entire duration. For instance, numerous explore/explain rotations may be needed before students are ready to transition to the elaboration phase. The teacher may move back and forth several times within the Es or may include an additional engagement prior to starting an elaboration phase. The cycle is very flexible and dynamic.⁴⁰

The evaluation activities are an opportunity to assess students and the knowledge that has been acquired, but this is not its only purpose. Evaluation is an opportunity to provide students with feedback on what they have learned so that they can use the information to improve their learning method or correct misconceptions. Evaluation activities during the learning process also allow teachers to evaluate individual student progress toward achieving learning goals and outcomes.

Evaluation is, at the same time, an important part of the learning journey of students. From a cognitive perspective, evaluation is not only useful for assessing learning and providing timely feedback, the act of retrieving information from long-term memory, which we performed when being tested, is one of the most effective actions for strengthening learning. Retrieving information from memory actually changes memory, increasing the probability of successful retrieval in the future.⁴¹

In conclusion, there are multiple types of evaluations that need to take place during the learning process, both informal and formal. Ongoing formal and informal assessments provide opportunities

⁴⁰ Duran, et al., 2011, p. 53

⁴¹ Ruiz-Martín, et all, 2022.

for teachers to evaluate their instruction, for students to reflect upon their learning, and for students to utilise feedback from the teacher and their peers to evaluate and make improvements to their work. Whereas summative assessments are designed to consolidate students' knowledge and to provide insight into the achievement of the learning objectives related to course level and grade level expectations.⁴²

*Socrative*⁴³

Why Socrative?

Socrative is an application created with the aim of including smartphones in pedagogies. The main function of the app is to manage students' participation in classroom activities in real-time. It allows the development of multiple types of evaluation activities such as tests, quizzes, and projects, and immediately provides feedback to students. Educators can monitor activity results in real-time or use the outcomes of the activity to evaluate students thanks to the reports that Socrative automatically provides.

Source: Socrative

What to expect from your students?

Socrative provides the opportunity to create tailored assessment activities that students can easily respond to from any device and receive immediate feedback with the results obtained in each task by the app, as well as further feedback from the educator. The creative activities are not only useful to evaluate the knowledge gained by students but they can also be used to motivate students,

⁴² University of Missouri, 2015, p.3-4.

⁴³ Bello Pintado, A., & Merino Díaz de Cerio, J. (2017). Socrative: A tool to dinamzye the classroom. *WPOM-Working Papers on Operations Management*, 8, 72–75. <https://doi.org/10.4995/wpom.v8i0.7167>

improve communication between classmates or encourage a spirit of self-learning and self-assessment. Through the test and quizzes of Socrative students can:

- Evaluate their progress or knowledge
- Check their progress and acquired core ideas and competencies against established criteria
- Assess progress by comparing current understanding with prior knowledge
- Answer open-ended questions by using observations, evidence, and previously accepted explanations.

Socrative step by step

1. Register and create a class (with an access code for students).
2. Create activities and tasks for students through the intuitive and easy-to-use app.
3. Set deadlines for students to complete the task and access their results to evaluate them.

Socrative's features

- Creation of 1 public room with a capacity of 50 students
- Possibility to create quizzes, rankings, and multiple question types available (multiple choices, true/false and short answer).
- Space Race assessment: questionnaires with timer.
- Access to the online help centre.
- Real-time access to activities results by the educator.
- Visual sharing of assessment results through the app reports.
- Compatible with most devices and available in multiple languages

*Kahoot!*⁴⁴

Why Kahoot?

Kahoot is a widely popular game-based learning platform that allows users to easily create, share and undertake learning games or trivia quizzes in minutes. Kahoot offers more than 40 million games already created that anyone could access, making it quick and easy to get started.

What to expect from your students?

Students will be able to participate in fun and interactive game activities with the purpose of being evaluated, self-assess their progress regarding a specific subject and consolidating their gained knowledge. Students can also foster their motivation, problem-solving and teamwork competencies through the games that are implemented by the teachers.

⁴⁴ Kahoot! Retrieve from <https://kahoot.com/schools/how-it-works/>

Kahoot step by step

1. Create an account.
2. Create a game from scratch, using the question bank of the app, customising existing tests or using a template. A PIN code will be assigned to the activity to access it.
3. Develop the game with the students, synchronously in a virtual class by sharing a screen through a video conference tool or showing the questions on their devices, or asynchronously to be completed by students in distance learning.
4. Collect the results to evaluate students and provide them with feedback.

Kahoot's features

- Create a quiz in minutes. Possibility to choose from pre-designed templates as the basis or duplicate and edit existing Kahoots.
- Import questions from a spreadsheet or search from millions of questions in our question bank
- Combine multiple Kahoots.
- Add slides with a classic layout, add drawings and images, or insert YouTube videos into questions.
- Host Kahoots live in class or via video conferencing.
- Display questions and answers on students' devices in live Kahoots.
- Assign student-paced challenges for review or homework.
- Get students to play individually or in teams.
- Add multiple types of questions such as multiple-choice or true/false.
- Adjust timer options depending on the complexity of the questions.
- Toggle points between 0, 1000 and 2000.
- Show rankings as visual representations of students' results.

Quizlet⁴⁵

Why Quizlet?

Quizlet is a global learning platform that offers engaging study tools to help people practise and master what they are learning. Teachers can sign up for a free account and enhance their study material and use the in-course assessment features to track students' progress. The app allows students to create study units from scratch or use the existing ones in the app as a starting point, as

⁴⁵ Quizlet. Retrieved from: <https://quizlet.com/es>

well as create a classroom that students can access. Students can also use Quizlet on their own to assess their learning and customize the metrics available to monitor their progress, in a way that is more useful for them.

What to expect from your students?

Quizlet is a popular application with more than 2 million users. It allows us to easily customise educators' and students' study material and adapt it to the characteristics and needs of students. The multiple types of evaluation activities that can be created foster students' motivation and engagement with the learning content and with their peers, through the sharing of study tools and group activities.

Quizlet step by step

Register

1. Create study units with your own material and maintain them actualize.
2. Create a classroom (that students can access with a link or code) and add your units. This is online and available in the Teacher mode pay version.
3. Implement the activities and provide feedback to students based on their responses.

Source: Quizlet

Quizlet's features⁴⁶

The evaluation activities that can be created are:

- Create flashcards that can be words + meanings or words + images. You could also make question-and-answer cards. Students could also make their own flashcards if they want.
 - Learn – Read the meaning/look at the image and type the correct word.
 - Spell – Type the target word you hear.
 - Test – An auto-generated mix of written, multiple choice, and true and false questions based on the vocabulary set.
 - Match/Gravity – a couple of games using the vocab set. The match works well on an interactive whiteboard.
 - Live – play a live game with multiple participants.
- Create learning units and classes that students can join.
- Track students' progress as well as actualize your study material and activities based on the feedback that provides their responses.

Eduflow – Peer Review

Why Eduflow?

Eduflow is a very easy-to-use platform with great accessibility from any type of device that allows one to design and develop complete online courses with personalised features and activities. Between its activities, we find question-and-answer exercises, virtual debates, group tasks, self-

⁴⁶ Exploring the Features of Quizlet. The Knowledge Network for Innovations in Learning and Teaching (KNILT), 2018, University at Albany's School of Education. Retrieved from: <https://knilt.arcc.albany.edu/Unit 3: Exploring the Features of Quizlet>

assessment activities and more. It is especially relevant because it has a Peer review option that allows students to review each other works and share feedback and ideas.

What to expect from your students?

The Peer Review option of this application will encourage students to collaborate and help each other, give feedback to other students, as well as reflect on their own learning by reading and assessing other students' work. The app will foster their motivation and engagement, support them to learn to work independently, help them understand the intention behind the work they do, and improve their critical thinking capabilities.

Eduflow Peer Review step by step

1. Creating an Eduflow Account and Course.
2. Adding Content and Submission Activities.
3. Creating a Peer Review Activity.
4. Creating Feedback Reflection and Scoring Activities.
5. Developing and Incorporating Feedback.

Eduflow Peer Review's features

- Space for students to submit their work, and multiple types of assignments are possible.
- Establish deadlines
- Allow students to review a defined number of other submissions using a rubric presented in a question format.
- Enable different options to review and score students' work. Open or close-ended multiple-choice questions can be introduced, as well as a grading option.
- Possibility to enable an additional academic review to be provided by the educator.
- Possibility to add the self-review to the peer review option.
- Use the Feedback Reflection option for students to read, reflect and incorporate the feedback received from their peers.
- Possibility to resubmit the work after the feedback from peers is incorporated.

Source: Eduflow

Recommendations for instructional designers and facilitators

Plan: Think about what content, information or tasks you need to give to your students. You can create a plan of what you want to achieve in every lesson and at the end of the week. Challenge your students to create their own content and engage in self-directed learning. It is important that the plans allow students to be creative and engage in different tools to deliver what they have learned.

Students' needs: Remember students learn by “doing” and with distance learning your face-to-face time is limited, so the more “doing” tasks you can give them the better.

Be interactive: When working alone or at a distance, the main challenge can be focus and boredom. The mind can easily wander if it is not challenged and engaged when students are working alone. We all know variety is the spice of life so change it up, and use multiple different learning-focused tools, it helps that a student can use different tools, even if they are covering the same topic, the more angles we can explain a concept or topic from the better a student will understand it.

Communicate: Feedback from students' peers and trainers encourages a student to keep going and keep trying, every effort should be encouraged and communicated in a positive and supportive way. Comments and discussion forms can be used in an online environment to support your students, in the same way, you encourage and support them in the classroom.

Be prepared: When you are planning an online class, you will need to master effective classroom management skills. Set clear expectations about the class start and end time, and as you deliver the class, keep it within the planned time. Ensure you have an appropriate number of concepts to cover within your allocated time. Usually, activities and discussions end up taking more time than initially planned. If your session spans longer than sixty minutes, consider including breaks in your session to ensure your learners can move away from the computer and return with increased attention. Take care of the timing of the small group activities and discussions to ensure they are progressing within the allocated timelines.

Remember: At the beginning of each session, remind the students of the expectations for classroom engagement. Encourage learners to participate in classroom discussions using virtual chat options and questions and answers.

Get along with technology: Test your audio, video, and screen-sharing options at least 30 minutes before the start of class. During the class, if you run into a technical issue, do not panic. Turn off your video and audio and check the system. Fix the problem. Inform the learners there is a technical issue and ask them to wait online or reconnect at a set time. Once you resolve the issue and feel more relaxed, turn the audio and video on, and take control of the lesson calmly and confidently.

Reflect: After each session, reflect on the strengths and areas in need of improvement. Celebrate your strengths and continue to hone in on the areas you can improve.⁴⁷

⁴⁷ Sriharan, A. Teaching Online: Tips for Engaging Students in Virtual Classrooms. Med.Sci.Educ. 30, 1673–1675 (2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-020-01116-7>

Course evaluation quiz

- 1) Today's learners grew up with digital technologies and we call them as
 - a) **Digital natives**
 - b) Digital immigrants
 - c) Digital people
- 2) According to Kapp Is using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning, and solve problems.
 - a) Digital learning
 - b) **Gamification**
 - c) Game
- 3) is a free platform where educators can engage their students in thoughtful discussions.
 - a) **Kialo Edu**
 - b) BookWidgets
 - c) PlayBrighter
- 4) is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems.
 - a) Data Analysis
 - b) **Artificial Intelligence**
 - c) Gamification
- 5) Which of the following is considered one of the four categories of competencies when it comes to using artificial intelligence?
 - a) Social media marketing
 - b) Media literacy
 - c) **Engineering and design thinking**
- 6) While using the 5E Model for digital facilitation, which of the below is the phase that allows the students to think and understand how they did something?
 - a) Engagement
 - b) Exploration
 - c) **Explanation**
- 7) in the educational context is a concept that includes the measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their context in order to understand and optimise learning and the environments in which it occurs.
 - a) **Data analysis**
 - b) Research methodologies
 - c) Creating courses
- 8) In which phase of the 5E Model will trainers observe their students during this process to see if they have a full mastery of the core concepts and give them feedback on the quality of their work and explanations.
 - a) Editing
 - b) Exploration
 - c) **Evaluation**
- 9) Which of the below is an area of competence included in the DigCompEdu framework?
 - a) **Professional Engagement**
 - b) Physical Resources
 - c) Internet Safety
- 10) Which of the below tools may be used for evaluating students?
 - a) Animoto
 - b) **Kahoot**
 - c) Pocket

Use cases for digital facilitation in VET

This guide was created to support VET teachers and trainers in digital facilitation. The course uses DigCompEdu as a baseline framework for defining the six areas of competence for VET digital facilitators. Moreover, it introduces gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis as key elements in assisting VET digital facilitators. Each of these three elements is exemplified with five digital tools. The guide then uses the 5E Instructional Model to explain how different gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis-assisted tools may be used to engage, explore, explain, elaborate and evaluate VET students.

This textbook guide was effectively used to create an online course for VET teachers and trainers, integrated into an open digital community. The online course was piloted internally by course designers and project partner organisations prior to being tested by more than 90 vocational education teachers and trainers from Turkey, Romania and Spain. Thanks to the methodologies and tools included in this course, these educators became better digital facilitators.

The project's ambition is to reach as many VET educators and help improve their digital facilitation awareness, knowledge, skills and attitudes. The following use cases serve as examples of how to integrate the learning outcomes of this course into day-to-day teaching and training activities.

Gamification use case

Yeliz is a VET teacher at a school who has been utilizing digital gamification tools in her classes. By leveraging these tools, she has been able to add an element of fun and engagement to her lessons. For example, she has been able to assign quests and challenges to her students, which they can then compete to complete. This helps to boost their motivation to learn and also encourages collaboration among them. Additionally, Yeliz has been able to incorporate interactive digital elements, allowing her students to explore concepts in a more immersive manner. In doing so, she has made the learning process much more enjoyable for them.

Yeliz leveraged PlayBrighter, a gamification platform, to give her students the opportunity to progress through levels and acquire rewards. This allowed them to become more engaged in the material and motivated to learn. Additionally, PlayBrighter incorporates leaderboards, which Yeliz used to create a sense of healthy competition among her students. This helped them stay motivated and sharpen their skills in a fun way. Finally, the platform is also equipped with data analysis tools which Yeliz has been using to track the progress of her students and measure their understanding of the material. This has enabled her to understand their learning patterns and better identify areas where they are struggling, allowing her to tailor the lesson plans accordingly.

Yeliz used PlayBrighter to facilitate a variety of activities related to digital citizenship. She was able to utilize the platform's gamification tools to engage her students in interactive quizzes and polls to help them better understand concepts such as online safety, responsible use of technology, and cyberbullying. Additionally, she could also award badges and assign quests to further incentivize students to pursue digital citizenship knowledge and skills. Lastly, she was able to track the progress of her students using the data analysis tools provided by PlayBrighter, allowing her to identify areas where they needed additional assistance. All in all, this enabled Yeliz to provide a more enjoyable and effective learning experience for her digital citizenship class.

Artificial intelligence use case

In his classes, Leonard, a teacher at a nearby VET high school for economics, has begun utilising AI-assisted technologies. He has been able to give his students a more individualised learning experience by utilising these technologies. For example, he has been able to program the AI not only to assess the educational needs of each individual student but also to create individualized lesson plans and activities based on their strengths and weaknesses. Additionally, Leonard has been leveraging the AI's real-time analysis capabilities to monitor progress and identify areas in need of improvement. This has enabled him to adjust the lesson plan accordingly, resulting in higher student engagement and better comprehension of the material.

Leonard used Alexa Skill Blueprints to create interactive lessons for his students. He created a range of 'blueprints' which contained content, questions and audio clips that his students could interact with. Students could ask Alexa questions about the topics they were learning, and Alexa would provide audio clips with information about the topic as well as answer questions. This enabled Leonard to provide a more interactive and engaging learning experience for his students.

Leonard developed an engaging eco-tourism course using Alexa Skill Blueprints. He developed "blueprints" that detailed various eco-tourism locations, activities, and conservation initiatives. Students could ask Alexa questions about the topics they were learning, and Alexa would provide audio clips with information about the topic as well as answer questions. Leonard also used Alexa Skill Blueprints to create quizzes and tests that students could take to test their knowledge on the topic. As such, Leonard to provide his learners a more involved and interesting learning experience.

Data analysis use case

A nearby VET training centre employs Jaime as a trainer. He has been assisting his students in learning more efficiently by employing data analysis tools. Jaime is able to give his students insightful information on their class results by using these methods. He can pinpoint opportunities for development, for instance, by examining important curricular components like test scores and presentations. Jaime can also find any connections between the curriculum and student performance using the data. This enables him to choose instructional materials with better knowledge, giving lesson plans more flexibility. Overall, Jaime's integration of data analysis tools into his teaching approach has proven to be a useful improvement.

Jaime used the classroom response system Plickers to enable his participants to engage in real-time polls and tests. As a result, he was able to receive immediate feedback from his learners on their comprehension of the subject and swiftly modify his lesson plan to suit their level of knowledge. The Plickers data also allowed Jaime to pinpoint students who required more assistance in certain subjects. Because of Jaime's ability to offer each student the right amount of assistance, the subject matter was better understood overall.

Jaime led several practical entrepreneurship-related activities using Plickers. He was able to use the surveys and tests to inquire about new company trends, consumer preferences, and how technology is affecting commercial endeavours. Additionally, Jaime was able to identify areas of agreement or disagreement among his learners using the data from the Plickers surveys and gain a deeper understanding of how they see these topics. This gave him the opportunity to modify the lesson plans to match their preferences and offer insightful advice on these subjects. Overall, this offered his trainees a comprehensive awareness of the entrepreneurial environment and a competitive advantage when beginning their own businesses.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to determine the contribution of gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis tools to the development of the use of digitalization in VET education. With the sudden outbreak of Covid-19, face-to-face education has been disrupted in many countries as well as it is in partner countries; Türkiye, Romania and Spain. It is necessary to benefit from the advantages and opportunities of Information Technologies, web tools in distance education, and virtual education without the need for pandemics and natural disasters.

The desk research done with target groups in partner countries showed us that most VET teachers and trainers adopt gamification, artificial intelligence and data analysis tools to their courses especially to improve students' engagement and increase their participation in the course. Teachers are keen on finding the right digital tools and the associated training methods to meet trainees' expectations, learning needs and styles. Digital facilitators encouraged collaborative work by setting up communication channels, such as WhatsApp groups, Moodle forums, and shared Google docs. Learning via Zoom is also an opportunity for students to work together.

In the national reports of partner countries (Türkiye, Spain and Romania) we came to the conclusion that both teachers and students have easily adapted to digital and distance education and use web tools and apps in their courses. Teachers and students are active users of web tools in education in the field of Gamification, Data Analysis and AI. Teachers prepare their lesson plans interactively and students engage in the courses via different types of tools. In interactive courses, students learn from each other and their collaborative, creative and communication skills improved.

Gamification tools, AI and data analysis tools and apps are used to improve student's learning motivation and engagement. With the developed skills and competences VET teachers and VET students with improved language and digital skills are what education, business and industrial sector really need. From the national reports of the partner countries, we assumed that VET teachers and students in project partner countries are almost on the right track to what we aimed for in this project.

VET teachers and trainers developed their teaching and training methods and learned innovative technics and tools. The need for digital education technologies while training promoted innovation in education. The use of instructional technology improved and optimized students' knowledge and substantially motivate them to continue their learning and stimulate their creativity and passion. Technology in education boosted variety and increased the diversity of learning environments and opportunities and enhances the quality of the learning experience by making class content more varied and accessible to almost every individual learner.

About the partner organisations

Osmaniye Provincial Directorate of National Education is a regional governmental organisation. Osmaniye covers an area of 3,767 km² and its population is 538.759 inhabitants. Osmaniye province is divided into 7 districts. The organisation takes care of the planning and coordination of all kinds of educational and training activities from preschool to the end of secondary school, vocational high schools, technical schools, adult education, and other institutions &

centres in its region. Osmaniye MEM organised many courses since 2019 for teachers to renew themselves and over 5000 teachers benefited from these courses. The project experts in the Research and Development office in our Institution have carried out the training of teachers, local or regional authorities and NGOs on preparing and managing EU projects. With these training activities more than 600 students, teachers and managers actively took part in EU projects.

In 1999, Femxa Formación S.L.U started its business trajectory as a training company, setting as its main objective to provide innovative training solutions to growing market needs and to anticipate future training needs arising in society. Since then, it developed consulting work specialising in Value Added training solutions, whose focus is on the development of projects of tailored training, aimed to solve the specific needs of customers more efficiently, which

has allowed us to reach a landmark in the field of training. Our reason for being is to build training solutions that provide job opportunities for people and improve the competitiveness of organisations. In the last 20 years, we have trained more than 64.000 unemployed, 40.000 people aged over 45, 15.800 unemployed young people under 30.

TEAM4Excellence (T4E) is a Romanian association aiming to improve the quality of life through education, research, and consulting activities. To address societal challenges, T4E provide learning opportunities and career advice for social inclusion, development, and employability of people, and equip trainers with key competences and skills to foster personal as well as professional development.

Within 30+ EU-funded projects, the association produces and transfers innovation, experience and know-how through cooperation with domestic and international partners. By hosting events, training courses and conferences, T4E strengthens collaboration between people, supports organisations and bridges gaps between generations. The wide expertise in management enables T4E staff to provide consultancy to large companies and SMEs using EFQM Model and Business Model Canvas.

Bibliography

A Learning Cycle for All Students. Modifying the 5E instructional model to address the needs of all learners. Emilio Duran, Lena Duran, Jodi Haney, and Amy Scheuermann. The Science teacher, March 2011. (p. 56 to 60).

About us. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.activelylearn.com/about-us> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Alexa Skills Blueprints. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://blueprints.amazon.com/home> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Bosova, L.L. (n.d.), Sets of digital educational resources for textbooks included in the Federal list as a way of mass introduction of ICT in the educational process of the Russian school. Information and communication technologies in education.

Brown, D. H. (1990). Language assessment: Principles and classroom practices. London: Longman
Chatfuel review. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.chatbots.org/chatfuel> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Edtechroundup BookWidgets: Design Interactive and Engaging Digital Content [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <http://www.edtechroundup.org/reviews/bookwidgets-design-interactive-and-engaging-digital-content> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Empowering Students: The 5E Model Explained [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://lesley.edu/article/empowering-students-the-5e-model-explained> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Eng, T. O., Devi, G., Charanjit, K. S., Md, N. I., Norwaliza, A. W., Mohamed, T. B., & Siew, W. T. (2021, February 1). The 5th inquiry learning model: its effects on the learning of electricity among Malaysian students. doi:10.21831/cp.v40i1.33415

Flipgrid Tutorial for Teachers. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aLzX13jw7bw> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Getting started. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://docs.chatfuel.com/en/articles/2568024-getting-started> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

How Does AI Work With Product Recommendation Systems? [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.smarthint.co/en/ai-product-recommendation-engine/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

How to use GoConqr for distance learning and tools that can help you. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.goconqr.com/en/blog/how-to-use-goconqr-for-distance-learning-and-tools-that-can-help-you/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

IBM SkillsBuild. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <http://www.skillsbuild.org/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

IMS, (2002). IMS Reusable Definition of Competency or Educational Objective - Best Practice and Implementation Guide, Version 1.0 Final Specification, Retrieved from http://www.imsglobal.org/competencies/rdceov1p0/imsrdceo_bestv1p0.html

Khaled M. Alhawti (2015). Advances in Artificial Intelligence Using Speech Recognition. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1106879

Kialo Edu. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.kialo-edu.com/tour> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

DigiFacT - 2020-1-TR01-KA226-VET-097638
www.digifactproject.com

- Mdsg About the 5E Instructional Model cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://www.mdsg.umd.edu/topics/k-12-lesson-plans/about-5e-instructional-model> [Accessed 16/12/2022]
- Miao, F., & Holmes, W. (2020, December). International Forum on AI and the Futures of Education. Developing Competencies for the AI Era. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. <https://bit.ly/3BOzZgT>
- Moore, R.L. (2019). The role of data analysis in education: Possibilities and limitations. In B. Khan, R. Corbeil, & M. Corbeil (Eds.), *Responsible Analytics and Data Mining in Education: Global Perspectives on Quality, Support, and Decision-Making* (pp. 101-118). Routledge, New York. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.4324/9780203728703-8>
- Nasseh, A., Mhouthi, A., & Erradi, M. (2013). How to evaluate the quality of digital learning resources? *International Journal of Computer Science Research and Application*, 3(3), 27–36. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260392089> [How to evaluate the quality of digital learning resources](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260392089)
- Nearpod. [cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://nearpod.com/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]
- Owston, R. (2017). Empowering Learners Through Blended Learning. *International JI. on E-Learning*, 17. <http://www.yorku.ca/rowston/IJEL2017.pdf>
- Punie, Y., editor(s), Redecker, C., *European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators: DigCompEdu*, EUR 28775 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2017, ISBN 978-92-79-73718-3 (print),978-92-79-73494-6 (pdf), doi:10.2760/178382 (print),10.2760/159770 (online), JRC107466.
- Purdue University, “What is instructional design?”. [cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://online.purdue.edu/blog/education/what-is-instructional-design> [Accessed 16/12/2022]
- REDECKER, C. (2017). *European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators: DigCompEdu*. (n.d.). (No. JRC107466). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/178382>
- Ruiz-Martín, H., Bybee, R.W. The cognitive principles of learning underlying the 5E Model of Instruction. *IJ STEM Ed* 9, 21 (2022). [cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-022-00337-z> [Accessed 16/12/2022]
- Schallert, S., Lavicza, Z., & Vandervieren, E. (2020, October 15). *Towards Inquiry-Based Flipped Classroom Scenarios: a Design Heuristic and Principles for Lesson Planning*. doi:10.1080/0020739X.2020.1831092
- Semenovskikh, T., Volkodav, T., & Shlyapina, S. (2021). *Digital Learning Resources In Teaching*. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2021.07.02.25>
- Skov, A. (2016). *What is digital competence?* Retrieved from <https://digital-competence.eu/dc/front/what-is-digital-competence/>, 16.Dec.2022.
- Sriharan, A. Teaching Online: Tips for Engaging Students in Virtual Classrooms. *Med.Sci.Educ.* 30, 1673–1675 (2020). [cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-020-01116-7> [Accessed 16/12/2022]
- Teachlearning What is Kahoot! and How Does it Work for Teachers? [cited 2022 Apr 24]Retrieved from <https://www.techlearning.com/how-to/what-is-kahoot-and-how-does-it-work-for-teachers> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

The 5-E Instructional Model Actively Engaging Students with Science. STEM Literacy 2015. University of Missouri – ReSTEM Institute. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from:

http://www.stemliteracyproject.org/uploads/3/7/0/6/37068337/5-e_overview.pdf [Accessed 16/12/2022]

The 5E Instructional Model: A Learning Cycle Approach for Inquiry-Based Science Teaching Lena Ballone Duran Bowling Green State University, OH, USA. Emilio Duran The University of Toledo, OH, USA. The Science Education Review, 3(2), 2004. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from:

<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1058007.pdf> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

The 5E lesson model: Engage& Explore Discover <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/Teaching-a-5-E-lesson-Watch-as-a-teacher-goes-through-all-the-5-Es> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Transform your teaching with a chatbot (2021, June 13). [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.cta.org/educator/posts/transform-teaching-with-chatbot> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

University of Santiago, “What is instructional design?”. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://onlinedegrees.sandiego.edu/what-is-instructional-design-examples/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Volkodav, T. (2021). Digital learning resources in teaching. European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences EpSBS. Conference: International Scientific and Practical Conference Education in a Changing World: Global Challenges and National Priorities. DOI: 10.15405/epsbs.2021.07.02.25

Vuorikari, R., Punie, Y., Carretero Gomez S., Van den Brande, G. (2016). DigComp 2.0: The Digital Competence Framework for Citizens. Update Phase 1: The Conceptual Reference Model. Luxembourg Publication Office of the European Union. EUR 27948 EN. doi:10.2791/11517

Wengroff, J. (2019, 21 June), “What is the Magic Triangle: Aligning Learning Objectives, Training Activities and Assessment Methods”. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://getsynapse.com/blog/what-is-the-magic-triangle-aligning-learning-objectives-training-activities-and-assessment-methods/> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

What is Flipgrid and How Does it Work for Teachers and Students?. [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from <https://www.techlearning.com/how-to/what-is-flipgrid-and-how-does-it-work-for-teachers-and-students> [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Yambi, T. A. C. (2018). ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION IN EDUCATION. Research Gate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342918149_ASSESSMENT_AND_EVALUATION_IN_EDUCATION

Zackary, W. D. (2019). The Purposeful Position of PhET Simulations in a 5E Model: A Rationale for PhET. Retrieved from Education and Human Development Master's Theses: [cited 2022 Apr 24] Retrieved from https://digitalcommons.brockport.edu/ehd_theses/1237 [Accessed 16/12/2022]

Appendix 1 Evaluation quiz check sheet

1a

2b

3a

4b

5c

6c

7a

8c

9a

10b